

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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CONTENTS

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- 自我实现价值观作为人生道路自组织的调节器
Self-Realization Values as Regulators of Life-Path Self-Organization
Kravchuk Nadezhda Yurievna, Dyakov Sergey Ivanovich 9
- 战争创伤性截肢退伍军人的临床和心理特征。心理治疗的目标和任务
Clinical and psychological features of war veterans with traumatic limb
amputation. Goals and tasks of psychotherapy
Mansurova Maria 17
- 人工智能信任作为社会心理学概念
Trust in Artificial Intelligence as a Socio-Psychological Concept
Yakhudina Tatiana Semenovna, Vorobyova Kseniya Andreyevna 25

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

- 现代俄罗斯学校教育设计基础
Foundations of designing educational activities in a modern Russian school
Masharova Tatyana Viktorovna 34
- 航海数学发展的主要方向
Main directions of development of mathematics in navigation
*Pankina Svetlana Ivanovna, Orlov Daniil Igorevich,
Antonov Artemii Olegovich*. 42
- 东方国家教育机构与企业之间的互动
Interaction between educational institutions and enterprises
in Eastern countries
Baymurzin Ruslan Khamitovich, Valeeva Roza Alekseevna 49
- 通过人工智能集成实现学员能力发展的协同方法
Synergetic Approach to Cadets' Competencies Development
through AI Integration
Filonenko Victoriya Aleksandrovna 56
- 将基础外语词汇融入高年级学前儿童体育教育过程中
Integration of elementary foreign language vocabulary in the process of physical
education of senior preschool children
Fedorova Svetlana Yurievna 62

列夫·托尔斯泰原创教育思想对当今教育的活力 The Vitality of Leo Tolstoy's Original Pedagogical Ideas for Today's Education <i>Danilova Irina Sergeevna, Danilova Yulia Sergeevna</i>	70
大学环境中适应性体育文化的发展前景 Prospects for the development of adaptive physical culture in the university environment <i>Vasiltsova Varvara Alekseevna, Dudus Alexander Nikolaevich</i>	77
虚拟现实技术作为培养青少年安全行为模式的工具 Virtual Reality Technologies as a Tool for Developing Safe Behavioral Patterns in Adolescents <i>Kytin Sergey Pavlovich</i>	82
开发基于 Vue.js 框架的分子热力学虚拟实验室， 旨在提高学生的认知兴趣。 Development of a virtual laboratory for molecular thermodynamics based on the vue.js framework as a means of enhancing students' cognitive interest <i>Sidorenko Pavel Eduardovich</i>	88

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

19世纪英国在亚洲的地缘政治利益 Geopolitical interests of Great Britain in Asia in the 19th century <i>Chebotarev Alexey Igorevich</i>	95
---	----

CULTURAL STUDIES

数字时代的音乐新闻：流派结构与功能系统的具体特征 Music journalism in a digital age: genre structure and the specifics of function system <i>Sorokina Tatiana Evgenievna</i>	101
不同的沉默他人：跨文化交流对学术话语的挑战 Dissimilar Silent Others: Cross-Cultural Communication Challenges for Academic Discourse <i>Moshnyaga Elena Viktorovna, Hussain Irfan</i>	110

ART HISTORY

创意产业作为发展家庭休闲文化的平台 Creative industries as a platform for the development of family leisure culture <i>Rybasova Yulia Yuryevna, Khanipova Dinara Radikovna</i>	119
---	-----

技术创新在文化遗产保护与诠释中的应用： 乌兹别克斯坦国家应用艺术与手工艺史博物馆的经验 Technological Innovations for the Preservation and Interpretation of Cultural Heritage: The Experience of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan <i>Ashurbaeva Sitora Abdukarimovna</i>	127
当代乌兹别克斯坦的区域现代主义与文化认同：布哈拉文化空间中的泽利姆汗·赛义德诺夫艺术遗产 Regional Modernism and Cultural Identity in Contemporary Uzbekistan: The Artistic Heritage of Zelimkhan Saidjanov in the Cultural Space of Bukhara <i>Ashurbaeva Sitora Abdukarimovna</i>	135

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

古俄语中主动和被动现在分词作为谓语的用法（ 与闪米特语系语言的比较） The use of active and passive present participles as predicates in Old Russian (in comparison with Semitic languages) <i>Baluta Anastasia Anatolyevna</i>	144
Holonyms 作为中世纪高级建筑和行政文化的证据 （基于 Abu' l-Fazl Bayhaqi 的“Tarikh-i Bayhaqi”和 Ahmad Tusi 的“Aja' ib al-Makhlukat wa Ghara' ib ib al-Mawjudat”的材料） Holonyms as evidence of the high architectural and administrative culture of the Middle ages (based on materials from Abu'l-Fazl Bayhaqi's “Tarikh-i Bayhaqi” and Ahmad Tusi's “Aja'ib al-Makhlukat wa Ghara'ib al-Mawjudat”) <i>Rustamshozoda Shahboz Rustam</i>	150
科尔涅·丘科夫斯基作品的塔吉克语译本中的双关语和词语创造 Puns and word creation in translations of Korney Chukovsky's works into Tajik <i>Saidova Diloru Rustamovna</i>	164

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

科学和人文认知术语改进和细化的基本原则 Basic principles for the improvement and refinement of the terminology in scientific and humanitarian cognition <i>Chernyakova Natalia Stepanovna</i>	172
--	-----

当代塔吉克哲学家论伊本·西那哲学遗产的作用和重要性 Contemporary Tajik philosophers on the role and importance of the philosophical legacy of Ibn Sina <i>Sodiqi Nasiba Nurullozoda</i>	178
从跨文化方法论的角度探讨伊本·西那哲学观点的某些方面 On some aspects of Ibn Sina's philosophical views in the light of intercultural methodology <i>Dinorshoeva Zarina Musoievna</i>	184
教育是文化和意义的对话 Education as a dialogue of cultures and meanings <i>Dudnikova Elena Evgenievna, Intymakova Larisa Grigorievna</i>	192
意义翻译的现象学 The phenomenology of the translation of meanings <i>Safonova Ekaterina Aleksandrovna</i>	196
数字文化语境下女性权力原型的转变：一个哲学维度 Transformation of the archetype of woman in power in the conditions of digital culture: a philosophical dimension <i>Koulakova Vladislava Vitalievna</i>	200

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

俄罗斯足球场建筑 Architecture of football stadiums in Russia <i>Kosirnikov Victor Sergeevich</i>	206
莫斯科地下体育设施通风参数的合理性 Justification of ventilation parameters of underground sports facilities in Moscow <i>Kosirnikov Victor Sergeevich</i>	218

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自我实现价值观作为人生道路自组织的调节器
**SELF-REALIZATION VALUES AS REGULATORS OF LIFE-PATH
SELF-ORGANIZATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了自我实现价值观作为生命路径自我组织意义调节器的作用。自我实现并非仅仅局限于特定能力的培养、外在成就或主观幸福感的体验，而是被诠释为一个协调个人潜能、存在性自我决定、活动、人际关系和社会贡献，并最终形成连贯生命轨迹的过程。理论分析表明，个人自我实现价值观是一个动态的价值和意义调节系统，它将内在意图和能力与其社会意义的体现联系起来。本文提出了一个精炼的概念框架，其中自我实现价值观介导了从个人资源到人生选择，再从人生选择到客观化活动和参与社会生活的转变。文章特别关注心理自我组织、反思、意志调节以及对经验的回顾性意义建构的作用。结论认为，人生道路的完整性不仅取决于资源或目标的拥有，还取决于一个人的能力、选择、行动体现以及对行动结果的解读之间的一致性。

关键词：个人自我实现，自我实现价值观，人生道路，自我组织，价值与意义调节，存在选择，行动，社会贡献。

Abstract. *The article examines self-realization values as meaning regulators of life-path self-organization. Self-realization is not reduced to the development of particular abilities, external achievements, or the subjective experience of well-being. It is interpreted as a process in which personal potential, existential self-determination, activity, relationships, and social contribution are coordinated in a coherent life trajectory. Theoretical analysis makes it possible to define personal self-realization values as a system of dynamic value-and-meaning regulators that connect internal intentions and capacities with their socially*

meaningful embodiment. The article presents a condensed conceptual framework in which self-realization values mediate the transition from personal resources to life choice and from life choice to objectified activity and participation in social life. Special attention is paid to the role of psychic self-organization, reflection, volitional regulation, and retrospective meaning-making of experience. It is concluded that the integrity of the life path depends not only on the presence of resources or goals, but also on the coherence between what a person is capable of, what he or she chooses, what he or she embodies in activity, and how he or she interprets the results of this embodiment.

Keywords: *personal self-realization, self-realization values, life path, self-organization, value-and-meaning regulation, existential choice, activity, social contribution.*

Introduction

The problem of personal self-realization occupies a special place in contemporary psychology because it combines several lines of analysis: personal potential, meaning in life, agency, activity, psychological well-being, and the organization of the life path. In the humanistic tradition, self-realization is associated with the tendency toward growth, autonomy, openness to experience, and full functioning [1; 2]. In existential psychology, it is connected with freedom, responsibility, the search for meaning, and the need to make a choice under conditions that cannot be completely controlled by the individual [3; 4]. In the activity approach, self-realization is revealed through the active transformation of the world and the objectification of human powers in the products of activity [5; 6]. Studies of the life path emphasize that a person is not only a bearer of individual qualities, but also a subject who organizes life time, decisions, relationships, and biographical continuity [7].

At the same time, the theoretical description of self-realization remains fragmented. In some studies, it is interpreted mainly through internal prerequisites: abilities, motivation, autonomy, or personal resources. In other studies, it is described through visible achievements, productivity, professional success, or social recognition. In a third group of studies, it is brought closer to psychological well-being and the subjective evaluation of life. Each of these perspectives is important, but none of them fully explains how internal possibilities become meaningful choices, how choices are transformed into sustainable activity, and how the results of activity are included in the person's coherent life path.

This difficulty makes it necessary to introduce a mediating category: personal self-realization values. In the present article, they are understood as a system of dynamic value-and-meaning regulators that orient a person from internal intentions and potential capacities toward their socially meaningful embodiment in activity, relationships, and the life path. Such an understanding does not reduce values to

a list of desirable qualities or to stable preferences. It treats them as regulators that connect potential, choice, action, and the interpretation of life experience.

The aim of the article is to substantiate the general regulatory role of personal self-realization values in the self-organization of the life path.

Materials and Methods

The study is theoretical and conceptual in nature. It was carried out using integrative theoretical analysis, synthesis, and structural-dynamic reconstruction. Theoretical analysis included the selection, comparison, and generalization of psychological and philosophical sources concerning self-realization, value-and-meaning regulation, agency, the life path, self-organization, and personal development. The method of theoretical synthesis was used to correlate the propositions of humanistic, existential, activity, subject-centered, systemic, and synergetic approaches.

The methodological basis of the study includes the humanistic approach to self-realization and full functioning [1; 2], the existential approach to meaning, freedom, responsibility, and choice [3; 4], the activity approach to the objectification of intentions in socially meaningful activity [5; 6], the subject-centered approach to the life path [7], the theory of values as motivational regulators [10], self-determination theory [11], the eudaimonic approach to psychological well-being [12; 13], and the approach to psychic self-organization and conscious self-regulation of the subject [14]. Systemic and synergetic ideas were used to describe the life path as an open, developing, and self-organizing system [15; 16].

Since the article is based on published scientific sources and does not include empirical procedures with participants, special ethical approval was not required. The main limitation of the study is its conceptual character: the proposed interpretation requires further empirical verification, including the operationalization of self-realization values and the study of their relationships with psychological well-being, resilience, value orientations, and life-purpose orientations.

Results and Discussion

Self-realization values as a mediating construct. Values in a broad sense define what is considered desirable, significant, and worthy of effort. Meaning formations express the subjective significance of events, goals, relationships, and actions. Goals organize the direction of activity. Activity gives intentions an objective form. Psychological well-being reflects the quality of a person's experience of life and development. Self-realization values connect these phenomena into a single dynamic system: they indicate not only what is important for the person, but also how what is important can be embodied in life.

This distinction is significant because self-realization cannot be adequately described only as achievement. A person may achieve a socially approved result but experience it as alien, accidental, or disconnected from his or her own life meaning. Conversely, a person may possess strong abilities and rich inner resources but fail to

translate them into a stable life decision or into activity that has personal and social value. Therefore, the key question is not simply whether a person has potential or whether he or she has achieved something, but whether potential, choice, activity, and meaning are integrated into a coherent life trajectory.

The concept of personal self-realization values allows this question to be formulated more precisely. These values regulate the movement from internal possibilities to existential self-determination and from self-determination to social embodiment. They perform a selective, motivational, orienting, and interpretive function. The selective function is expressed in the fact that a person distinguishes those possibilities that are subjectively and ethically significant. The motivational function supports the person's readiness to act. The orienting function connects action with the desired image of life. The interpretive function makes it possible to include the achieved result in the meaning structure of the life path.

Life-path self-organization. The life path is not a mechanical sequence of events. It becomes psychologically coherent only when past experience, present decisions, future expectations, activity, and relationships are connected by a value-and-meaning logic. In this sense, self-organization of the life path is not identical to external planning or arbitrary self-control. It is a more complex process in which a person coordinates resources, meanings, choices, actions, and the interpretation of the results of these actions.

The approach to psychic self-organization is especially important here. S. I. Dyakov and S. N. Kostromina describe psychic self-organization as an information-semantic system involved in conscious self-government of the subject [14]. This position makes it possible to consider personal development not as a simple accumulation of qualities, but as the ordering of internal meanings, regulatory processes, and modes of interaction with the world. In relation to self-realization, psychic self-organization means that personal resources acquire developmental significance only when they are included in a system of meaning, choice, and activity.

At a general level, the proposed structural-dynamic model distinguishes three analytical planes of self-realization values. The first plane concerns internal resources and intentions that make self-realization possible. The second concerns the transformation of these resources into meaningful life self-determination. The third concerns the embodiment of value choice in activity, relationships, social contribution, and cultural or professional continuity. These planes should not be understood as rigid stages that always follow one another in a fixed order. Rather, they are mutually connected dimensions of the self-organizing life path.

The first plane emphasizes the importance of cognitive, emotional-volitional, and motivational readiness for self-realization. It includes the development of knowledge about oneself and the world, the ability to regulate one's emotional states, and the readiness to initiate action. However, resources by themselves do not

yet constitute self-realization. If they are not included in a conscious value choice, they remain unrealized possibilities. This explains why the transition from potential to self-determination is a central theoretical problem.

The second plane is associated with the person's existential choice. It is here that the individual correlates internal possibilities with responsibility, meaning, and the image of the desired life. Reflection allows alternatives to be seen not only as practical options, but also as values. Volitional effort makes it possible to sustain the tension of choice under conditions of uncertainty. Existential choice transforms the passive possession of resources into a personally significant direction of life.

The third plane concerns objectification. In the activity approach, a person realizes himself or herself not only through inner experience, but also through deeds, products of activity, relationships, and participation in social life [5; 6]. For this reason, self-realization requires embodiment. A choice that is not translated into activity remains incomplete, while activity that is not connected with inner meaning risks becoming formal, alienated, or externally imposed. Social contribution, care, professional work, creativity, mentoring, and participation in meaningful communities can become forms through which the person's inner value choice acquires objective existence.

The integrity of self-realization. The central characteristic of the described process is integrativity. The issue is not the isolated development of separate qualities, but the coherence between internal resources, meaningful choice, activity, relationships, and the subsequent interpretation of experience. Local incoherence may arise when knowledge is not connected with emotional maturity, when motivation is not supported by volitional regulation, or when activity is disconnected from personal meaning. Systemic incoherence may arise when a person possesses resources but does not make a life choice, makes a choice but cannot embody it, or is externally active but does not experience this activity as his or her own.

This interpretation also clarifies the relationship between self-realization and psychological well-being. Eudaimonic well-being includes personal growth, purpose in life, autonomy, environmental mastery, positive relations, and self-acceptance [12]. These characteristics are close to self-realization, but they do not exhaust it. Self-realization includes not only the quality of subjective experience, but also the dynamic transition from potential to choice and from choice to objectified activity. Thus, well-being may be considered one of the important correlates and outcomes of self-realization, but not its complete equivalent.

The same applies to value orientations. Basic values describe general motivational priorities and principles of behavior [10]. Self-realization values are more specific because they regulate the way in which a person's capacities, choices, and activities are included in a coherent life path. They do not replace general values; rather, they specify how general value priorities are transformed into the personal logic of self-realization.

The proposed framework has several theoretical implications. First, it allows self-realization to be analyzed not as a final state, but as a process of life-path organization. Second, it connects subjective meaning with activity and social participation. Third, it makes it possible to distinguish between the presence of personal resources and their real inclusion in life self-determination. Fourth, it provides a basis for further empirical study of different types of self-realization, including harmonious, resource-fragmented, existentially blocked, and externally productive but internally alienated variants.

Further research may include the development of a diagnostic instrument for studying personal self-realization values. Such an instrument should not only register the intensity of separate value orientations, but also evaluate the coherence between resources, choice, activity, and meaning. It is also important to study the intergenerational dynamics of self-realization values, since different generations may differ in the way they understand autonomy, achievement, social contribution, family and professional continuity, and the acceptable balance between individual development and responsibility to others.

Conclusion

Personal self-realization values can be understood as dynamic value-and-meaning regulators that connect internal intentions and capacities with their socially meaningful embodiment in activity, relationships, and the life path. They mediate the transition from potential to existential self-determination and from self-determination to objectified participation in social life.

The self-organization of the life path is not a linear accumulation of resources or a simple sequence of achievements. It is a process of coordinating resources, meanings, choices, actions, relationships, social contribution, and the retrospective interpretation of experience. The coherence of these elements determines whether self-realization becomes an integral line of personal development or remains fragmented.

The structural-dynamic interpretation proposed in the article makes it possible to distinguish self-realization from related phenomena such as value orientations, achievements, psychological well-being, and life meaning. It also creates a theoretical basis for further empirical research, including the operationalization of self-realization values, the analysis of their integrativity, and the study of their intergenerational dynamics.

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战争创伤性截肢退伍军人的临床和心理特征。心理治疗的目标和任务
**CLINICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF WAR
VETERANS WITH TRAUMATIC LIMB AMPUTATION. GOALS
AND TASKS OF PSYCHOTHERAPY**

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摘要：地雷爆炸伤导致的创伤性截肢会使战斗老兵的社会心理康复和重返平民生活变得更加复杂。该问题的现实意义在于，经历完全截肢或部分截肢的老兵人数不断增加。处于这种境况的老兵面临着尤为艰难的处境——失去肢体带来的心理创伤与战斗压力交织在一起。本研究旨在识别正在接受假肢治疗的地雷爆炸伤后创伤性截肢老兵的临床和心理特征，确定心理治疗工作的主要目标和方向，并分析韧性与创伤后应激障碍特征之间的关系。

关键词：创伤后应激障碍，韧性，焦虑，抑郁，截肢。

Abstract. *Traumatic limb amputation after a mine-explosive injury complicates the socio-psychological rehabilitation and readaptation of combat veterans to civilian life. The relevance of the problem is due to the growing number of veterans who have experienced complete amputation or have amputated limbs. Veterans in such conditions face a particularly difficult situation – a combined psychological trauma due to the loss of a limb and the stress of combat. The purpose of this study was to identify the clinical and psychological characteristics of veterans with traumatic limb amputation after a mine explosion injury who are undergoing prosthetics, to determine the main objectives and targets of psychotherapeutic work, and to analyze the relationship between resilience and the characteristics of post-traumatic stress disorder.*

Keywords: *post-traumatic stress disorder, resilience, anxiety, depression, amputations.*

A person faced with the loss of a limb often experiences acute grief associated with the loss of a ‘part of themselves,’ a profound shift in life orientation, future prospects, and a state of helplessness (1). For veterans returning from war, traumatic amputation is part of their combat experience; therefore, they require

comprehensive support – including medical, social, and psychological assistance. Veterans require social reintegration into civilian society, the development of new ways of interacting with their environment, and adaptation to life with physical disabilities. The wounded confront challenges related to self-identification, future professional engagement, and the development of long-term prospects.

Psychogenic reactions in combatants are typically at a pre-nosological level and are characterized by borderline states such as depression and neurotic reactions (7). Post-traumatic stress disorder in the majority of combatants manifests partially (presented by individual clinical symptoms). All symptoms can be conditionally categorized as psychogenic physical (phantom pain syndrome), cognitive (decreased rationality, memory, neuroplasticity, and learning capacity), and emotional (apathy, depressive state, increased irritability, and hypervigilance).

The main difficulties encountered by patients are presented below, based on complaints at the initial consultation and data from the clinical interview (Table 1).

Table 1. Ranked list of main complaints and difficulties, faced by patients with limb loss

Complaints	Distribution, %
Phantom pain syndrome	96
Traumatizing memories	80
Sleep disturbances (difficulty falling asleep)	76
Dreams about traumatic events	53
Reaction to sudden sounds and triggers	34
Outbursts of irritation and aggression	19
Depressed mood and reduced emotional tone	15

Primarily, veterans report complaints of phantom pain and sleep disturbances characterized by difficulty falling asleep and dreams with traumatic content (deceased comrades are seen in dreams). Patients also report heightened emotional reactions to trigger sounds (for example, the sound of a passing electric wheelchair resembles the flight of a drone). In their dreams, patients often see themselves as completely healthy and whole, just as they were before the injury and amputation.

The most frequently observed clusters of posttraumatic stress disorder symptoms include intrusion (obsessive memories, dreams) and arousal (hypervigilance, anxiety, irritability). Patients also report thoughts and fantasies about returning to the combat zone to assist their comrades (“There is a completely different life there; you are fully engaged every day, you feel a sense of purpose...”).

The condition of veterans following physical injury is further complicated by an overall severe physical state, partial or complete loss of motor functions, prolonged hospitalization, and extended waiting periods for prosthetic fitting. The

transition from a military environment to civilian life, as well as the rehabilitation and recovery process after sustaining injuries, constitutes one of the most challenging periods for patients. During this period, veterans are in great need of support and psychological assistance.

Research objective

The objective of the study was to identify the clinical and psychological characteristics of veterans who have experienced traumatic limb amputation and are at the stage of prosthetic fitting, to determine the primary objectives and targets of psychotherapeutic intervention, as well as to analyze the relationship between resilience and the characteristics of post-traumatic stress disorder.

Research Methods

A study was conducted on the psychological characteristics of 25 veterans who were wounded during combat operations, followed by limb amputation according to medical indications. The age range of the patients was 25–45 years. According to the nature of their injuries, the patients can be divided into two groups: those with amputation of one or two lower limbs, and those with amputation of one or two upper limbs. A clinical-psychological examination was conducted in wounded patients, consisting of a clinical interview, as well as a set of psychological instruments – the HADS anxiety and depression scale, a PTSD screening questionnaire, the Impact of Event Scale, the Luscher color test, and Maddi’s resilience test. The psychological state of the patients and characteristics of the emotional sphere were assessed, along with the level of resilience and personal resources across three scales – engagement, control, and risk-taking.

Data processing was conducted using Statistica 12 software, employing univariate measures and nonparametric Spearman-Kendall correlation analysis.

Results

As a result of the examination and clinical interview, the following symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder were identified, as previously mentioned: sleep disturbances (difficulty falling asleep), dreams related to traumatic events, depressed mood, and recurrent recollections of the traumatic experience. For patients, limb loss is perceived as part of the overall combat experience, most often representing the conclusion of this stage of life. Some patients reported a sense of relief due to the inability to continue military service (“finally, it’s all over”), whereas others expressed a desire to return, primarily motivated by reluctance to leave their comrades-in-arms, a sense of duty, and personal significance.

According to the examination results, 20% of patients following limb amputation due to mine-explosive injuries experience high levels of personal anxiety in daily life (the ratio of patients with pronounced versus low anxiety among 25 respondents is presented in Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Graphical depiction of the proportion of patients with subclinically expressed and low anxiety.

Subclinically expressed depression, characterized by apathy, low mood, and severe fatigue, was identified in 44 % of patients; symptomatology associated with PTSD was observed in 36 % (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Proportion of patients without depression symptoms and those with subclinically expressed depression

Fig. 3. The ratio of patients without PTSD symptoms to those with a high probability of developing PTSD.

Simultaneously, a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) was found between anxiety levels and a high risk of PTSD (correlation coefficient 0.4), and between depression levels and a high risk of PTSD (correlation coefficient 0.6), indicating two primary types of post-traumatic disorder manifestation – anxious and asthenic (depressive). It was also found that the higher the overall level of life resilience (including control, involvement, and risk acceptance), the lower the levels of depression and PTSD symptomatology (a significant negative correlation at $p < 0.05$). The Lüscher color test showed that patients often prefer the color black, placing it in the first position, which may indicate internal protest and a stressful state during rehabilitation.

Discussion of Results

The results of the examination, combined with patients' reported complaints, indicate a complex psychological condition in some cases, predominated by anxiety or depressive components, as well as signs consistent with the development of post-traumatic stress disorder. According to clinical interviews, the development of PTSD in such cases is primarily associated with combat experiences endured (death of comrades, life-threatening situations, distressing imagery, and extreme survival experiences in a life-threatening combat environment). Certainly, unlike typical wounds, limb amputation is a factor that complicates the process of rehabilitation, recovery, and return to civilian life.

Various PTSD symptoms were observed in 36% of combatants with amputations. According to some studies, wounded individuals with amputations are less likely to experience post-traumatic stress disorder compared to those without amputations. This is associated with the experience of guilt in combat-related PTSD, where limb amputation becomes a form of ‘atonement’ (6).

According to the examination results, a high level of resilience and fundamental internal stability, as well as the ability to cope with stress, are factors that prevent the development of PTSD. Resilience is understood as a system of core beliefs about oneself, the world, and one’s relationships with the world, which facilitate coping with stress and enable maintaining resilience in crisis situations (5). Patients with high resilience demonstrate a greater ability to control situations, are more engaged in the recovery process during a crisis, and cope more effectively with situations with uncertain outcomes. Post-traumatic growth may be more pronounced in such patients (a condition in which a crisis situation leads to a re-evaluation of life values and priorities, resulting in personal growth). According to research, veterans with amputations exhibit a higher level of post-traumatic growth compared to veterans without amputations, which appears to be related to more complex physical rehabilitation and a reconsideration of the experienced trauma (2).

The data obtained indicate that premorbid personality characteristics – such as psychological resilience, involvement (engagement in ongoing events and interest in life), a sense of control (the belief that one is the author of one’s own life), and acceptance of risk (willingness to act despite the absence of guarantees of success)—reduce both the risk and severity of the PTSD symptom complex. Meanwhile, the predisposition to PTSD may manifest predominantly with either anxious or depressive components and may be further complicated by somatic conditions, cognitive impairments (resulting from traumatic brain injuries and concussions), and alcohol dependence.

A significant feature of wounded patients with amputations is the disruption of the body schema following limb loss, accompanied by phantom pain syndrome of varying intensity. Therefore, acceptance of the new body (adaptation to life with a prosthesis), development of a future perspective under new conditions, and reduction of overall stress and tension levels become crucial targets of psychotherapeutic and psychocorrective work.

Psychotherapeutic Features of War Veterans with Amputations

Psychotherapeutic work with veterans who have undergone limb amputation following mine-explosive injuries is crisis-focused – addressing the consequences of combat stress, managing post-traumatic symptomatology, complex emotions, and facilitating adaptation to civilian life. It is important to recognize that limb loss is not only a physical but also a profoundly traumatic psychological issue; therefore, great emphasis is placed on constructing a life perspective, envisioning the future, and

forming internal personal supports. Existential issues (awareness of life's finitude, freedom and responsibility, and the meaning of life) often emerge in psychological work with combat veterans. The life journey following injury, severe trauma, and amputations is often experienced by patients as a 'second life.' In this context, combat experience is perceived as an 'initiation,' a period during which the extremes of physical and mental capacities were engaged – capabilities the individual may not have even been aware of (8). Awareness of this can arise during psychotherapeutic work, where the individual can relive and reframe the experienced events, perceiving them within the broader context of their entire life perspective. This process is influenced by common factors in psychotherapy (regardless of the therapeutic approach)—a positive interpersonal connection, the opportunity to be heard, and the ability to undergo emotional release in the presence of a significant other.

A key focus involves working with physical sensations such as phantom pain syndrome or other sensations localized in the area of the missing limb. Phantom pain has a complex nature (neuropathic, psychogenic), and its intensity can be alleviated through muscle relaxation, autogenic training, and suggestion-based psychotherapy (4).

Combat veterans require comprehensive medical and psychological care that promotes their integration into peaceful society, aids in overcoming the consequences of combat stress, and broadly adjusts the psyche to a 'safe mode of functioning.'

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人工智能信任作为社会心理学概念
**TRUST IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AS A SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONCEPT**

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摘要

本文探讨了在社会心理学语境中界定“人工智能信任”概念内涵的问题。该主题的现实意义在于，人工智能正日益广泛地融入青年群体的教育、信息获取、职业活动以及日常生活实践之中。在既有科学文献中，对人工智能的信任常常与技术可靠性、技术接受度、使用便利性或对数字工具的一般性积极态度相混同。本文旨在揭示人工智能信任的心理学内涵，并论证其作为独立社会心理学现象的结构特征。

研究表明，对人工智能的信任并不能被简化为对其回答的无条件接受。它是一种有条件的心理态度，包括对技术有用性的认可、对其局限性的理解、对结果进行核查的意愿、用户自主性的保持，以及对人类在智能系统应用过程中所承担责任的意识。本文提出，应对人工智能的生态性信任理解为一种对技术的平衡性态度：在这种态度下，用户能够利用人工智能的功能与优势，但并不将最终决策权完全交由人工智能。

关键词：人工智能；人工智能信任；心理态度；青年群体；数字环境；用户自主性；信息核查；人类控制；生态性信任。

Abstract. *This article examines the problem of defining the content of the concept of "trust in artificial intelligence" in a socio-psychological context. The relevance of the topic is connected with the active integration of AI into the educational, informational, professional, and everyday practices of young people. In scientific literature, trust in AI is often conflated with technical reliability, technology acceptance, ease of use, or a general positive attitude toward digital tools. The purpose of this article is to reveal the psychological content of trust in artificial*

intelligence and to justify its structure as an independent socio-psychological phenomenon. It is shown that trust in AI is not reduced to the unconditional acceptance of its responses. Rather, it represents a conditional psychological attitude that includes recognition of the usefulness of the technology, understanding its limitations, willingness to verify results, preservation of user autonomy, and awareness of human responsibility for the application of the intelligent system. The article proposes considering ecological trust in AI as a balanced form of attitude toward technology, in which the user utilizes the capabilities of artificial intelligence but does not transfer the right to make the final decision to it.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, trust in artificial intelligence, psychological attitude, youth, digital environment, user autonomy, information verification, human oversight, ecological trust*

引言

人工智能的广泛传播正在改变人们获取信息、学习、沟通以及作出决策的方式。现代人工智能系统能够提供现成答案、生成建议、解释复杂主题、创作文本和图像，并形成分析性结论。由此，人工智能逐渐介入那些以往主要归属于人类思维活动的过程之中。

这一变化在青年群体中表现得尤为明显。年轻用户在完成学习任务、查找信息、翻译、文本处理、生成创意以及解决日常问题时，越来越多地求助于人工智能。与此同时，一种新的心理情境随之产生：个体从一个内部运行逻辑在很大程度上并不透明的系统中获得结果。用户能够看到答案，但并不总是理解该答案是如何形成的，也不总是清楚其可信程度。

因此，对人工智能的信任问题不仅是技术问题，也是社会心理学问题。它与控制、责任、批判性思维、自主性以及用户评估数字结果适用边界的能力密切相关。在这一意义上，对人工智能的信任不能仅仅理解为对算法准确性的相信。它形成于用户与技术互动经验、对技术可靠性的认知、情感安全感、核查意愿以及对潜在风险的意识之间的交汇处。

在科学文献中，信任传统上被视为一种在不确定性和风险条件下产生的关系。尼克拉斯·卢曼将信任与社会复杂性的降低联系起来：主体虽然无法完全预见其决策后果，却仍然采取行动[1]。罗杰·迈耶、詹姆斯·戴维斯和戴维·舍曼将信任界定为：基于对另一方能力、诚实性和善意的期待，愿意在与其关系中接受自身脆弱性的心理准备[2]。这些理论路径对于分析人工智能具有重要意义，但同时也需要重新阐释，因为人工智能并不是人类意义上的主体，也不承担道德责任。

关于自动化系统信任的研究表明，当人们将某项技术感知为可靠、可预测且有用时，便更倾向于依赖该技术[3]。然而，现代人工智能系统可能生成看似有说服力、逻辑上也较为连贯的回答，但其中仍可能包含错误、不完整信息或事实扭曲。这就带来了过度信任的风险，即用户在未经核查的情况下直接接受系统结果。

本文的目的在于揭示并概念化“人工智能信任”作为社会心理学现象的内涵。

为实现这一目的，本文提出以下研究任务：考察理解信任的主要理论路径；区分人工智能信任、技术可靠性和技术接受度；描述人工智能信任的结构；在理论分析和青年样本经验数据的基础上，提出该概念的定义。

理解人工智能信任的理论基础

信任产生于主体面对不确定性的情境之中。个体并不掌握全部信息，也无法事先计算所有可能后果，但仍然需要作出决定并采取行动。对于人工智能的分析而言，这一点具有特别重要的意义，因为用户在与人工智能互动时，几乎总是处于系统透明度不足的条件之下。

人工智能系统在界面层面可以是清晰易懂的，但在运行机制层面却可能保持复杂和封闭。用户看到的是结果，却并不总是理解系统究竟如何得出这一答案。因此，对人工智能的信任并非源于对技术的完全了解，而是源于用户对其有用性、可靠性、可核查性和可控性的主观评价。

约翰·李和卡特里娜·西指出，对自动化系统的信任是适当依赖这些系统的必要条件，但过度信任或信任不足都可能导致错误[3]。拉贾·帕拉苏拉曼和维克托·赖利描述了自动化误用的风险：过度使用、拒绝使用以及错误使用自动化系统[4]。这些风险同样直接适用于人工智能：用户可能不加批判地接受系统回答，也可能因害怕错误而完全拒绝技术，或者在超出适用边界的情境中使用它。

凯文·霍夫和玛苏玛·巴希尔指出，对自动化的信任取决于系统特征、用户特征和情境特征[5]。在人工智能的情境下，系统因素包括准确性、可解释性、稳定性和回答质量；用户因素包括数字能力、互动经验、焦虑水平和批判性；情境因素则包括应用领域、错误代价以及外部核查的可能性。

因此，对人工智能的信任并不是绝对的。同一名用户可能在文本翻译或创意搜索中信任人工智能，却在医学、法律或金融问题上不信任它。这意味着，人工智能信任具有条件性和情境性。

还需要特别注意“可信人工智能”与用户心理信任之间的区别。在国际文件中，可信人工智能通常通过合法性、伦理性、透明性、安全性、可靠性、公平性、问责性以及人类监督等原则来描述[6]。这些特征对于人工智能的开发和治理十分重要，但它们并不能完全解释具体用户在真实互动情境中如何感知技术。因此，应当将人工智能的心理信任与技术可靠性以及制度层面的技术“可信性”区分开来加以考察。

基于上述理论路径，人工智能信任可以被理解为一种多成分的社会心理态度。其结构包括对技术能力的评价、情感态度、行为准备、核查行为、用户自主性的保持以及对人类责任的认知。人工智能信任的概括性结构见图1。

图1 - 人工智能信任的社会心理学结构

资料来源：作者基于理论分析自行绘制。

图1 - 人工智能信任的社会心理学结构

资料来源：作者基于理论分析自行编制。

如图1所示，人工智能信任具有复杂结构。认知成分反映用户对人工智能能力与局限的理解；情感成分体现焦虑感、安全感和警觉性；行为成分表现为使用人工智能的意愿；核查成分涉及信息比对和寻找来源的实践；主体性成分体现用户自主性与控制感；伦理—制度成分则反映人类对智能系统开发和应用所承担责任的意识。这样的理解使我们能够将人工智能信任视为人与数字智能环境互动的一种调节方式，而不是对技术的简单积极评价。

人工智能信任及其相关概念

在数字技术研究中，“技术接受”这一概念被广泛使用。弗雷德·戴维斯的模型通过感知有用性和感知易用性解释技术接受[7]。UTAUT模型则在此基础上补充了绩效期望、努力期望、社会影响和促进条件等因素[8]。这些模型能够解释用户为何开始使用某一数字工具，但并不能完全揭示人工智能信任的内涵。

年轻人可能会积极使用人工智能，因为它速度快、方便，并且有助于学习。但这并不意味着他会无条件信任所获得的回答。使用与信任相互关联，但并不等同。技术接受可以是实用性的：“我使用它，是因为它方

便。”而信任则具有更深层的心理意义：“我承认这一结果可能成为我行动的依据。”

为了更准确地揭示本文所研究的概念，有必要将人工智能信任与若干相近范畴区分开来，因为这些范畴有时会被当作可互换概念使用。相关区分见表1。

表1
人工智能信任与相关概念的区分

概念	基本内容	与人工智能信任的区别
人工智能的技术可靠性	系统能够稳定、正确且可预测地运行的属性	描述的是技术本身的特征，而不是用户的心理态度
技术接受	使用数字工具的意愿	可能与便利性和有用性有关，但并不必然意味着对人工智能结果的信任
使用便利性	与系统互动的简单性和舒适性	反映用户体验的舒适程度，但不能说明用户的批判性水平
数字能力	有意识且安全地使用数字工具的技能	是形成自觉信任的条件之一，但并不等同于信任本身
人工智能信任	在保持核查、自主性和责任意识的前提下，有条件地接受人工智能结果	包括对有用性、风险、控制、真实性以及适用边界的评价

资料来源：作者基于理论分析自行编制。

上述区分表明，人工智能信任并不等同于技术可靠性、使用便利性或技术接受。它所描述的是用户面对智能系统结果时所持有的心理立场。一个人可能经常使用人工智能，但只是在有限程度上信任它；也可能认为该技术十分方便，但仍然核查每一个回答；还可能具备较高的数字能力，却在错误代价较高的情境中保持谨慎。

因此，对人工智能的信任不应被理解为用户对技术的喜爱程度，也不应被理解为其使用频率，而应被视为调节用户对人工智能结果态度的一种机制。

界定人工智能信任的经验基础

为揭示人工智能信任的内涵，本文采用了青年样本的实证研究数据。研究共有242名受访者参与，年龄范围为15至35岁。研究分析了人工智能使用频率、对其结果的信任自评、负面使用经验、回答核查方式、焦虑水平、控制感以及在与智能系统互动时保持自主性的意愿。

研究结果显示，青年群体高度卷入人工智能使用实践。大多数受访者会定期使用人工智能：每天使用、每周使用数次或每月使用数次。最常使用

的是通用文本类人工智能服务、具备人工智能功能的翻译工具以及图像生成工具。这表明，青年群体首先将人工智能视为一种学习支持、信息支持和沟通支持工具。

然而，较高的使用频率并不意味着无条件信任。最常见的回答是“既信任，也不信任”，选择这一选项的受访者占42.7%。对人工智能结果表达积极信任的参与者占39.4%，表示不信任的占10.3%，另有7.5%的受访者难以回答或未使用人工智能。这一分布说明，青年群体对人工智能的信任具有矛盾性和双重性。

这种矛盾性可能表明，青年群体正在形成一种更加成熟的技术态度。受访者承认人工智能的有用性，但同时也意识到其回答需要核查。换言之，对人工智能的信任是建立在保留怀疑、уточнение 信息和核对资料可能性的基础上的一种有条件接受。

与人工智能互动中的负面经验是本研究发现的重要经验结果。相当一部分受访者曾遇到错误回答、事实扭曲、信息不足、技术故障或访问问题。这说明，对人工智能的信任并不是在系统完全无误的条件下形成的，而是在用户真实体验到其局限性的背景下形成的。

核查实践具有特别重要的意义。部分受访者会将人工智能回答与一个或多个来源进行比对；部分受访者会要求系统提供链接或论证依据；也有部分受访者会认真核查信息。然而，也有相当一部分参与者表示不会核查人工智能回答。这使我们能够划分出生态性信任与对系统非批判性依赖之间的重要边界。

如果用户信任人工智能，但仍然保留核查、自主性和控制，那么这种信任可以被视为成熟的信任。相反，如果用户在不核查的情况下接受回答，尤其是在重要情境中如此，那么信任便会转化为对算法结果的风险性依赖。

相关分析表明，自评信任与综合性人工智能信任心理指数、人工智能使用频率以及对技术焦虑水平的降低存在关联。这证实，人工智能信任不仅包括对技术有用性的理性评价，也包括用户在互动过程中对安全性、可理解性和可控性的情感体验。

人工智能信任的结构与定义

基于理论分析和实证数据，可以区分出人工智能信任的若干组成部分。

认知成分与用户对人工智能能力和局限性的认识有关。情感成分反映用户面对技术时的焦虑、兴趣、安全感或警觉性。行为成分表现为用户求助于人工智能并在活动中使用其结果的意愿。核查成分与回答比对、来源搜索和信息 уточнение 有关。主体性成分反映用户自主性和控制感的保持。伦理—制度成分则与这样一种理解有关：人工智能的责任由创造、引入和应用它的人、组织及专业共同体承担。

这种理解有助于避免两种极端。第一种极端是技术乐观主义，即将人工智能视为几乎不会出错的知识来源。第二种极端是技术恐惧主义，即将人工智能完全视为威胁。在二者之间，存在一种更具建设性的立场 - 生态性信任。这种信任建立在有用性、批判性和责任意识的平衡之上。

人工智能的生态性信任，是指用户能够利用人工智能的功能与优势，同时保持批判性思维、自主性以及最终决策负责的一种态度形式。它取决于任务类型、错误代价、核查可及性、用户能力水平以及人类控制程度。在低风险情境中，信任可以更加开放，例如在生成想法或准备初步计划时。而在责任较高的领域 - 教育、医学、法律、金融、心理援助 - 信任则应当是有限的，并需要伴随专家核查。

基于上述分析，可以提出如下定义。

人工智能信任 是主体面向智能系统的结果、建议或行为所形成的一种社会心理态度。它表现为在感知人工智能有用性和能力、与其互动经验、理解其局限性、愿意核查所获信息、保持用户自主性以及承认人类对最终决策承担责任的基础上，对人工智能结果进行有条件接受。

在这一定义中，有几个原则性要点尤其重要。第一，信任被理解为一种态度，其中包括用户的知识、体验、行动和期待。第二，信任具有条件性，取决于具体情境、任务以及错误可能造成的后果。第三，核查实践并不是信任的反面，而是成熟信任结构的一部分。第四，信任意味着人的自主性得以保持：人工智能可以提供帮助，但不应完全取代人的独立判断。第五，人工智能结果应用的责任仍然由人、组织或专业共同体承担。

结果讨论

本文提出的人工智能信任理解，拓展了既有关于人与数字技术互动的分析路径。经典信任理论表明，信任产生于不确定性条件下，并与个体在信息不完整时仍然采取行动的意愿有关[1; 2]。自动化研究则强调，信任应当与系统能力相匹配，并且不应转化为非批判性的依赖[3; 4; 5]。

人工智能创造了一种新的情境，因为它经常以语言化、对话化并且在外部表现上似乎“理性”的形式与用户互动。用户可能会觉得系统理解了问题、进行了推理，并像人一样作出了回答。然而，人工智能仍然是一种技术系统，它基于算法和数据生成结果。因此，在心理层面上，重要的是不要将人际关系中常见的信任形式直接转移到人工智能之上。

获得的实证数据表明，青年群体积极使用人工智能，但同时保持着与错误、信息不完整和核查必要性相关的矛盾态度。因此，人工智能信任并不是一个线性过程，即使用频率的增加并不会自动导致信任提升。它更可能是在一种经验过程中发展起来的，在这一过程中，有用性、错误、核查以及对技术边界的逐渐理解相互结合。

本文所提出路径的科学新颖性在于，将人工智能信任视为一个独立的社会心理学概念，而不是技术可靠性或技术接受的某种特殊形式。这一路径不仅能够描述信任水平，也能够描述信任的质量。如果高信任伴随核查和控制，它可以是成熟的；但如果高信任表现为对人工智能回答的无条件接受，它就可能是有风险的。

本研究的实践意义在于，所提出的理论路径可以用于数字素养和人工智能素养教育项目的开发。青年群体不仅需要学习如何使用人工智能工具，

还需要理解其局限性，掌握信息核查、来源分析、错误识别以及保持自身作者立场的能力。

结论

人工智能信任是一种复杂的社会心理学现象，不能被简化为系统的技术可靠性、使用频率或对数字技术的一般性积极评价。它形成于不确定性情境之中：用户从智能系统中获得结果，并需要判断该结果是否可以使用、是否需要核查，以及谁应当对最终决策承担责任。

本文分析表明，人工智能信任包括认知、情感、行为、核查、主体性以及伦理一制度成分。其成熟形式并不表现为对人工智能回答的无条件接受，而是表现为有意识地、批判性地、负责任地使用技术的能力。

本文提出，将人工智能信任定义为主体在理解人工智能局限性、愿意进行核查、保持用户自主性并承认人类责任的前提下，对人工智能结果、建议或行为进行有条件接受的一种社会心理态度。

生态性人工智能信任这一概念具有特别重要的意义。它能够描述人与智能系统之间一种平衡的互动形式：在这种形式中，技术扩展了用户的能力，但并不取代其思考、批判性和责任。这样的理解可以成为后续研究、诊断方法开发以及教育项目设计的基础，从而促进青年群体形成与人工智能负责任互动的能力。

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现代俄罗斯学校教育活动设计基础
**FOUNDATIONS OF DESIGNING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN
A MODERN RUSSIAN SCHOOL**

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摘要： 学生教育一直是教育过程中不可或缺的一部分。这类活动在培养年轻一代融入社会和公共生活、塑造其道德伦理品质方面发挥着主导作用。

本文探讨了这一问题的近期历史发展，并将其与当前教育实践的现状进行了对比。

关键词： 基本人格文化；优先民族理念；俄罗斯文化历史准则。

Abstract. *The education of students has always been an integral part of the educational process. This type of activity has played a leading role in preparing the younger generation for social and public life, and in shaping their moral and ethical qualities.*

In the proposed article, the author examines recent historical aspects of this issue and draws parallels with the current situation in this area of pedagogical action.

Keywords: *basic personality culture; priority national idea; Russian cultural and historical code.*

After many years of underestimating the role of formative work in preparing the younger generation for life, our education system has gradually come to recognize the seriousness and significance of this type of pedagogical activity. Model programs for formative work have been developed, and methodological recommendations and projects are being drafted that highlight the importance of upbringing at the current stage of societal and social development in Russia [12].

Typically, educators involved in designing formative education programs in contemporary schools tend to 'try to cover too much,' including a wide variety of types and directions of activity within the program. This includes ecological

education (a careful attitude towards nature), the development of tolerance towards others, respect for school traditions, reverence for elders, and many other aspects. All of this leads to fragmentation and dilution of limited pedagogical resources and efforts, and does not always culminate in the final results declared in the program.

In this regard, the author of this article posits that the foundation of any program aimed at educational (formative) development should consist of a limited number of leading (priority) directions (ideas), to which the corresponding types of educational activities are linked. This is the well-known 'cascade model' of interaction and activity between learners and educators, widely recognized in pedagogy and beyond.

Analyzing the conditions in which Russian schools currently operate (the migrant issue, the special military operation, the loss of traditions developed over decades), the author concludes that the foundations for designing educational programs today may be the basic personal culture, a priority national idea, the Russian cultural-historical code, and an objective justification for their incorporation in the upbringing of future Russian citizens.

Consider each of these directions more closely, namely – the content, features, possibilities, and conditions of their application in the design of educational activity programs.

Basic personal culture and its characteristics. The definition of 'basic personal culture' was proposed by O. S. Gazman in the previous century (Gazman O. S., 1989). Providing an interpretation of this definition, O. S. Gazman states: 'It encompasses those essential qualities necessary for the student's independent activity, which determine their further development.'

Under these conditions, the learner activates their existing capabilities and the latent potential of their personality, bringing them into a heightened state of readiness. To effectively cultivate the foundational culture of learners, it is necessary for the school to intentionally design pedagogical situations and conditions that activate existing personal resources in the interests of the individual, the surrounding society, and the nation [1].

In the process of education, referring to the finest examples of our multinational culture entails students' understanding of a layered system of values that foster the development of personality traits and qualities harmoniously aligned both internally and with the external environment. Under these conditions, it is necessary to broaden the range of moral and ethical qualities and values being developed, depending on the age, personal aspirations of the students, external conditions, and objective circumstances.

According to this thesis, the key elements of an individual's foundational culture should include: *the axiological* component, encompassing students' mastery of established values: knowledge, concepts, and their attitudes toward them; *the technological*, which determines the student's level of readiness to address (either individually or

in a group) arising tasks and problems; *personality-oriented creative*, fostering the self-realization of learners and the development of their abilities and interests.

The formation and development of a foundational culture in accordance with the specified components create the prerequisites for developing concepts of personality education. One such concept was proposed by O. S. Gazman and A. V. Ivanov (Gazman O. S., Ivanov A. V., 1992) and was primarily intended for class teachers [4].

The central idea of the proposed concept was considered to be the cultural appropriateness of education. That is, in addition to general education, the school's information and educational environment must create the necessary conditions for students to master the fundamentals of basic culture. At the same time, one of the principal postulates of the examined concept was the nature-appropriateness of education, based on the mandatory consideration of students' age and gender-specific characteristics, their natural predispositions and qualities that facilitate successful self-development of the personality.

A particularly valuable aspect of the proposed concept is that it incorporates certain provisions of the contemporary existentialist approach. In these circumstances, it is crucial to assist the learner in mastering methods of self-education, self-analysis, and self-determination.

For example, the author of this article examines the essence and nature of self-education from the perspective of the competency-based approach (Masharova T. V., 2017). The author concludes that the semantic dominance of independence allows us to consider self-education as the unity of the processes of self-learning and self-cultivation. The linkage between these two senses is realized through self-knowledge as both a condition and a result of self-education [6].

However, the freedom of self-determination does not prohibit the learner from establishing purposeful relations with the external world. The fact is that the learner cannot be entirely free (independent) from external objective circumstances or the surrounding environment, but is capable of demonstrating a principled stance towards them, transforming from external dependence to the internal conditions of their consciousness and practical activity.

At the core of another concept of upbringing, proposed by N. E. Shchurkova (Shchurkova N. E., 1998) conceptualizes the upbringing process as the subtle acculturation of the learner. The essence of «acculturation» is defined by the formation within the learner of a model of a life worthy of them. In this framework, the educator effectively “shares” a certain period of time with the learner, exchanging values and life meanings. The primary objective of this concept of upbringing is the development of a learner’s personality capable of independently designing a life worthy of a citizen of their country [3].

N. E. Shchurkova defines upbringing as a purposeful process of a learner’s entry into the culture of modern society, and the ability to live within it in peace and harmony.

The following concept of upbringing, on which we will focus, was developed by a group of scholars under the leadership of A. A. Bodalev, Z. I. Malkova, and L. I. Novikova (Bodalev A. A., 1998; Malkova Z. I., 1991, [2]; Novikova L. I., 2009, [7]). The proposed concept directed teachers' activities towards humanistic approaches to education, fostering effective interaction between teachers and learners' personalities.

According to the authors, the aim of education was also the comprehensive development of learners' personalities. Among the objectives of education were the following directions: the inculcation of moral and ethical Russian values in learners; the development of creative potential; the understanding of the relative freedom of the individual; the development of the ability for adequate self-assessment; the expression of respect for the rules of communal living; the establishment of a positive attitude toward labor.

It should be noted that the goal of education, articulated as the comprehensive development of the learner's personality, is far removed from the actual state of affairs. This is an ideal, and an ideal, as a rule, remains unattainable. Under these circumstances, the author proposes a personal understanding of the goal of educational (formative) activity.

At the current stage of educational development, amid uncertainty, the educator's task is to cultivate the archetypal model of socialization of a congruent personality. The formation of the archetypal image of socialization of a congruent personality involves the integration of the concepts of archetypes, congruence, and socialization. Archetypes are universal symbols and primordial images that recur in myths, fairy tales, art, and culture. They constitute elements of the deep structure of the psyche that influence thoughts, behavioral patterns, and life scenarios.

The role of archetypes lies in their formation of habits, preferences, and behavioral patterns. They facilitate a deeper understanding of oneself, the identification of strengths and weaknesses, and the assessment of one's motives, values, and preferences.

Congruence (a term borrowed from mathematics) refers to the alignment between an individual's internal attitudes, beliefs, and values and their external expressions (behavior, and modes of expressing feelings and emotions). The impact of congruence on personality enables one to be understood and accepted by others – when verbal communication, emotions, and nonverbal signals are consistent, a person engenders greater trust. This fosters internal harmony: the individual feels freer, more whole, and more satisfied in interactions with others. However, congruence does not imply that a person should act impulsively – it is important to express emotions within cultural and ethical norms, without violating the boundaries of others' freedom.

Thus, basic personal culture is understood as an integrity encompassing a set of essential properties, qualities, and orientations of the personality, enabling the

learner to develop in harmony with the surrounding cultural environment. This involves the acquisition of what is necessary for the preservation of cultural heritage, the mastery of basic knowledge, skills, and abilities, key competencies, elements of functional literacy, and culture of conduct.

Thus, the first component to be considered when designing educational programs with a formative orientation in contemporary schools is the basic personal culture of the learner. The mastery of basic personal culture by learners allows us to identify, among the spectrum of educational concepts considered, the principal, overarching foundation – the Russian national idea.

The National Idea and Its Meaning. The Russian national idea, its significance and system-forming role, as well as its historical essence, are determined by the formation of civic self-awareness among youth. The most important result in adopting the national idea is the learner-citizen's awareness of their Homeland – the great country of Russia.

Typically, the national idea is materialized in the form of artistic works and the material and ideal attributes of heritage from both the past and the present.

The issues of shaping the Russian national idea and its impact on the consciousness of young Russian citizens under contemporary social conditions are highly timely and pertinent. Their relevance is determined by the principles underlying the social development of civil society in our country. At present, these principles may encompass categories such as patriotism, spirituality, and moral-ethical values. Currently, there is a renewed interest in the phenomenon of the Russian national idea across various strata of the population.

In this regard, as early as February 3, 2016, during a meeting of V. V. Putin with the leadership of the Business Initiative Implementation Leaders Club, the President stated that patriotism is regarded as the leading national idea in the Russian Federation and emphasized: 'We will not devise another idea, nor is there any need to do so, as it already exists.'

Therefore, in formative educational activities, we should delineate specific directions for transitioning to new ethical coordinates. For this purpose, it is critically important to ensure conditions conducive to the upbringing of a personality of a new formation. This is an overarching task not only for the general education system but also for the learner's entire surrounding social environment.

As practice demonstrates, addressing this task will be most effective through organizing network interaction among social partners and civil institutions of the local community (educational organizations, libraries, clubs, religious organizations, business structures, parent committees, prevention councils) united by a common idea.

Thus, the second essential component in designing the program of educational upbringing activities in contemporary schools is the Russian national idea. The national idea enables the identification of another key component of upbringing activities – the cultural-historical code.

The cultural-historical code and its understanding. National values are highlighted in the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation No. 400 dated July 2, 2021, 'On the National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation.' Among them are: "life, dignity, human rights and freedoms, patriotism, civic responsibility, service to the Fatherland and accountability for its destiny, high moral ideals, a strong family, constructive labor, the priority of the spiritual over the material, humanism, compassion, justice, collectivism, mutual assistance and mutual respect, historical memory and generational continuity, the unity of the peoples of Russia" [10].

In this regard, T. A. Aimaletdinov (Aimaletdinov T. A., 2014, [8]) and others describe the concept of the cultural-historical code as 'a set of characteristics, images, and stable representations passed down to a people from their ancestors, which are comprehensible to all.' The authors also contend that the cultural-historical code functions as a unique key to understanding the distinctive cultures of various peoples and their differences from others.

Thus, the cultural-historical code constitutes the unique cultural traits inherited by contemporary peoples from their ancestors; This is information encoded in various forms that enables the identification of national culture.

For example, the cultural-historical code is embedded in words, phraseological units, and idioms. Therefore, to ensure that interaction is not disrupted at the very initial stages, it is necessary to study and understand the language of another culture. This may be a foreign language, an unfamiliar dialect, or a professional lexicon used by a very limited circle of people. V. I. Dahl's dictionary (Dahl V. I., 1914) notes that 'code is a mystery, an enigma, a secret, a cipher' [5].

At present, cultural-historical codes are phenomena that will bring contemporary Russia prominence and international recognition. The incorporation of cultural-historical codes into the everyday life of peoples frequently occurs through the enactment of traditional national holidays, dances, competitions, rituals, and other cultural initiatives.

It is natural that the code itself may undergo modernization during its development (being simplified, refined, or modifying the semiotic system). However, the cultural code must necessarily exhibit self-sufficiency, openness, and universality. This naturally raises the question: is it possible to modify the cultural code of a nation, to introduce appropriate adjustments, or to recode it?

In the article 'Russia: the National Question,' our President remarked: '...the cultural code, which has undergone serious trials in recent years, and which has been subjected to attempts to be hacked.' Nevertheless, it has unquestionably been preserved. At the same time, it must be nurtured, strengthened, and preserved.

Education plays a crucial role here. The choice of educational programs and the diversity of education are our indisputable achievements. However, variability must be grounded in immutable values, fundamental knowledge, and worldviews.

The civic mission of education and the enlightenment system is to provide each individual with the absolutely necessary volume of humanitarian knowledge that underpins the self-identity of the nation.

Primarily, the educational process should enhance the significance of subjects such as the Russian language, Russian literature, and national history – naturally, within the context of the full richness of national traditions and cultures. There is much to learn here [9].

In other words, the cultural-historical code of a nation is mentally encoded information – a set of characteristics of a people inherited from their ancestors, which enables the identification of Russian culture. It should be noted that the cultural code of any people is formed over a rather extended period. This process is influenced by many factors, ranging from natural conditions and historical events to the level of civil society development, the country's economic structure, and its political system.

Thus, the conceptual foundations for designing educational (formative) programs directed at students in contemporary schools encompass the following components: the foundational culture of the individual, which ensures the successful socialization of students; the Russian national idea, which facilitates the preservation of the distinctiveness of Russians within the global multicultural space; the Russian cultural-historical code – a unique mentality of the Russian people encoded in the subconscious.

Accordingly, when emphasizing the features of designing educational (formative) programs in contemporary schools, the author notes:

1. Identification of a limited number of fundamental overarching ideas.
2. Construction of the program structure based on the cascade model.
3. Application of the principle of open architecture, which enables the inclusion of new elements in the program in accordance with contemporary requirements and the conditions of a particular school, as well as the phasing out of morally outdated components.

In light of these provisions, the designed program should be distinguished by its efficiency, compactness, focus on specific educational outcomes, and the potential for sustained use over time.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the author in this article has addressed only the main features of designing educational (formative) program orientations in the contemporary school environment, where conditions change almost daily.

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航海数学发展的主要方向
**MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICS IN
NAVIGATION**

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摘要：数学与工程教育的融合对于培养未来海洋专家的系统性专业思维至关重要。计算数学和统计学的基础知识是应对相关航行挑战的基础。现代工程师不仅运用动态过程建模、最优控制和分析预测等方法，而且对计算结果（包括使用专业软件包获得的结果）保持批判性思维。本研究旨在培养未来海洋专家在系统分析、适应创新和跨学科协作方面的跨学科能力。

本文强调采用系统方法研究跨学科联系，并通过将数理统计方法与应用学科相结合来解决复杂的专业任务来阐述这一方法。这种跨学科应用能够拓展数据分析的功能潜力，并支持在实际条件下做出明智的决策。

关键词：统计学，数学，统计分析，安全，风险评估。

Abstract. *The integration of mathematical and engineering education is essential for the development of systematic professional thinking in future marine specialists. Fundamental knowledge in computational mathematics and statistics forms the basis for addressing relevant navigation challenges. A modern engineer not only applies methods of modeling dynamic processes, optimal control, and analytical forecasting, but also maintains a critical view of the results of calculations, including those obtained using specialized software packages. The objective of this study is the formation of metadisciplinary competencies in future marine specialists for systemic analysis, adaptation to innovations, and interdisciplinary collaboration in professional practice.*

In this article, the authors emphasize a systemic approach to studying metadisciplinary connections, illustrating it through the integration of mathematical statistics

methods with applied disciplines for solving complex professional tasks. This interdisciplinary application enables the expansion of the functional potential of data analysis and supports the making of informed decisions under real-world conditions.

Keywords: *statistics, mathematics, statistical analysis, safety, risk assessment.*

The primary objective of the educational program is to ensure that students thoroughly assimilate the content components of professional disciplines with the aim of developing their professional and general cultural competencies, based on a systemic interdisciplinary approach and the integration of inter-subject connections.

To ensure optimal outcomes, various technologies and methods of information delivery are employed, grounded in engagement with perception and cognition. Today, one of the most popular, advanced, and promising directions for developing critical thinking in terms of solving current problems, proposing scientific hypotheses, and fostering professional flexibility and adaptability is the method of metadisciplinary connections, or 'interdisciplinary education,' 'trans-disciplinary approach,' and the like. 'Societal problems are no longer structured by disciplines... The most complex challenges of the 21st century require us to transcend the boundaries of individual subjects and synthesize knowledge' [1].

The essence of this method lies in presenting each science studied during the mastery of a profession not as an isolated discipline, for which a 'cram and forget' approach suffices, but as a component of an integrated whole, without which the complete picture cannot be formed. Alternatively, the subject is delivered as the fundamentals and bases for understanding a more narrowly focused, so-called 'professional' science, which is itself founded on the interconnection of multiple fields of knowledge. Thus, an unconventional approach to achieving the established goals is being developed. Rather than seeking answers within a single direction, an individual begins to view the issue through the prism of various related fields, thereby expanding the range of potential methods for obtaining the desired result. "In the modern era, many problems are inherently interdependent and therefore require integrative approaches and collaborative solutions" [2].

The relevance of this research is determined by several contradictions, the principal one being the gap between the necessity to implement metadisciplinary connections as a core resource of modern education, the theoretical importance of this approach, and its practical application within the marine specialist training system.

The goal of this work is the professional training of marine specialists based on a meta-disciplinary approach that fosters the development of systemic thinking, adaptability to rapidly evolving marine technologies, and readiness for effective interdisciplinary collaboration within the crew.

When examining the issue of metadisciplinary links in the course 'Water Transport Operation and Navigation,' one can identify numerous directly related

disciplines, as well as subjects where understanding one can facilitate comprehension of the structure of another or enable a more detailed and profound mastery of it. Mathematics plays an indisputably important role in the profession of Navigator. In addition to the fact that one third of the entire curriculum in higher education is devoted to its study, many professional sciences are founded upon it. Fundamentals of Navigation (FN) and Mathematical Foundations of Navigation (MFN) are disciplines that encapsulate the core navigational aspects for mariners, while being directly linked to the mathematics mentioned earlier, without which their study would be impossible. Many specialized disciplines incorporate methods from one of the key fields of mathematics — mathematical statistics.

Diagram 1. Interrelation of Professional Subjects with Mathematical Statistics

When discussing calculations based on repeated values and measurements, it is essential to mention 'Life Safety (LS)' and 'Navigation Safety,' where the identification of patterns and probabilities is fundamental to successfully mitigating

risks and preventing emergencies. Moreover, there is 'Investigation of Accidents and Incidents at Sea,' where a mathematical approach can offer a different understanding of events, enrich the overall picture, and enable consideration of causes from a new perspective. From this, it can be concluded that 'research at the intersection of disciplines is a fertile ground for innovation' [3]—in other words, the integration of sciences and working on their interaction can unveil entirely new and advanced methods of understanding.

As noted earlier, statistics has a place in many disciplines, both as one of the primary methods of cognition and as an alternative approach. In light of the above, it was concluded that statistical analysis is an indispensable component of many fields within navigation. To validate the significance and importance of metadisciplinary connections, we decided to examine the application of statistics in conjunction with other disciplines. The example is shown in Diagram 1.

Statistics in Navigation. The use of statistical analysis in the water transport operation course is not, in itself, a novel approach. There are numerous formulas intended for various fields and contexts. The list is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Principal Methods of Statistical Analysis

Method	Application Mechanisms	Formula	Theoretical Foundations
Risk Theory Method	Classical Engineering Risk Analysis and the Theory of Mathematical Expectation of Losses.	$R = P(A) * C$	Integral safety assessment based on balancing the frequency of incidents and the severity of their consequences.
Monte Carlo Method	The Law of Large Numbers and Statistical Modeling of Random Variables.	$P(A) \approx \frac{N_A}{N}$	The overall frequency of emergency situations through direct numerical simulation.
The apparatus of stochastic processes	Navigational hydrodynamics, ship motion equations.	$x_{t+1} = x_t + V \cos \psi * \Delta t + \varepsilon_x$ $y_{t+1} = y_t + V \sin \psi * \Delta t + \varepsilon_y$	Dynamics and trajectory of ship movement over time.
Bayesian analysis	Bayes' theorem (conditional probability).	$P(H/E) = \frac{P(E/H) * P(H)}{P(E)}$	Correction and continuous updating of current risk assessments

Method	Application Mechanisms	Formula	Theoretical Foundations
Importance Sampling method(Importance sampling)	Probability theory and statistical modeling	$R \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum C * I_i * \omega_i$	Probability of critical but extremely rare navigational incidents
Logistic regression	Multivariate statistical analysis and the maximum likelihood method.	$P(A) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$	The influence of a complex of diverse external factors on a binary outcome
Fault tree analysis (FTA)	Mathematical logic and system reliability theory.	$P(Top) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - P_i)$	Causal relationships underlying accident occurrence
Kohonen networks (SOM)	Neural network algorithms and unsupervised learning	$\Delta\omega_j = \eta(t) * (x - \omega_j)$	Clustering of trajectories in large volumes of navigation data.

The vessel entry process into the port water area was selected as the object of statistical analysis, given that the effectiveness of this maneuver depends on numerous interrelated factors requiring comprehensive consideration.

Among the presented types of statistical analysis, we have selected the most appropriate for the field of navigation, specifically: the Method of Risk Theory, Stochastic Processes, and the Importance Sampling Method. To obtain the final model that satisfies the requirements for integrating multiple disciplines, it is necessary to perform several transformations as shown in diagram 2.

As a result, formulas characterizing the safety of vessel entry into the port water area were obtained. In disciplines such as life safety and navigation safety, factors were identified that statistically have the greatest influence on the hazard and accident rate of the navigational situation [4,5]. The optimal selection of criteria presented in Scheme 2 enables a more precise risk assessment based on statistical indicators. Ultimately, computational formulas were derived that can be applied as a tool for a transdisciplinary approach in risk assessment within navigation and in the investigation of maritime accidents and incidents. In assessing the probability of risk for a vessel, this method can serve as an alternative for calculations and problem-solving within this discipline. The results of the calculations obtained during the investigation of a given incident make it possible to determine, for example, the extent to which a specific factor influenced the danger of the navigational environment and whether it could have caused a catastrophe, accident, or did not lead to significant risks [6].

Diagram 2. Diagram describing the application of statistical methods in assessing the risk of a vessel entering the port water area

Therefore, it can be concluded that the integrative approach in education is an excellent tool for fostering students' critical thinking, equipping them to identify hidden connections and patterns, and enabling more profound analyses [7]. The transdisciplinary approach teaches one to perceive the discipline not as an isolated object, but as a language for describing the professional world; it teaches how to search for information, build models, and coordinate one's actions with real situations that one will have to face after completing education.

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东方国家教育机构与企业之间的互动
**INTERACTION BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND
ENTERPRISES IN EASTERN COUNTRIES**

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摘要：本文以日本、中国、印度、土耳其等东亚国家为例，探讨了教育机构与企业之间的互动问题。文章分析了企业与教育体系各环节（包括中小学、高等院校、大学、科研机构和企业）之间社会伙伴关系的形式、法律框架、发展方向和条件。文章阐明了这种互动的本质，以及它对教育机构和企业本身乃至整个社会发展的积极影响。

关键词：互动，教育机构，企业，合作，社会伙伴关系，科学研究

Abstract. *This article addresses the issues of interaction between educational institutions and enterprises in Eastern countries, analyzed through the examples of Japan, China, India, Turkey, and others. It identifies the forms, legal frameworks, directions, and conditions of social partnership between enterprises and various segments of the education system – school – college – university – research laboratories – enterprises. The nature of the interaction has been elucidated, along with its positive outcomes for both educational institutions and enterprises specifically, as well as for the development of society as a whole.*

Keywords: *interaction, educational organizations, enterprises, cooperation, social partnership, scientific research,*

Introduction

Significance. The significance of this article on the interaction between educational institutions and enterprises in Eastern countries is grounded in global trends, economic challenges, cultural specificities, and the demands of workforce preparation. In the context of globalization, digitalization, and the transition to a knowledge-based economy, cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises becomes a key factor in enhancing the quality of specialist training,

adapting curricula to the actual needs of the labor market, and stimulating innovative development. This study was conducted *with the aim of* identifying the forms, directions, conditions, and characteristics of scientific and educational cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises. The scientific novelty of this article lies in the systematization of key data concerning the interaction between educational institutions and enterprises across four levels: school – college – university – enterprise.

The study employed the following *methods*: comparative analysis, synthesis, and theoretical generalization of the examined materials.

The theoretical foundation of the research was formed by the works of Sh. G. Akramova, N. Vlasov, O. V. Zinevich, V. A. Zherebtsov, E. V. Neborsky, P. A. Pronnikov, E. V. Sitnikov, V. N. Shkunov, and others.

The practical significance of the study lies in the applicability of its results for the development of specialized pedagogy courses at universities, for lecturers in preparing lectures and practical sessions, and for postgraduate and doctoral candidates in the composition of dissertations.

Discussion and Results

In Eastern countries, educational institutions and enterprises collaborate through various forms of integration. This phenomenon is evident in several countries, including Japan, China, India, and Turkey (Neborsky, 2011, p. 48). We will briefly examine their characteristics.

In *Japan*, vocational-technical institutions exist where students acquire practical knowledge in various fields (electrical engineering, metalworking, woodworking, etc.). At the vocational department, no less than 40% of the time is devoted to specialized subjects, while general education is offered in smaller volumes and under simplified curricula (Pronnikov, Electronic resource).

Production training exerts a positive effect on the socialization of students, the acquisition of practical skills, the final determination of their professional choice, the development of professionally significant personal qualities, and the preparation for independent labor activity.

The interaction between educational institutions and industry in Japan exists in various forms.

- Development of linkages between universities and industry. Many universities strengthen connections with local industry, including increasing revenue derived from intellectual property applied within industry;

- Establishment of technopolises – purpose-built sites comprising universities, research laboratories, and institutes to consolidate scientific expertise and production capabilities for the implementation of innovations.

- the development of venture business enterprises based at universities, which leads to the establishment of startups;

– the creation of legal entities to facilitate technology transfer, such as technology licensing organizations that assist researchers in securing patents for their inventions and support industry in licensing these inventions.

In *China*, educational institutions actively collaborate with industry. The Chinese government places significant emphasis on university science, recognizing that university research is crucial for the development of new products and processes, thereby enhancing the international competitiveness of Chinese industry.

The forms of interaction are diverse:

1. Formal cooperation. This includes joint publication of articles, contractual agreements, research projects, patent licensing, and consultancy.

2. Informal cooperation. They conduct joint scientific and practical conferences.

3. Integration of production and education. They establish enterprises where the production process is integrated into education, or jointly create, together with vocational schools, facilities for internships and practical training.

4. Cooperation with international companies. This facilitates the adaptation of foreign technologies to the specific production conditions of the national industry.

It should be noted that the integration of industry and vocational education is inextricably connected with the demands of industry and enterprises. There are more than 3,000 enterprises in the country where the production process is integrated with education. Innovation-oriented educational clusters have been developed, within which universities, research institutions, companies from various sectors, and venture capital funds engage in strategic cooperation. Such interaction produces a synergistic effect in the development of innovative products and the delivery of high-quality educational services. Cooperation between universities and both local and international companies facilitates the adaptation of foreign technologies to the specific production conditions of domestic industries. The creation of enterprises based on universities (spin-offs, start-ups) represents a fundamental source of innovative activity (Akramova, 2016).

Collaboration between production sectors and colleges is also widespread. Vocational schools and enterprises jointly establish platforms for internships and practical training. This collaboration is structured around the principle of ‘customized training.’ Students receive training in cooperation with the enterprises where they will be employed following graduation.

Colleges establish a foundation for preparing teachers with ‘dual qualifications’ to serve both in schools and enterprises (Zherebtsov, 2014, p.72). For example, the ‘Luban Workshop’ Project is intended to promote sustainable collaboration between industry partners (enterprises) and colleges, as well as to optimize the duration of training programs (Sitnikov, 2023, p.37).

In *India*, there are initiatives aimed at fostering collaboration between schools and colleges and the industrial sector. These projects focus on the development

of skills and technological innovation, as well as on preparing young people for employment across various fields.

Schools collaborate with innovative companies in diverse sectors, including nanotechnology, pharmaceutical manufacturing, and others. Researchers from Indian universities engage with companies operating in these domains. This clearly illustrates a tripartite relationship among schools, industry, and universities.

India implements student exchanges between schools and universities. For example, in 2023, a delegation from the Higher School of Economics (HSE) in Saint Petersburg proposed establishing units dedicated to the development of international relations in Indian schools and initiating student exchanges between schools and universities.

There are teacher professional development programs. For instance, the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) has initiated the training of teachers through short-term certification programs to align engineering students with new-century technologies (artificial intelligence, robotics). The 'Indovation' centers (India Innovations) have been established. They facilitate the transfer of technologies, as well as the implementation of innovations and ideas, for example, in the field of nanotechnology.

The interaction between industry and colleges also merits attention. The implementation of projects aimed at establishing the foundation for vocational education in specific fields is common. For example, in 2025, a mechatronics project was initiated in India, supported by the Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA). It entails the development of a specialized training program, textbooks, and instructional manuals for educators, adapted specifically for education in the field of mechatronics. Within the framework of the project, students are provided with state-of-the-art equipment to foster a conducive learning environment, while educators participate in professional development programs. This creates opportunities for students to acquire practical experience and hands-on training.

Furthermore, the Government of India promotes private sector initiatives within the higher professional education system, including in the domain of IT technologies. For instance, in 2015, reports indicated that Indian universities actively engage in collaborations with leading innovative domestic companies specializing in pharmaceutical manufacturing (Shkunov, 2011).

In India, infrastructure and industrial projects such as Smart Cities and Make in India are being implemented, which necessitate the preparation of personnel: engineers, IT specialists, medical professionals, and technical experts. These projects include initiatives aimed at resolving the problem of personnel shortages.

In *South Korea*, schools and colleges engage with industry within an educational system designed to train specialists for various sectors of the national economy. This interaction is manifested in various aspects: in the activities of schools, vocational and technical colleges, and enterprises collaborating with educational institutions.

In South Korea, there exist schools that provide vocational education. These institutions specialize in technical disciplines, such as technology, agriculture, or finance. Their curricula integrate general education courses (Korean language, mathematics, science) with professional courses related to production. Career development programs are designed to prepare students for professional careers, including career courses and vocational training. In addition, schools train career counselors and allocate resources for career education.

Students participate in programs associated with production sectors. For instance, there is a '2 + 1' system consisting of two years of school education followed by one year of workplace training.

The collaboration between colleges and the production sector is primarily focused on their vocational training. They establish partnerships with enterprises and jointly develop programs tailored to their specific needs (company-customized). Close collaboration facilitates the employment of graduates. Over 80% of college students secure employment in accordance with their specialization.

Many colleges are consolidated under a single administrative framework; for instance, the Korean Polytechnic Institute encompasses 11 colleges and 29 campuses nationwide. Students may select from 500 educational programs in electrical engineering, electronics, and communications, with courses lasting two years. The institute also offers continuing professional development courses.

Korea is one of the few countries where the development of the entrepreneurial model within universities integrates education and research with an entrepreneurial culture. Universities develop their curricula and research directions in response to the most acute challenges emerging in society, thereby exerting an influence on the country's economic development.

Additionally, the formation and development of innovative national and regional clusters are undertaken: universities, businesses, and the state expand their participation, introduce new initiatives, and contribute to the establishment and advancement of innovative clusters (Zinevich, 2017, p. 146).

The interaction between educational institutions and industry in the *Middle East* region is evident in various countries, including Arab states, Iran, Turkey, and Israel. This cooperation is directed towards the advancement of priority scientific research and the development of new technologies aligned with the market economy.

In the *Arab countries*, the internationalization of higher education is currently progressing successfully. Governments of the Arab states of the Persian Gulf actively support educational integration with other countries and foreign universities. For instance:

- Numerous branches of foreign universities are located in the UAE and Qatar;
- Universities in Oman and Kuwait offer a wide range of dual degree programs;
- Saudi Arabia makes active use of English as the medium of instruction and adopts the American educational system;

– Specialized workforce training for companies. For example, several universities in the UAE were established by major corporations and provide training for the management of hotel complexes both domestically and internationally, as well as for the national oil company and Emirates Airline.

In *Iran*, collaboration among educational institutions occurs across various domains: secondary education, higher education, scientific research, and within the scope of international cooperation. Iran's education system is centralized: public schools are administered by the Ministry of National Education and Training, whereas universities are overseen by the Ministry of Higher Education and Culture (Vlasov, 2019).

In *Turkey*, collaboration among educational institutions is evident at multiple levels: preschool, secondary, and higher education, as well as within international cooperation. The education system in Turkey comprises public and private institutions, as well as international schools.

Turkey undertakes:

- Collaboration between universities and industry. Large corporations and recently founded innovative enterprises demonstrate an interest in developing research infrastructure and jointly undertaking specific transformations with universities;
- The involvement of the business community in university governance (boards of trustees, supervisory boards), the establishment of new educational structures, and the financing of scientific and educational projects.
- Establishment of innovative infrastructure (technoparks, incubators).

However, obstacles exist in the development of cooperation, such as the predominance of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Turkish economy, which do not always possess the requisite educational, technological, and psychological capacities for effective collaboration.

Israel is a comparatively well-developed country in the sphere of education. Nevertheless, the state's primary concern is the defense of the country against external aggression; accordingly, it prioritizes the training of specialists for the armed forces; An emphasis on innovative technologies at the school level. Students engage in long-term projects that integrate knowledge across various subject areas; The relationship between the military and higher education. The experience acquired during military service can constitute a valuable asset in the study of certain specialties, particularly in fields related to security, technology, and leadership.

Conclusion. In summarizing the experience of cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises in Eastern countries, it can be concluded *that this process entails a protracted and complex developmental trajectory. This is substantiated by a substantial number of scholarly works on the issue. A brief review of existing research on the subject reveals that the forms of interaction between educational institutions and enterprises in many countries are analogous:*

- collaborative educational programs have been developed, and professional education centers established to facilitate effective graduate employment;
 - joint bodies uniting educational institutions and employers have been created (professional committees, sectoral councils);
 - scientific research is concentrated in ‘technopolises.’ For example, in Japan, there is the ‘Science City’ Tsukuba;
 - cooperation with local companies, as well as with international companies and multinational corporations. For example, more than 200 universities in China maintain close cooperation with Alibaba (a Chinese e-commerce company) and other domestic and foreign enterprises;
 - Centers for youth workplace training, as well as internships for students and graduate students, have been established;
- Clusters function according to the scheme: university – research centers – industry.

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通过人工智能集成实现学员能力发展的协同方法
**SYNERGETIC APPROACH TO CADETS' COMPETENCIES
DEVELOPMENT THROUGH AI INTEGRATION**

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摘要：鉴于科技的飞速发展，本文探讨了海事教育的未来发展前景。文章从人格与人工智能相互映照、产生协同效应的角度，分析了专业自主组织在海员自主发展中的地位。已建立的自主发展层级凸显了内化机制在专业培训中的重要性。为了评估当前人工智能工具在自主发展中的有效性，本文开展了一项关于学员使用新技术工具进行自身专业发展的习惯的研究。尽管已知已证实的好处，但研究表明，适当的专业教师支持对于有效性至关重要。本文还考虑了国际海事组织（IMO）的相关要求，例如《海员培训、发证和值班标准》以及终身学习。

关键词：专业自主组织，海员培训，STCW公约，外语能力

Abstract. *Taking into account the fast technological progress, the perspective development of maritime education is considered. The place of professional self-organization is analyzed from the position of mutual reflection of human personality and Artificial Intelligence generates synergy. The established hierarchy of self-processes rises the importance of interiorization mechanism in professional training. To assess the nowadays situation, considering effectiveness of Artificial Intelligence tools in self-process, the research on cadets' habits to use new technological instruments for their own professional development was arranged. Although proven benefits are known, studies have shown that appropriate professional teacher support is essential for effectiveness. International Maritime Organization requirements like Standards of Training Certification and Watch keeping and lifelong learning are taken into account.*

Keywords: *professional self-organization, seafarer training, STCW convention, foreign language competencies*

Artificial intelligence (AI) in the contemporary world is no longer merely a tool of statistical analysis; it has become an actively demanded means for solving problems, finding unconventional approaches, and rapidly processing large volumes of

data. The introduction of AI into education transforms the system: technologies become salient, while participants' unpreparedness generates resistance, uneven feedback, and myths surrounding AI. One key prospect is AI's influence on human self-organization, in both ontology and phylogeny.

Historically, technological progress has provoked anxiety, but today debates focus on controlling technological evolution and defining humanity's place in the future. AI penetrates cognitive, creative, and social spheres, including the emotional domain. People already struggle to compete with AI in data volume and processing speed or in physical endurance, which emphasizes the importance of personal self-organization when working with AI. The scale and accessibility of AI stimulate its adoption, yet rapid integration demands system adaptation and critical reflection. [1, pp 155–158; 2]

A synergetic approach at the maritime university aims to activate cadets' subjectivity, relying on self-organization theory and the development of professional self-organizational skills. Our observations show that AI affects cadets' self-preparation: it opens new opportunities but disturbs the balance of educational processes. A stabilizing factor remains self-organization – the personal capacity for feedback, planning, and control – which determines technology use. [3] Professional self-organization is considered as a pedagogical condition for effective AI use in professional education through theoretical review, a synergetic model, empirical analysis, and identification of implementation conditions specific to the maritime profession.

Professional self-organization is defined as the ability to consciously use and refine personality components to solve educational, professional, and personally significant tasks. Among the “self-” processes we distinguish three levels: basic (self-knowledge, self-analysis), systemic (self-organization, self-governance), and final (self-learning, self-realization). [4] Monitoring as Self-knowledge diagnoses the state of professional development; self-analysis explains successes and failures; self-control disciplines behavior and implements tactics; self-programming sets goals and stages. [5, pp. 271–273; 6, pp. 387–390] Self-organization integrates these processes and enables the shift from knowledge consumption to professional growth: from “I liked the AI test” to “This task will develop a skill if I formulate the query correctly and critically process the result.”

AI is effective as an instrument during self-knowledge and self-learning stages, helping to identify error patterns and provide feedback, but its power is constrained by the epistemic limits of any complex system. AI itself is a developing complex system subject to the same modeling limitations. The mutual reflection of human personality and AI generates synergy: through reflection and self-organization a cadet can compensate for AI's epistemic limits, filter its hallucinations, and steer it toward real professional tasks.

In maritime education, openness of the learner, sea practice, [7] live interaction with professionals, and quasi-professional training (simulators, language labs)

remain crucial. [8] Moreover, critical and dosed inclusion of AI is essential: AI acts as a catalyst, not a dictator, of personal development.

Seafarer training requires communication and English-language proficiency, perception, prognostic and reflexive skills. One cannot impose a single developmental trajectory on a complex personality; education must foster motivation through heuristic methods, debates, and practice-oriented courses. Professional self-organization enables informed choice among alternative paths and adapts to changes.[9]

Practically, AI is applied in the maritime university for test generation, simulator scenarios, and result analysis, particularly in language training and competency assessment. [10, pp. 99–108] Experience shows that integrating AI together with emphasis on self-organization improves outcomes: project work with AI and personalized distance courses enhance productivity and retention. However, AI's effectiveness depends on its instrumental use by the system and on cadets' maintenance of critical thinking, self-control, and goal orientation. [11]

Thus, professional self-organization functions as the systemic integrator of “self-” processes and the key pedagogical condition for successful AI integration. The optimal degree of AI inclusion should consider the development of cadets' self-organizational skills, provision of practice and live interaction, and safeguards against passivity and information distortion. In this hybrid approach AI enhances analysis and personalization, while self-organization ensures responsibility, criticality, and professional adaptability of cadets.

Smart ships, IMO safety rules, and lifelong learning needs make self-development essential for cadets. The need to analyze expediency is a core principle when using computer tools in training, ensuring AI fits learning goals like text generation and summaries. [12, pp. 147–152] Studies show AI provides strong online support for maritime cadets, improving self-organization and foreign language competence through translation and analysis. Research also stresses better monitoring of language skills via AI, alongside professional self-organization growth with AI integration.

At the same time, ethical and methodological challenges exist, such as AI hallucinations and quality risks in generative tools. These issues demand careful use to avoid threats to language preparation and skill quality for future seafarers. It is necessary to research AI in Cadets' Professional Self-Training and Self-Development because recent works reveal high potential for efficiency and competence growth, but gaps remain in cadets' real practices, tool preferences, and overcoming limits like errors and ethical risks. Without such studies, maritime education cannot fully adapt AI to meet Standards of Training Certification and Watch keeping Convention standards and digital ship demands. [13]

The subject of the practical research is the use of AI by cadets in their professional self-training and self-development. It focuses on how AI tools support learning for career skills. The object is maritime cadets during their training period. They

learn skills like navigation, safety, and leadership. The research uses specially arranged and provided data from a Google Form survey where cadets shared their AI experiences. This survey asked about tools they use, benefits, and problems faced.

The arranged research was aimed to solve some tasks: analyze survey results; find common AI tools; check effects on skills; and suggest better methods. 100 cadets took active part in the survey. The survey was called "AI in professional self-development." It contains data from ~100 maritime cadets (mostly 2nd-4th year, Navigation Department prominent at 47%).

Survey results confirm AI's positive impact, including increased average score (15–25%). Cadets spend 1–3 hours weekly on tools like DeepSeek, ChatGPT, Gemini and many others, with 79% using text generation for summaries and translation. Key benefits include reduced preparation time (46% agree) with the kept efficiency, improved STCW competencies (40%), and stronger critical thinking (41%). Self-practices like error analysis (47% always/often) and knowledge checks (42%) is shown.

Some challenges were revealed as well. Half encountered AI hallucinations, requiring fact-checking, and 34% worry about losing independent thinking skills. Text tools are proved to outperform image/video generation (30–45%).

After provided analyses and interview, discussions and practical lessons within the research program the AI boosts self-training efficiency was confirmed provided with human oversight. High adoption (71% rate 4–5 effectiveness) fits modern maritime needs like IMO standards. After analyze expediency as a core principle when using AI tools in training, every cadet developed and offered a list of advice whereby the further discussion allowed to combine and analyze them and recommend at least to plan AI usage, verify outputs, and balance with manual practice to maximize gains.

In conclusion, the taken data of provided research is used in the further development of special programs for professional self-organization logically included into the linguistic trainings and test-simulation programs.

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将基础外语词汇融入高年级学前儿童体育教育过程中
**INTEGRATION OF ELEMENTARY FOREIGN LANGUAGE
VOCABULARY IN THE PROCESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION
OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN**

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摘要：本文探讨了在作者为学前儿童设计的体育课部分教学计划中融入基础外语词汇的理论和应用问题。文章分析了将基础外语词汇（以法语为例）融入高年级学前儿童体育课的心理和教育条件。文中介绍的作者设计的体育课部分教学计划是学前教育主课程中一个不可或缺的结构教育组成部分，并已融入其目标和实质内容部分。本研究的意义在于探索适用于学前儿童的现代体育教学方法，从而为儿童在各个发展阶段的和谐成长奠定坚实的基础。作者特别关注在将基础外语词汇融入学前儿童体育课的过程中，如何创造最佳的心理和教育条件以及良好的教育环境。研究对象为学前儿童的体育教育过程。本研究的主题是将基础外语词汇融入高年级学前儿童的体育教育过程。本研究的实验部分旨在通过实验验证作者设计的融入基础法语词汇的体育教育方案的有效性，并探究融合式体育课程对高年级学前儿童语言发展和体育学习动机的影响。本研究的方法论基础是综合性研究，通过对学前儿童体育教育和语言发展理论与方法论中的概念进行理论分析，并结合实证方法，将运动和认知活动融入高年级学前儿童的体育教育课程中。研究方法包括：分析与研究问题相关的心理学和教育学文献；分析学前儿童的体育教育方案；进行教学观察；开展教学实验；评估高年级学前儿童的语言发展和学习动机；运用数理统计方法处理所获得的数据。本研究的科学创新之处在于证实了将基础外语词汇融入高年级学前儿童的体育活动中，并结合部分体育课程，能够有效促进高年级学前儿童的语言发展及其参与体育活动的积极性。这拓展了我们对学前儿童全面发展有效途径和方法的理解。实证研究结果表明，高年级学前儿童语言发展的主要指标（语音、词汇、连贯性表达）呈现积极趋势，且其参与体育活动的积极性也显著提高。本研究的实践意义在于，通过实验验证了作者为高年级学前儿童设计的、融入基础外语（以法语为例）的部分体育课

程，该课程被整合到学前教育基础课程中，并融入到参与者互动学习的环节结构中。这些研究成果为现代学前教育理论与实践提供了重要的方法论工具。

关键词：融合、体育、学前儿童、融合式教学法、作者部分方案、学前教育、语言发展、动机领域。

Abstract. *The article addresses the theoretical and applied aspects of integrating elementary foreign language vocabulary in the course of the experimental implementation of the author's partial program of physical education for preschool children. The psychological and pedagogical conditions for integrating elementary foreign language vocabulary (exemplified by French) into physical education sessions with senior preschool children are analyzed. The author's partial program of physical education presented in the article represents an integral structural educational component, integrated into the target and substantive section of the main educational program of preschool education. **The relevance of the research** is grounded in the need to identify modern means and methods of physical education for preschoolers, thereby providing a solid foundation for the harmonious development of the child throughout all stages of ontogenesis. The author pays particular attention to the creation of optimal psychological and pedagogical conditions and a favorable educational environment in the process of integrating elementary foreign language vocabulary into physical education sessions with preschool children. **The research object** is the process of physical education of preschool-aged children. **The research subject** is the integration of elementary foreign language vocabulary into the process of physical education of older preschool children. **The aim** of the experimental-empirical part of this study is to experimentally verify the effectiveness of the implementation of the author's partial physical education program utilizing elementary French vocabulary, and to identify the influence of integrated physical education sessions on speech development and motivation for physical education among older preschool children. **The methodological foundation of the study** is an integrative approach realized through the theoretical analysis of concepts within the theory and methodology of physical education and speech development of preschool children, alongside empirical methods for integrating motor and cognitive activities during physical education sessions with senior preschool children. **Research methods:** analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature related to the research problem; analysis of partial physical education programs for preschool children. pedagogical observations; pedagogical experiment; assessment of speech development and the motivational sphere of senior preschool children; mathematical-statistical methods for processing the obtained data. **The scientific novelty of the work** lies in substantiating the positive influence of integrating elementary foreign language vocabulary into the physical education process of senior preschool children,*

implemented within the framework of a partial physical education program, on the speech development of senior preschool children and their motivation to engage in physical activity. This expands the understanding of effective means and methods for the comprehensive development of the child during the pre-school ontogenetic period. The results of the empirical study enabled the identification of positive trends in the main indicators of speech development in senior preschool children (phonetics, vocabulary, coherent speech), as well as statistically significant increases in the motivation of senior preschool children to engage in physical education. The practical significance of the study lies in the experimental validation of the author's partial physical education program for senior preschool children incorporating elementary foreign language (using French as an example), through its integration into the structure of the component formed by the participants in educational relations within the basic educational program of preschool education. These results provide modern science and practice with a significant methodological tool in the theory and practice of preschool education.

Keywords: integration, physical education, preschool children, integrative approach, author's partial program, preschool education, speech development, motivational domain.

Introduction

The problem of integrating foreign language vocabulary into the process of teaching and educating a child during the preschool period of ontogenesis constitutes a complex, multifaceted task closely related to age-specific developmental characteristics. Accordingly, the study by Yu. I. Bakhtalina presents a comprehensive model of integrated foreign (English) language instruction for preschool children [1]. I. G. Kosareva and N. M. Rodina presented the concept of integrating foreign language vocabulary into productive activities (artistic activity, construction) [3]. However, despite existing research in this field, the present state of integration of elementary foreign language vocabulary remains unresolved in the practice of physical education in preschool educational institutions. For this reason, in the theory and practice of physical education for preschool children, special attention is given to partial (from Latin *partialis* – partial, particular) programs aimed at an in-depth study of one or more educational areas, implemented as an additional program and/or as a variable component of the main preschool education program. **The aim of this study** is to develop and conduct a pilot experimental validation of the effectiveness of the implementation of the author's partial physical education program for senior preschool children using elementary foreign (French) language vocabulary, as well as to identify the impact of integrated physical education on speech development and motivation for engaging in physical activity among

senior preschool children. The established goal allowed us to formulate the object and subject of the research. **Object of the research** – the process of physical education of preschool-aged children. **Subject of the research** – the integration of elementary foreign language vocabulary into the process of physical education of senior preschool-aged children.

The scientific novelty of the research consists in the fact that:

1. the positive influence of integrating elementary foreign (French) language vocabulary into the process of physical education on speech development and the enhancement of motivation for physical activity is substantiated;
2. Data concerning effective methods for diagnosing speech development and the motivational sphere during the preschool ontogenetic period have been refined.
3. The authorial partial physical education program ‘Jump – Run – Play!’ incorporating elementary French foreign vocabulary was experimentally validated on an age group sample of children aged 5 to 6 years.

Practical significance of the study:

1. It has been established that the integration of elementary French foreign vocabulary into the process of physical education enhances the interest and motivation of senior preschool children to perform physical exercises, ensures positive progress in speech development, thereby positively influencing the comprehensive development of children in the senior preschool age group;
2. The psychological and pedagogical conditions for the integration of elementary French foreign language vocabulary based on the use of the author’s partial program in the process of physical education of 5–6 year-old children have been defined;
3. The role of the educator in the speech, cognitive, and physical development, consisting in the effective leadership of children’s motor activities during the physical education of senior preschoolers based on the integration of elementary French foreign language vocabulary, has been established.

Main Part

Theoretical Approaches to the Study of the Problem of Integrating Elementary Foreign Language Vocabulary into the Process of Physical Education of Senior Preschool Children Studies by domestic researchers (E. Yu. Bakhtalina, I. G. Kosareva, N. M. Rodina, E. I. Negnevitskaya, Z. N. Nikitenko, N. A. Gorlova, M. A. Pravdov, V. T. Kudryavtsev) demonstrate that the integration of various means and methods of educating preschool children, including acquaintance with elementary foreign language vocabulary, is possible only within activities natural for the child (motor, play, socio-communicative) [1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7]. In this study, we proceeded from the understanding of the concept of “integration” within the context of the systems approach formulated by M. A. Pravdov, defined as “a systemic unity of knowledge, methods of action, cognitive approaches,

educational-cognitive problems, methods and means of teaching, ensuring the organic fusion of motor and cognitive activities into a holistic educational process” [6, p. 112]. At the same time, according to the scholar, it is necessary to take into account a number of crucial psychological and pedagogical conditions, under conditions under which the process of integration (including foreign language vocabulary) into the physical education of preschool children will be most effective. These conditions include the didactic unity of the educational material presented to preschoolers, as well as the synergistic effect of teaching and upbringing, the result of which is the formation in the child of a qualitatively new experience, which can be reflected in the three-level structure “action-thought-feeling” [6].

N. A. Gorlova’s research substantiates the expediency of an activity-based approach to the integration of foreign language vocabulary into the theory and practice of preschool education [2]. This approach permits the exclusion of mechanical rote memorization of isolated lexical units outside the context of children’s activities and facilitates the integration of foreign language words, including in the process of physical education, as an instrument of cognition rather than as an objective. According to the scholar, ‘the teaching of foreign language to children should not be aimed at mastering the language as a system, but at mastering speech activity as a means of communication and cognition, which is possible only through the integration of language material into activities significant to the child – play, motor, productive, and theatrical activities’ [2, p.42].

Foreign researchers (D. Marsh, P. Hood, D. Coyle) have introduced the concept of subject-language integrated learning (Content and Language Integrated Learning) [9]. Meanwhile, the issue of integrating elementary foreign language vocabulary into the physical education process of senior preschool children, and its impact on speech development and the motivational domain, remained outside the scope of this research.

Methodological basis of the study

The concept of the personal activity approach in teaching foreign languages to preschool children by N. A. Gorlova [2].

The concept of developmental preschool education by V. T. Kudryavtsev and B. B. Egorov [4].

The concept of integration of motor and cognitive activities in physical education sessions with preschool children by M. A. Pravdova [6].

The study was conducted during the period from September 2025 to April 2026 within the network of private kindergartens “Bambika” and at the preschool department No. 5 of school 1400, city of Moscow. Thirty-two preschool-aged children (5–6 years old) participated in the study, including 23 girls and 9 boys. The children were divided into two groups – the control group (16 children, comprising 12 girls and 4 boys) and the experimental group (16 children, comprising 11

girls and 5 boys). In the experimental group, lessons were conducted following the author's partial program of physical education incorporating elementary foreign language vocabulary of the French language, with a frequency of once a week and a duration of 30 minutes per session. In the control group, lessons with preschool children were conducted without the use of foreign language vocabulary, in accordance with the core general educational preschool curriculum.

For the diagnosis of speech development and the motivational sphere of older preschool children, we employed the following diagnostic techniques, modified and developed by us in accordance with the research objectives.

The diagnostic technique by O. S. Ushakova and E. M. Strunina included a comprehensive assessment of the main parameters of child speech development, where the primary integrative indicator is connected speech [7]. This technique was implemented in the course of motor activity with older preschool children.

To assess the motivational sphere of children regarding physical culture, we developed and implemented a diagnostic method entitled "Conversation about Physical Culture." This method is designed to study the cognitive interest of senior preschool children in physical culture and sports and included a series of questions, for instance: "If you were offered to attend a kindergarten where there are no physical culture activities or a kindergarten where children participate in physical culture and play active games, which kindergarten would you choose?"

Diagnostics were conducted at the beginning of the study (September 2025) and at the conclusion of the experiment (May 2026).

Research Results

At the developmental stage of the experiment, the proprietary partial physical education program using elementary French vocabulary entitled 'Jump – Run – Play!' was implemented. The program was implemented in the experimental group with consideration of the age-specific and individual characteristics of the children's physical, cognitive, and speech development. The program is structured around three thematic blocks (autumn, winter, spring); the content component was presented in the form of counting-out rhymes, rhymed verses, and quatrains in French developed by the author, as well as musical compositions, in accordance with the calendar-thematic plan. The integration of elementary French vocabulary into physical education activities with older preschool children acted as a factor promoting the cognitive interest of children, laying the foundation for the harmonious comprehensive development of the child's personality in older preschool age [8].

After the completion of the formative stage of the experiment, a follow-up assessment of speech development and cognitive interest towards physical education activities among children in the control and experimental groups was conducted in order to compare the results at the beginning and at the end of the implementation of the author's partial program. A positive dynamic in speech development

indicators was observed in the experimental group, showing an improvement of 34% compared to the baseline indicators obtained at the ascertaining stage of the experiment. Positive trends in speech development outcomes demonstrate a statistically significant advantage of indicators in children of the experimental group compared to those in the control group ($t = 5.2$; $p < 0.01$).

Indicators of cognitive interest in physical education classes also revealed positive trends in outcomes among children in the experimental group (methodology ‘Conversations about Physical Education’). At the start of the formative experiment, boys and girls in the control and experimental groups showed similar average-level indicators. In March 2026, statistically significant differences in the cognitive interest indicators of children in the experimental group were revealed (10–15%, at $t = 2.12$, $p < 0.05$). The positive dynamics in cognitive interest indicators among boys and girls in both the control and experimental groups confirm the effectiveness of implementing the author’s partial physical education program utilizing elementary French foreign language vocabulary.

Conclusions

In the course of our experimental work on integrating elementary French foreign language vocabulary, we have concluded on the advisability of implementing this approach in the theory and practice of preschool education. The enrichment of children’s motor activity during physical education classes through the integration of elementary foreign language vocabulary stimulates speech development, cognitive interest, and motivation for physical activities in children; motor activity becomes more substantive and emotional, which also contributes to enhancing the effectiveness of the physical education process for senior preschool children.

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列夫·托尔斯泰原创教育思想对当今教育的活力
**THE VITALITY OF LEO TOLSTOY'S ORIGINAL PEDAGOGICAL
IDEAS FOR TODAY'S EDUCATION**

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摘要。俄罗斯联邦各级现代教育正在经历重大变革，在强化民族认同、提升儿童、家庭和教育领域专业人才培养质量、复兴教育传统以及将俄罗斯教育打造为世界领先水平等方面取得了显著进展。这些变革与托尔斯泰的理念相契合，即“对我们俄罗斯人民而言，公共教育是当下唯一能为全人类谋求最大幸福的自觉活动”[6，第34卷，第405页]。托尔斯泰的教育活动及其不朽的创作遗产，体现了他教育体系的完整性，为现代教育方法奠定了坚实的基础，并几个世纪以来一直是俄罗斯社会精神生活和文化不可或缺的一部分。本文旨在强调列夫·尼古拉·托尔斯泰教育思想的意义建构性，这些思想几个世纪以来一直指导着俄罗斯教育的发展方向。本文作者揭示了亚斯纳亚·波利亚纳的先驱托尔斯泰在教育领域提出的诸多概念的价值和语义意义，这些概念包括：俄罗斯的民族教育、儿童的和谐发展、教育者的引导作用、师生合作、个性化学习原则、非暴力教育以及儿童教育文学。在当今俄罗斯教育中，这些概念再次变得至关重要，需要深入的科学理解。

关键词：托尔斯泰的教育活动、俄罗斯教育、真正的人民教育、列夫·尼古拉·托尔斯泰的教育思想、民族认同。

Abstract. *Modern education at various levels in the Russian Federation is undergoing significant transformation, making progress toward strengthening its national identity, improving the quality of training professionals in the fields of childhood, family, and education, reviving pedagogical traditions in teaching and upbringing and establishing Russian education as a leader in the world. These transformations are in keeping with Tolstoy's understanding that "public education at the present time for us, Russian people, is the only conscious activity for achieving the greatest happiness for all of humanity" [6, vol. 34, p. 405]. Tolstoy's pedagogical activity*

itself and his immortal creative legacy, which reflect the integrity of his pedagogical system, they serve as a viable foundation for modern approaches to education, remaining an integral part of the spiritual life and culture of Russian society for centuries. The purpose of this article is to emphasize the meaning-forming significance of the pedagogical ideas of L. N. Tolstoy, which for centuries determined the educational guidelines in Russian education. The author of this article reveals the value and semantic significance of concepts that the Yasnaya Polyana visionary advanced in pedagogy, namely: national education in Russia, the harmonious development of the child, the guiding role of the educator, teacher-student collaboration, the principle of individualized learning, non-violent education, and educational children's literature. In today's Russian education, these concepts are once again becoming key, requiring deep scientific understanding.

Keywords: *Tolstoy's pedagogical activity, Russian education, genuine education for the people, pedagogical ideas of L. N. Tolstoy, national identity.*

L. Tolstoy developed a highly original system of education and upbringing. His name ranks among those of outstanding thinkers of the past and present. They are united by a keen interest in Russian education, a profound understanding of the subject and pedagogical methods, and, most importantly, a desire to create a unique system of public education. A man of extensive European education and fluent in several foreign languages, L. Tolstoy devoted his enormous, passionate heart to his native Russian people, desiring to see everyone, without exception, educated. He worked tirelessly, studying the pedagogical works of his predecessors, and traveled extensively, attempting to define a system of genuine education for the people.

Research methods:

– the axiological vector of the biographical method is shaped by the pedagogical works and activities of Leo Tolstoy, defining the compositional component of the author's reasoning as a dialogue;

– a critical analysis of historical and pedagogical sources and L. N. Tolstoy's original works contributed to the concretization of key pedagogical categories that recreate the originality and individuality of the individual in the era, demonstrating the meaning-forming significance and viability of Tolstoy's distinctive pedagogical ideas for modern education.

Even at the age of 15, L. Tolstoy was fascinated by the works of the French thinker Jean-Jacques Rousseau, whom he later called his teacher. In 1905, he wrote: "Rousseau never ages" [7, vol. 20, p. 582]. Throughout his life, L. Tolstoy showed a keen interest in Rousseau's pedagogical ideas on free education. Unconditionally rejecting the method of compulsory education, L. Tolstoy became even more convinced that a true school should be built solely on the principle of student freedom. "The school has been defined – to bring what is ready from life into a system"

[5, p. 399]. With this conviction, he began the search for a Russian educational system that would stem from the needs of the people. Foreign trips enriched Tolstoy with theoretical and practical information in the field of education. He returned to Russia loaded to the brim with pedagogical materials and overflowing with ideas. The study of pedagogical experience in other countries contributed to the formation of L. Tolstoy's firm conviction that "the only method of education is experience, and its only criterion is freedom" [4, p. 79]. In the process of searching for a method, a "criterion" of education, suitable for the Russian school and education in general, he believed that the school in Russia should be formed in accordance with its historical era, in which it should develop, in accordance with its history. Continuing to work in the interests of the correct interpretation and rational organization of the matter of education, Tolstoy absorbed the pedagogical ideas of thinkers of past eras and developed his own ideas on the upbringing and development of the child.

According to Tolstoy, a newborn child is the prototype of harmony, truth, beauty, and goodness. The French philosopher Rousseau also wrote about natural goodness as the starting point in human development: "Man is good by nature" [8, p. 108]. Sharing this assertion, Tolstoy himself exclaimed: "Man will be born perfect – that is the great word spoken by Rousseau, and this word, like a stone, will remain firm and true" [8, p. 287]. A newborn human being is beautiful, gifted, and through education it is necessary for this natural perfection to acquire new shades, so that the transition from the natural, natural state to the social state occurs. Harmony, within the defined natural boundaries, will bring freedom and happiness to man. A child "only needs material to be replenished harmoniously and comprehensively" [8, p. 288] – such was L. Tolstoy's pedagogical conviction. He was convinced that the teacher's personality and guiding role are crucial to the holistic, harmonious development of a child. To be a good teacher, one must master two rules: not only live well, work on oneself, and constantly improve, but also never hide anything from children. In "General Notes for the Teacher" (1872), Tolstoy cites love as an important quality of a teacher: "This quality is love... If a teacher combines love for the work and for the student, he is a perfect teacher" [8, p. 292].

The Yasnaya Polyana school, and later the schools in the Krapivinsky district of the Tula province, founded by Leo Tolstoy, became a multifaceted space for his pedagogical experience, reflecting his lofty and noble ideals in his quest to develop, educate, and raise peasant children, who – as descendants and representatives of the Russian people – were in need of a broad education. Unique in its innovation and humane approach to children, in which pedagogical theory was closely integrated with teaching practice, Tolstoy's school became a phenomenon in the education system not only in Russia but also abroad. In his pedagogical reflections, the founder of the Yasnaya Polyana school strove to establish the dual goal of educative teaching as the foundation of pedagogy, arriving at the idea that

a spiritual and moral person is born as a result of selfless love for people, animals, and inanimate nature. Thus, in October 1893, he wrote in his diary: "There are two ways of understanding the external world: one is the crudest and most inevitable way of understanding through the five senses... The other way is to, having learned love for oneself, then learn love for other beings... This method is what is called the poetic gift; it is love" [6, vol. 52, p. 101]. Using the example of the education and upbringing of peasant children at the Yasnaya Polyana school, Tolstoy demonstrated that their creative and moral potential is revealed when they become participants in the pedagogical process in a collaborative environment. The teacher should act not by force of coercion, but by the interest he awakens in the students. Tolstoy believed that the advancement of pedagogy lay in bringing the relationship between teacher and student closer to a natural one, and in reducing coercion. It is precisely this absence of coercion that presupposes freedom. Thus, Tolstoy considered the principle of freedom paramount in raising a child. In his diary for 1860, the writer noted: "...In education, equality and freedom are again paramount" [7, vol. 20, p. 229]. Not limiting himself to theoretical considerations regarding non-violent education, Tolstoy applied these pedagogical ideas in practical work at the Yasnaya Polyana School. He set forth his own views on the tasks of education, on what it should be like in order to most fully assist a person in his striving for the common good. This reasoning of Tolstoy represents the final conclusion he came to on such an important issue as the question of education. "That freedom is a necessary condition for any true education, both for students and for teachers, I acknowledge, as before..." [8, p. 452]. School is a free institution, the foundation of which is the personality of the student; education cannot be violent, it must give students pleasure. The great experimental educator L. Tolstoy believed in the question of non-violent education that "violence is used only as a result of haste and lack of respect for human nature" [8, p. 138].

Distinguished by his keen understanding of child psychology and his belief in creative potential, Tolstoy believed that "for a teacher immersed in the freedom of the school, each student has a unique character." Tolstoy the educator focused on developing this "special character," creative thought, and cognitive activity in children. His article "Who Should Learn Writing from Whom, the Peasant Children from Us, or We from the Peasant Children?" testifies to this talented work. At the Yasnaya Polyana School, he boldly implemented the ideas of free education in his own original interpretation, along with the principles of non-violent pedagogy. He sought to create a school where an atmosphere of natural relationships between teachers and students would foster active and creative work by teachers, defining the school's overall style. The ideas of respect for the individual child and freedom formed the foundation of the principle of individualized education. Tolstoy emphasized that individualization is possible only if the teacher is well-versed in their field.

Tolstoy placed particular emphasis on labor education, teaching children how to work not only mentally but also physically. "Manual labor... has always been considered the simplest and most natural application of the moral principle" [7, vol. 19, p. 497]. Our compatriot believed that it is necessary to demand as little as possible from others and give as much as possible. L. Tolstoy was convinced that labor education is a means of moral knowledge and participation in life in the broadest sense. In his opinion, education in school should be a continuation and development of family upbringing, where the principle of labor education is even more important, as it is reinforced by the authority and example of parents. "The habit of an idle life is worse for a person than any misfortune in life. Therefore, it is of the utmost importance that children be accustomed to work from a young age" [6, vol. 44, p. 206]. Learning a useful craft, in his opinion, is not an end in itself, but a means of bringing the student closer to the life of the people.

Tolstoy's pedagogical reflections did not go unnoticed by his contemporaries. The validity of his pedagogical questions found support not only among his followers in Russia but also abroad. Many of Tolstoy's articles from the journal "Yasnaya Polyana," which expanded on the program of public schools and labor education, were widely read by thoughtful educators worldwide, having a profound influence on the pedagogical thought of his time and retaining their relevance today. Tolstoy's correspondence with foreign educators addressed not only theoretical but also didactic issues. The fame of the Russian novel abroad and the popularity of Tolstoy's pedagogical views sparked interest in the Russian language. In many educational institutions, the study of Russian was introduced as a compulsory subject. In 1898, Tolstoy received a letter from Michel Kanner, a teacher at the Lyceums in Paris, informing him that a Russian language course had been introduced at the Parisian lyceums and that Russian writing and reading were being taught using the "New Russian Alphabet" and "The First Book for Reading." Tolstoy himself was the creator of these books, which he used to teach children in public schools. Now, even abroad, the "ABC" began to be used for utilitarian purposes, as a textbook. Enclosed with Kanner's letter was a message from forty-four Parisian lyceum students, expressing their deep admiration and sincere gratitude to "the highly respected thinker, the great writer, the superb teacher, whose fame resounds in France no less than in his homeland" [3, p. 145].

The renowned French scholar and Russian language teacher Paul Boyer, author of a Russian language textbook for French students, consulted Tolstoy for some of the facts needed to comment on the stories included in the textbook. All Russian texts were taken from Tolstoy's works, without adaptation or abbreviations, with detailed footnotes, grammatical and lexical comments. The stories from the "Azbuka" (ABCs) were also included in the Russian language textbook of Boyer.

The original results of Leo Tolstoy's creative work and teaching experience – the "Azbuka" and "Novaya Azbuka" – have become significant for the history of

Russian pedagogy and methodology, as well as Russian children's literature. "The writer-educator sharply opposed obsessive moralizing, pedantry, didacticism, and sheer bias. These requirements for school textbooks were clarified and expanded upon by the author during his teaching career; the content and general focus of the textbooks were determined" [2, p. 27]. Indeed, his textbooks not only enabled children to learn to read, write, and count, but also shaped their general outlook, moral principles, willingness to work, and love for the world around them and their homeland. Russian folklore became one of the first sources to which the author of "Azбука" turned, convinced that it (folklore) was understandable and close to the people because it was created by them.

L. Tolstoy considered pedagogical activity to be "the greatest undertaking," asserting, "...everything we desire can only be realized in future generations" [6, vol.73, p.45]. And he was right, and the meaningful significance of his pedagogical ideas determined the educational guidelines in Russian education for centuries. And the relevance of Tolstoy's ideas is proven in the educational practices of modern schools, in the pedagogical experience of more than one generation of Russian teachers.

"And, whatever they say, he is, first and foremost, a dreamer... He is a dreamer in pedagogy as well" [3, p. 234] – it is about L. Tolstoy even today. And this is not surprising, since even in his early youth he wrote in his diary: "There is a side to a dream that is better than reality; there is a side to reality that is better than a dream. Complete happiness would be the combination of both" [6, vol. 21, p. 254]. And he achieved this happiness by combining his pedagogical dreams and reality through his own pedagogical work.

"The paradox of the system's stability continues to excite the pedagogical thought of each new generation of teachers, for whom Tolstoy's pedagogical work continues to be a source of enlightenment of thinking people in different countries" [1, p. 4]. L. N. Tolstoy, as a great Russian educator, developed a democratic principle of teaching and upbringing, leaving us, his compatriots and all of humanity, his creative and pedagogical legacy. His original pedagogical ideas confirmed the truth that great ideas are born in the study of the experience of generations and peoples.

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大学环境中适应性体育文化的发展前景
**PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL
CULTURE IN THE UNIVERSITY ENVIRONMENT**

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摘要：本文基于对现有科学文献的分析，探讨了大学环境中适应性体育教育（AFC）的现状与发展前景。文章研究了确保适应性体育教育（AFC）课程有效性的主要措施、残疾学生教学组织方面存在的问题，以及常规课程对学生身心健康的影响。文章论证了采取系统性方法的必要性，包括制定个性化发展路径、对教师进行方法论培训、提供心理和教育支持、推进教学过程数字化以及构建无障碍环境。

关键词：适应性体育教育，残疾学生，融合教育，大学环境，康复训练，数字技术，心理和教育支持

Annotation: *The article examines the current state and prospects of adaptive physical culture (AFC) development in the university environment based on the analysis of current scientific publications. The main provisions ensuring the effectiveness of adaptive physical education (AFC) classes, the problems of organizing work with students with disabilities, as well as the impact of regular classes on the psychophysiological status of students are studied. The necessity of a systematic approach, including an individual trajectory, methodological training of teachers, psychological and pedagogical support, digitalization of the process and the development of a barrier-free environment, is substantiated.*

Keywords: *adaptive physical education, students with disabilities, inclusive education, university environment, physical rehabilitation, digital technologies, psychological and pedagogical support*

In the context of the modernization of the Russian higher education system, ensuring equal access to quality education for all categories of citizens, including people with disabilities, is becoming one of the priorities of state policy. Adaptive physical education (AFC) acts not only as a means of physical rehabilitation, but also as the most important tool for the social integration of students into the university environment. As O. A. Ermolaev notes, "in the current conditions of the educational process in higher educational institutions, there are methods of working with both the main group of students and students who, due to their physical characteristics, are unable to fully study in general groups".

Unlike physical therapy, which focuses primarily on restoring lost functions, adaptive physical education (AFC) in a university environment has a broader goal – the formation of an active lifestyle, socialization and improving the quality of life. The student age is a sensitive period for the development of physical, mental and social competencies, which gives adaptive physical education (AFC) classes special importance.

The purpose of this article is to identify key promising areas for the development of adaptive physical education (AFC) in Russian universities based on an analysis of current sources, considering modern scientific approaches, including the possibilities of digital transformation of the educational process.

In a study by Tarasov, Kozenko and Miroshnik, published in the journal "Physical Education and Student Sports" in 2024, the authors identified the main principles that ensure the effectiveness of adaptive physical education. They hypothesized that "an individual approach to each student, the correct selection of physical exercises, motivation and support, as well as the systematic nature of the занятия, play a key role in the effectiveness of adaptive physical education". At the same time, the most important factor for success is not just the adaptation of physical activity, but the creation of a psychologically comfortable environment that promotes positive motivation for exercise.

The practical experience described in the article by the Angarsk State Technical University (AnSTU) shows that activities such as playing checkers, chess, and darts, as well as general development exercises with a controlled load, are used in classes for students with disabilities who have minor visual or musculoskeletal impairments. The authors emphasize that "practical classes with individuals with health conditions allow them to expand their social circle with students in their group", which contributes to their social adaptation. However, practice shows that such forms of work are often fragmented and do not cover all nosological groups, which are categories that unite diseases that share common features: similar causes, mechanisms of development, clinical presentations, and often similar treatment methods.

Despite the positive trends, the development of adaptive physical culture (APC) in the university environment faces several serious problems, including:

- insufficient methodological training of teaching staff for working with different nosological groups;
- lack of specialized equipment and adapted gyms;
- lack of scientifically based programs that take into account the specifics of various diseases;
- psychological barriers for both students with disabilities (fear of failure, low self-esteem) and their healthy peers (lack of understanding, negative attitudes);
- low awareness of the administration of educational institutions about the real needs of students with disabilities in the field of physical education;
- there is a lack of in-house specialists in adaptive physical education, which means that classes are often taught by teachers who do not have specialized training.

The researchers emphasize that a teacher working with students with disabilities has the task of "studying the diseases of students and determining which group of nosological categories they belong to", as well as developing general developmental exercises considering individual limitations.

The study by E. V. Verdnikova and her co-authors, published in the journal "Theory and Practice of Physical Culture" (No. 1, 2024), deserves special attention. The authors have developed a physical rehabilitation methodology that includes three blocks of exercises (respiratory, corrective, and coordination exercises), which, according to their data, is "an effective means of rehabilitation for students with disabilities, as it is based on the adaptive capabilities of the body and is individualized".

Regular practice of the proposed method demonstrates positive dynamics of indicators of psychophysiological status in students with disabilities: a decrease in the level of anxiety, an improvement in concentration, an increase in emotional stability. This confirms the thesis that properly organized motor activity stimulates not only physical, but also mental processes, including attention, memory, and emotional stability.

An analysis of the topics covered in the scientific and practical journal Adaptive Physical Education allows us to identify the key areas of development in this field that are relevant for the university environment: adaptive physical education, adaptive sports, adaptive motor recreation, and physical rehabilitation.

The following areas of university practice seem promising:

1. Individualization of educational trajectories – the development of personalized programs based on the diagnosis of nosology and physical condition, with the ability to choose the format of classes (group, individual, mixed). This allows for the individual characteristics of each student without averaging the workload.

2. Technologization of the process – introduction of digital means of monitoring physical condition (heart rate monitoring, activity tracking), use of mobile applications for self-control and video materials for independent training. This becomes

especially relevant for students with mobility restrictions, who find it difficult to regularly attend in-person classes.

3. Interdisciplinary interaction is the integration of the efforts of physical education teachers, psychologists, doctors, social workers, and tutors. Regular consultations allow for timely adjustments to programs based on the students' health status.

4. The development of adaptive student sports is the creation of conditions for the participation of students with disabilities in competitions of various levels (from intra-university to national), including Paralympic sports. This increases motivation and promotes the formation of a positive image of physical activity.

5. Psychological and pedagogical support includes conducting training sessions on developing an inclusive culture among students and teachers, as well as working with students with disabilities to address their personal anxiety and academic motivation.

6. Training and professional development of personnel – introduction of adaptive physical education modules into master's programs and advanced training courses with mandatory practice in inclusive groups. This will help to eliminate the shortage of competent specialists.

It is important to emphasize that the development of adaptive physical culture in higher education institutions cannot be limited only to solving organizational and methodological problems. It is necessary to form an inclusive culture of the university environment in which students with disabilities are perceived not as a "problem group", but as full-fledged participants in the educational process, having equal opportunities for physical, social and professional development. This implies a revision of the attitude towards adaptive physical culture (APC) – from a "special discipline for the disabled" to a "universal technology of inclusion".

The formation of such a culture is possible through a system of educational activities, educational work among students and teachers, as well as through the personal successful experience of students with disabilities in university life (sports competitions, physical education events, and volunteer projects).

Thus, the prospects for the development of adaptive physical culture in the university environment are associated with the implementation of a complex of interrelated areas. Firstly, this includes the improvement of the scientific and methodological base, including the development and testing of effective methods that take into account the specific features of various nosological groups. Secondly, it involves the implementation of the principles of individualization and systematicity, which are recognized as key factors in the effectiveness of adaptive physical culture. Thirdly, it involves the technologicalization of the process and the interdisciplinary collaboration of specialists from various fields. Fourth, it is about targeted training and the development of an inclusive culture in the university environment.

The implementation of these areas requires not only the local efforts of individual universities, but also systematic state support: the development of new-generation

federal educational standards for adaptive physical education (AFC), targeted financing of adaptive infrastructure, the creation of resource centers and methodological platforms for the exchange of experience. Only if these conditions are met will adaptive physical education be able to fully realize its potential as a means of physical, mental and social well-being of students with disabilities.

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虚拟现实技术作为培养青少年安全行为模式的工具
**VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGIES AS A TOOL FOR
DEVELOPING SAFE BEHAVIORAL PATTERNS IN ADOLESCENTS**

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摘要：本文探讨了虚拟现实（VR）技术作为一种创新工具在青少年安全行为模式形成中的应用。青少年时期是一个发育阶段，青少年更容易出现冒险行为，因此安全教育是一项尤为重要的教学任务。传统的教学方法往往不足以帮助青少年有效应对需要快速评估、明智决策和负责任行动的危险情况。在此背景下，VR技术提供了一个沉浸式、可控且注重实践的环境，能够模拟危险情境，同时避免学习者遭受实际伤害。本文认为，VR模拟和角色扮演场景能够帮助青少年在安全的环境中分析后果、演练安全应对措施并内化行为准则，从而促进其情境意识、风险评估和负责任行为的培养。本文特别关注风险情境建模的教育潜力，它不仅能够培养具体的安全技能，还能增强青少年对自身决策的责任感。文章总结认为，基于虚拟现实（VR）的方法在预防性教育以及培养青少年自觉且稳定的安全行为模式方面具有巨大潜力。

关键词：青少年，安全行为，虚拟现实，VR模拟，风险情境，安全教育，预防性教育，情境意识，决策，责任行为。

Abstract. *This article examines virtual reality (VR) technologies as an innovative tool for the formation of safe behavioral patterns in adolescents. Adolescence is a developmental period marked by heightened vulnerability to risky behavior, which makes safety education a particularly relevant pedagogical task. Traditional instructional approaches often prove insufficient for preparing adolescents to respond effectively to hazardous situations that require rapid assessment, informed decision-making, and responsible action. In this context, VR offers immersive, controlled, and practice-oriented environments that simulate dangerous situations without exposing learners to real harm. The article argues that VR simulations and role-playing scenarios support the development of situational awareness, risk assessment, and responsible behavior by enabling adolescents to analyze consequences, rehearse safe responses, and internalize behavioral algorithms*

in a secure setting. Particular attention is given to the educational potential of risk-situation modeling, which fosters not only specific safety skills but also personal responsibility for one's decisions. The article concludes that VR-based methods have significant potential for preventive education and for cultivating a conscious and stable model of safe behavior in adolescents.

Keywords: *adolescence, safe behavior, virtual reality, VR – simulations, risk situations, safety education, preventive education, situational awareness, decision-making, responsible behavior.*

Adolescence is a critical developmental period characterized by rapid physical, cognitive, emotional, and social changes. During this stage, individuals begin to form stable patterns of behavior, develop a sense of identity, and acquire the skills necessary for independent decision-making. At the same time, adolescents are particularly vulnerable to risky and unsafe behaviors due to heightened emotional reactivity, peer influence, and incomplete development of self-regulation mechanisms [4]. For this reason, the formation of safe behavioral patterns during adolescence represents an important task for educators, psychologists, and other professionals involved in youth development.

In recent years, the growing complexity of the social environment has intensified the need for innovative approaches to safety education. Traditional instructional methods, while valuable, often have limited effectiveness in preparing adolescents for real-life situations that require quick assessment, responsible choices, and appropriate responses to risk [2]. As a result, there is increasing interest in interactive and practice-oriented technologies that can simulate potentially dangerous scenarios without exposing learners to actual harm. Among such technologies, virtual reality has emerged as a particularly promising tool.

Virtual reality technologies provide immersive, controlled, and highly engaging environments in which adolescents can observe, analyze, and practice safe behavior in realistic contexts. By recreating everyday and emergency situations, VR enables users to experience the consequences of their actions and develop behavioral strategies in a safe settings [1]. This experiential dimension makes virtual reality especially valuable for reinforcing situational awareness, decision-making skills, and responsible conduct. In addition, the motivational and interactive nature of VR may increase learners' involvement and improve the effectiveness of safety-related education.

Despite the growing attention to virtual reality in education and training, its potential for shaping safe behavioral patterns in adolescents remains insufficiently explored. Existing studies have primarily focused on technical aspects of implementation, while pedagogical and developmental outcomes require further investigation [4]. In particular, more research is needed to understand how VR-based interventions influence adolescents' attitudes toward risk, their

ability to respond appropriately in hazardous situations, and the long-term sustainability of acquired behavioral skills.

The present article examines virtual reality technologies as a tool for developing safe behavioral patterns in adolescents. It considers the educational potential of VR, its advantages over traditional methods, and its possible applications in safety-oriented training. By analyzing the role of immersive technologies in adolescent development, the article seeks to contribute to the discussion of innovative approaches to preventive education and the formation of responsible behavior in young people.

In his work with adolescents, the author employs the method of simulating risk situations through role-playing games and VR simulations. The simulation of risk situations plays a key role in preparing adolescents to act under conditions of real threats. However, its value lies not only in the development of specific safety skills. Through participation in such activities young people acquire a crucial quality – an awareness of personal responsibility for their own decisions.

Analyzing the possible consequences of their actions becomes a natural part of adolescents' thinking. Through regular practice in simulating various scenarios, learners begin to assess the degree of risk in everyday situations automatically. For example, by becoming accustomed to calculating possible outcomes in game-based scenarios involving fire or aggression, young people transfer this analytical approach to real life.

The psychological mechanism underlying this effect is based on the formation of stable neural connections. When adolescents repeatedly “experience” a dangerous situation in a safe environment, clear response algorithms are developed. Over time, these behavioral patterns become automated, enabling prompt action even under conditions of stress.

Unlike traditional safety lectures, simulation:

1. provides immediate practical experience;
2. develops the ability to analyze situations;
3. enables a more balanced assessment of risks when faced with dangerous circumstances.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the authors' program for developing safe behavior. The research methods included comparative analysis, the modeling method, and test-based measurements (the “Study of Risk Propensity” technique by A. G. Shmelev). The sample consisted of 80 adolescents aged 13–15 years.

The program we developed represents an innovative synthesis of psychological and pedagogical approaches and modern technologies, particularly virtual reality. It should be noted that VR-based scenarios of dangerous situations constitute an optimal means of developing safe behavior, as adolescents are required to analyze the situation and construct an appropriate model of behavior within it [5]. At the

same time, each of their actions is monitored, which subsequently makes it possible to adjust the stages of exiting a risk situation.

The program is designed for 24 sessions. The duration of one session is 120 minutes. This length of time is optimal for adolescents' actions within a particular risk situation. The situations themselves are organized into three levels, ranging from simple to complex.

The content block includes situations of uncertainty when being in an unfamiliar place, accompanied by the fall of a bulky object. At the first, simple, level, the adolescent must merely choose a safe trajectory for passing by an unstable object. At the more complex level, there are several objects, not all of which are within the character's field of vision; this requires a comprehensive analysis of the situation and a multi-stage strategy for resolving it.

The methodological basis of the program is the combination of virtual reality technologies and story-based play. This combination makes it possible to create an educational environment conducive to the successful training of adolescents in safe behavior.

The use of VR simulators is a technology that allows any dangerous situation to be modeled without emotional or physical risk. Virtual reality makes it possible to enact scenarios that cannot be implemented in school or in supplementary education settings. VR technology not only engages all adolescents but also allows their mistakes to be recorded for further reflection. In this way, critical thinking and analytical skills are developed, without which safe behavioral skills cannot be formed. As noted above, when used in a methodologically appropriate manner, VR simulations reduce stress among adolescents and contribute to a calm emotional background. The gradual introduction of increasing complexity in risk situations helps prevent psychological overload.

The value component of the program lies in the relevance of the situations, which may occur in everyday life. This helps maintain participants' intrinsic motivation and teaches them to value safety in the context of preserving health and life.

Our experience showed that participants in the experimental group demonstrated the ability to exit risk situations without loss, as they anticipated their actions and analyzed the environment comprehensively. This distinguished them from the control group of learners. Monitoring of the program's effectiveness indicates that adolescents in the experimental group became more serious about observing safety rules compared with the control sample.

However, methodological issues were also identified during the study. In particular, clear criteria are needed for assessing the character's behavior in a risk situation for different age groups.

Instructional task: "After the objects have fallen, assess the area: approach it or ensure safety and call for help."

Expected behavior:

- do not approach an unstable area;
- do not remove objects independently;
- assess overhead risks;
- report to the responsible person;
- wait until the situation stabilizes.

The overarching educational line consists in ensuring a transition from reactive behavior to a proactive algorithm:

noticed → assessed → stepped back → chose a route → did not exacerbate the situation.

The series of scenarios forms an integrated model of safe behavior in a changing environment.

In conclusion, the proposed VR scenarios demonstrate considerable pedagogical potential for the development of safe behavior in adolescents. Their gradual structure, ranging from simple recognition of risk to more complex decision-making in dynamic and uncertain environments, enables learners to move from reactive responses to conscious and algorithmic action. By immersing adolescents in realistic but controlled hazardous situations, VR creates conditions for the formation of situational awareness, risk assessment skills, and responsible behavior.

The sequence of scenarios contributes to the development of a stable model of safe conduct:

notice → assess → step back → choose a safe route → avoid aggravating the situation

Such an approach encourages adolescents not only to respond appropriately to immediate threats, but also to anticipate possible consequences and take responsibility for their actions. In this way, VR scenarios serve as an effective educational tool for cultivating both practical safety skills and a conscious attitude toward personal and collective safety.

Thus, the modeling of risk situations can be considered an effective tool in the process of developing safe behavior. However, the success of its application depends on the establishment of clear criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of scenarios, the behavior of participants in a simulated risk situation, and the conditions for integration into the educational system. Further research will focus on developing an algorithm for the use of VR technologies, taking into account the challenges of a technogenic society.

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开发基于 VUE.JS 框架的分子热力学虚拟实验室，旨在提高学生的认知兴趣。

**DEVELOPMENT OF A VIRTUAL LABORATORY FOR
MOLECULAR THERMODYNAMICS BASED ON THE VUE.
JS FRAMEWORK AS A MEANS OF ENHANCING STUDENTS'
COGNITIVE INTEREST**

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摘要：本文探讨了基于 JavaScript 框架 Vue.js 3 和 Composition API 开发的分子热力学虚拟实验室。该模拟器包含一个带有可移动活塞的双室模型、分子动力学可视化、P-V 图和麦克斯韦-玻尔兹曼分布直方图。本文重点关注未来物理教师的培养以及他们激发学生认知兴趣的能力。文中描述了使用皮尔逊一致性系数进行教学研究的方法。研究表明，使用该交互式模拟器能够显著提高学生的认知兴趣 ($p < 0.05$)。

关键词：虚拟实验室，Vue.js，分子热力学，认知兴趣，交互式可视化，教学实验，物理教师培养。

Abstract. *The article discusses the development of a virtual laboratory for molecular thermodynamics based on the JavaScript framework Vue.js 3 using the Composition API. The simulator features a two-chamber model with a movable piston, molecular dynamics visualization, a P-V diagram, and a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution histogram. Particular attention is given to the preparation of future physics teachers and the development of their readiness to foster students' cognitive interest. The methodology of pedagogical research using Pearson's concordance criterion is described. It was established that using the interactive simulator significantly increases the level of students' cognitive interest ($p < 0.05$).*

Keywords: *virtual laboratory, Vue.js, molecular thermodynamics, cognitive interest, interactive visualization, pedagogical experiment, preparation of physics teachers.*

Introduction

In the context of the digital transformation of education, the issue of improving the effectiveness of teaching natural science disciplines is relevant. Physics is traditionally

associated by students with significant difficulties in comprehending abstract concepts [1]. In this regard, the development of cognitive interest constitutes a key factor in the success of the educational process. This issue gains particular significance in the context of preparing future physics teachers, since the overall quality of physics education directly depends on their professional readiness to cultivate cognitive interest in school students. A modern physics teacher must possess not only fundamental knowledge of the subject but also methods to activate students' educational and cognitive activities through the use of digital educational resources.

According to research by K. A. Kocharyan, the development of students' cognitive interests in physics education requires the application of specialized methods that stimulate learning activities [1]. The use of multimedia technologies stimulates the cognitive interest of children and adolescents [2], while virtual laboratories enable the visualization of processes invisible to the naked eye [3]. Analysis of the works by V. M. Gulin and O. F. Ognjeva demonstrates that virtual physics laboratories are becoming a full-fledged alternative to traditional laboratory practical sessions [4].

The purpose of the study is the development and approbation of a virtual molecular thermodynamics laboratory based on Vue.js as a means of developing cognitive interest among students during the training of future physics teachers.

Cognitive interest is regarded in educational psychology as a selective orientation of the individual towards objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, accompanied by an emotionally positive attitude towards the process of their cognition. According to M. L. Popova and O. S. Gibelgaus, the development of cognitive interest in school students during physics lessons requires the creation of engaging educational situations [5]. For a future educator, it is important not only to understand the mechanisms of cognitive interest formation but also to master tools that enable the creation of such situations in their own pedagogical practice. Computer modeling of physical processes facilitates the development of skills in physical modeling and the enhancement of critical thinking [6]. Research by A. V. Nikitin and co-authors demonstrates that computer modeling in physics encompasses all stages of modeling: problem formulation, mathematical modeling, software implementation, and computational experiment [7]. The mastery of such tools during professional training at a pedagogical university enhances the future physics teacher's readiness to organize students' research activities and to foster their cognitive interest in the subject.

Materials and methods

The choice of technological platform is determined by requirements for performance and interactivity. The study by S. V. Kozlov and P. L. Ilyin demonstrates that among modern frameworks for web applications, solutions based on component architecture are popular [8]. The Vue.js framework features a progressive paradigm, the Composition API, a reactive state management system, and excellent integration with HTML5 Canvas [9]. In physical modeling, Vue.js enables efficient binding

of the model state to the visual representation via reactive properties, allowing the separation of the physics engine and the rendering layer [9]. The use of gamification elements in physics education promotes increased learner motivation [10].

The developed virtual laboratory is a single-page web application built on Vue.js 3, utilizing the Composition API and the Vite build system. Its architecture comprises a molecular dynamics engine, a physical model of the piston system, an HTML5 Canvas visualization module, a statistics collection subsystem, and a charting module.

The physics engine implements a two-dimensional model of the motion of ideal gas molecules accounting for elastic collisions. A Gaussian distribution is applied for the generation of initial velocities. Pressure is calculated as the sum of momenta transferred by molecules to the walls per unit time. The interface includes a control panel (selection of gas, adjustment of the number of molecules, piston control, heating/cooling), a real-time molecular visualization area, and a physical quantities monitoring unit.

The simulator interface, depicted in Fig. 1, provides intuitive control over the experiment parameters and allows real-time observation of the behavior of the molecular system. Color coding of particle velocities, dynamic movement of the piston driven by pressure differences, and instantaneous display of physical quantities create a clear correspondence between microscopic processes and macroscopic thermodynamic parameters. The diagnostic module comprises a P–V diagram and a Maxwell–Boltzmann velocity distribution histogram, enabling learners to independently establish the qualitative and quantitative relationships that form the basis of molecular-kinetic theory.

Figure 1 – Interface of the virtual laboratory for molecular thermodynamics

To verify the effectiveness of the developed laboratory in fostering cognitive interest and enhancing the professional readiness of future educators, a formative pedagogical experiment was conducted in two stages: confirmatory (diagnosis of the initial level) and formative (pilot testing of the tool). The study was conducted during the spring semester of the 2024/2025 academic year at a pedagogical university with 2nd and 3rd year students enrolled in the 44.03.01 “Pedagogical Education” program (profile “Physics”).

The sample comprised 128 students: the experimental group (EG) – 66 participants, and the control group (CG) – 62 participants. The groups were equivalent in terms of preparation level ($p > 0.05$). Diagnostics were conducted using a motivational domain questionnaire, an express diagnostics method for academic motivation, and an author-developed questionnaire assessing readiness to use digital educational resources in professional activities. The level of interest was assessed across three categories: high, medium, and low. Pearson’s χ^2 goodness-of-fit test was applied for statistical processing.

At the stage of the ascertaining experiment, all participants were provided with a complex of diagnostic methodologies. The obtained data indicated the absence of statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups ($p > 0.05$), which confirmed the initial equivalence of the groups. During the formative stage, students of the experimental group engaged with the virtual laboratory in a blended learning format: independent investigation using the simulator remotely, followed by discussion of the results and methodological aspects of its application during face-to-face sessions. The control group studied the corresponding material using traditional methods.

Results and Discussion

The results are presented in Table 1. In the experimental group, the proportion of students with a high level of cognitive interest increased from 16.7% to 37.9% (an absolute increase of 21.2 percentage points), while in the control group it increased from 14.5% to 21.0% (an increase of 6.5 percentage points).

Table 1 – Dynamics of students’ cognitive interest levels, %

Level of Interest	Beginning (experimental)	End (experimental.)	Start (control)	End (control)
High	16.7	37.9	14.5	21.0
Medium	62.1	54.9	62.9	61.2
Low	21.2	7.2	22.6	17.8

The analysis of the dynamics of cognitive interest levels, presented in Fig. 2, visually demonstrates the advantage of the experimental group at all stages of the study. To verify the statistical significance of the differences at the final stage,

the Pearson χ^2 test was applied. At a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and degrees of freedom $df = 2$, the critical value is $\chi^2_{crit} = 5.99$. The empirical value of the χ^2 test, $\chi^2_{emp} = 9.18$, exceeds the critical value from the table. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no differences is rejected ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2 – Dynamics of the level of students’ cognitive interest

The growth coefficient of high-level interest in the experimental group exceeded the control group’s indicator by a factor of 3.3. The decrease in the proportion of students with low levels of interest in the experimental group amounted to 14.0 percentage points. (from 21.2% to 7.2%), in the control group, only 4.8 percentage points (from 22.6% to 17.8%). Qualitative analysis of responses showed that students reported increased confidence in using digital resources in their future pedagogical work and expressed the intention to use similar simulators when conducting their own physics lessons.

Conclusions

The developed software package is a single-page web application built on Vue.js 3 (Composition API, Vite bundler), implementing a two-chamber ideal gas model with a movable piston. The physical engine performs calculations of elastic molecular collisions, piston dynamics under the pressure difference, and real-time construction of the P-V diagram at a refresh rate of 60 FPS. The modular architecture enables adapting the simulator to other sections of school and university physics without altering the core engine.

The trial was conducted at the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education ‘Azov State Pedagogical University named after

P. D. Osipenko.' The study involved 128 students in their 2nd and 3rd years of the 44.03.01 'Pedagogical Education' program (profile 'Physics'): 66 students in the experimental group and 62 in the control group. The experimental group used the simulator in a blended format (remote independent study combined with in-person discussion of its application methodology), while the control group followed the traditional approach.

Statistical analysis using Pearson's χ^2 test ($df = 2$, $\alpha = 0.05$) revealed significant differences in the dynamics of cognitive interest between groups at the final stage of the experiment ($\chi^2_{emp} = 9.18$ versus $\chi^2_{crit} = 5.99$; $p < 0.05$). The proportion of students in the experimental group with a high level of interest increased from 16.7% to 37.9% (an increase of 21.2 percentage points), whereas in the control group, the corresponding figure rose from 14.5% to 21.0% (an increase of 6.5 percentage points). The reduction in the number of students with a low level of interest in the experimental group amounted to 14.0 percentage points compared to 4.8 percentage points in the control group.

Students of the experimental group reported in a qualitative survey an increase in confidence when using digital resources in physics lessons and an intention to incorporate such simulators into their own practice. This indicates the formation not only of cognitive motivation but also of the professional preparedness of the future teacher for designing a digital educational environment.

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19世纪英国在亚洲的地缘政治利益
**GEOPOLITICAL INTERESTS OF GREAT BRITAIN IN ASIA
IN THE 19TH CENTURY**

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摘要：英国力图尽可能广泛地扩张其影响力。这包括在尼泊尔和不丹的军事行动，以及英阿战争（1838–1842年和1878–1880年），这两场战争确立了英国对阿富汗的控制。在1857–1859年的印度兵变之后，英国议会于1858年颁布了《印度政府法案》，将权力从东印度公司移交给英国王室。控制战略要地是其核心关注点：阿富汗和俾路支斯坦对英国在中亚的政策具有重要意义。印度被视为大英帝国的重要组成部分，常被誉为“皇冠上的明珠”。

关键词：英国，大博弈，印度，利益。

Abstract. *Great Britain endeavored to extend its influence as extensively as possible. This included military campaigns in Nepal and Bhutan, as well as the Anglo-Afghan Wars (1838–1842 and 1878–1880), which established British control over Afghanistan. Following the Sepoy Rebellion (1857–1859), in 1858 Parliament enacted the Government of India Act, transferring authority from the East India Company to the Crown. Control over strategic regions was a central concern: Afghanistan and Baluchistan held considerable significance for British policy in Central Asia. India was regarded as a crucial component of the British Empire, often described as the ‘jewel in the crown.’*

Keywords: *Great Britain, The Great Game, India, interests.*

The Vienna System of international relations—refers to the system of international relations established in Europe following the Napoleonic Wars, codified by the Congress of Vienna in 1814–1815. Within this system, the concept of the ‘great powers’ (Austria, Great Britain, Russia, Prussia) was articulated for the first time, and their interactions largely determined the dynamics of the international order. Great Britain held a pivotal role in the Vienna system by virtue of being one of the victorious powers and establishing its fundamental principles. At the Congress

of Vienna, Great Britain was represented by R. S. Castlereagh and A. W. Wellington. London sought to construct a balanced system in Europe, wherein each great power was engaged in rivalry with its neighboring states, but no single state could overpower all its adversaries. This measure prevented the emergence of a new continental superpower analogous to Napoleon, while concurrently embroiling the European powers in mutual opposition, thereby inhibiting their engagement in the colonial partitioning of the world. Following the Congress of Vienna, Great Britain acquired the island of Malta, the island of Ceylon, and the Cape Colony in southern Africa. Great Britain aspired to act as the 'conductor' and arbiter within the framework of the 'European Concert.' Therefore, Great Britain constituted one of the principal actors within the Vienna system, although its role exhibited particular characteristics shaped by its geopolitical interests and strategic objectives. The Vienna System persisted for approximately forty years and concluded with the outbreak of the Crimean War in 1853–1856.

From a formal perspective, the Vienna System upheld general stability in Europe; however, beyond its borders, tensions among the great powers increasingly intensified. For Great Britain, India remained a pivotal component of global security; consequently, any measures taken by Russia to reinforce its presence in the Caucasus, expand within the Eurasian steppe zone, and advance toward Central Asia were regarded by British elites as a potential threat to strategic communications and colonial dominion. The inherent logic of expansion of the two empires – Russia as a continental power striving to consolidate its position in the Eurasian space, and Britain as a maritime empire concerned with securing trade routes and approaches to India – rendered the conflict of interests structurally inevitable. In this context, as N. A. Halfin emphasized, the Anglo-Russian confrontation in Asia was the outcome of the rivalry between two expanding powers whose strategic orientations and spheres of influence increasingly overlapped.²⁶¹

A pivotal moment in the history of British presence in India was the Battle of Plassey (23 June 1757). In this confrontation, the forces of the British East India Company, commanded by Robert Clive, defeated the army of the Nawab of Bengal, Siraj-ud-Daulah, who counted on support from segments of the local elite as well as French involvement. The victory at²

Plassey held significance extending far beyond a localized military triumph: it paved the way for the British to establish political influence in Bengal and

¹ Khalfin N. A. *Russia's Policy in Central Asia, 1857–1868*. London: Central Asian Research Centre in association with St Antony's College (Oxford), 1964 P. 5–15

² Robert Clive // *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. – URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Robert-Clive> (accessed: 16 April 2026).

constituted the foundation for the subsequent transformation of the company from a commercial entity into the effective sovereign authority over Indian territory¹.

The establishment of British dominion over Bengal afforded Britain not only a strategic foothold but also access to one of the most prosperous regions of South Asia, thereby significantly augmenting the financial resources underpinning British presence. Thereafter, it was precisely the economic foundation of Bengal that enabled the East India Company to expand its administrative infrastructure, sustain regular military forces, and progressively displace both indigenous rivals and European competitors.

Thus, Plassey became one of the initial points in the establishment of the British colonial order in India and the subsequent expansion of London's influence in Asia². For Great Britain, India gradually emerged as the central core of the imperial system – in strategic, financial, and symbolic dimensions. The Indian sphere served as a source of revenue and reinforced the conception of Britain's global status as a preeminent power. Moreover, dominion over India enabled the projection of power into neighboring regions: the Persian Gulf, the Indian Ocean, and the trade routes leading towards China and Southeast Asia. In this context, control over India constituted not merely one of the colonial acquisitions but a structural foundation of the comprehensive British global policy³.

Great Britain acquired numerous economic, political, social, and cultural advantages in India, which exerted a significant influence on both the colonizer and the colonized. India was frequently referred to as the 'jewel in the crown of the British Empire' owing to its significance as a source of resources and a tool for imperial consolidation.

As demonstrated by Andrew Porter, during the nineteenth century the Indian territory was perceived by the British not merely as an administrative-colonial entity but also as a fundamental component of the project of a global empire, intimately connected with the ideological and religious foundations of expansion, particularly through missionary activity. The empire operated as a system not only

¹ Battle of Plassey // National Army Museum. – URL: <https://www.nam.ac.uk/explore/battle-plassey> (accessed: 16 April 2026).

² Battle of Plassey // National Army Museum. – URL: <https://www.nam.ac.uk/explore/battle-plassey> (accessed: 16 April 2026).

³ Porter A. N. *Religion versus Empire? British Protestant Missionaries and Overseas Expansion, 1700–1914*. Manchester; New York: Manchester University Press, 2004 P. 213

of economic and military control but also of cultural influence, with India occupying one of the central positions¹.

By the beginning of the 19th century, several sources of threat to British control over India had emerged:

1 The Shahs of Persia, particularly under Abbas Mirza (1789–1833), sought to expand their influence to the east, thereby threatening British interests in the Persian Gulf.

2 Under the leadership of Ranjit Singh (1780–1839), the Sikh Empire became a formidable military power in northwestern India.

3 Russia actively conducted military campaigns in the Caucasus and in Central Asia

In response to these external threats, the British government and the administration of British India gradually formulated the so-called buffer states strategy. Its objective consisted in the creation and maintenance of a territorial ‘security belt’ between the territories of the British Empire and zones of Russian influence; as such a barrier

Afghanistan was primarily considered, and to a certain extent Persia, since through these territories a route potentially leading to the northwestern borders of India could pass. This policy entailed preserving the external independence of these states while simultaneously augmenting British political and diplomatic influence – thus effectively transforming them into instruments of strategic containment².

The buffer state doctrine rested on a widely held assumption in nineteenth-century British military and political thought that Russia sought access to the Indian Ocean and, in the long term, might attempt to exert pressure upon India via Central Asia and Afghanistan. Within British strategic culture, this conception became a persistent element in threat assessment, despite the highly challenging geographical conditions of such a campaign and the lack of practical means available to Russia for a large-scale invasion of the Indian subcontinent during most periods³.

Contemporary studies demonstrate that Russian policy in Central Asia was primarily aimed at reinforcing borders and exerting control over the steppe regions,

¹ Bowen H. V. *Revenue and Reform: The Indian Problem in British Politics, 1757–1773*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1991 P. 1–5

² Masato Toriya *Afghanistan as a Buffer State between Regional Powers in the Late Nineteenth Century*. P. 49

³ Martin J. Bayley *Imperial ontological (in)security: ‘buffer states’, IR, and the case of Anglo-Afghan relations*. P. 29, 31

while the perception of an inevitable Russian invasion of India frequently overstated the empire's actual capabilities¹.

Thus, the buffer strategy functioned not merely as a defensive measure but became part of a broader Anglo-Russian competition for influence in Eurasia – a process which by the mid-19th century had developed into a sustained model of confrontation known as The Great Game. As emphasized by K. A. Fursov, Russia's advance into Central Asia was primarily guided by strategic considerations and occurred within the framework of geopolitical rivalry with Britain, thereby shaping the enduring configuration of Anglo-Russian relations in the Asian sphere.

The expression 'The Great Game' was first employed by **Arthur Conolly**, an officer in the service of the East India Company. He inscribed it in the margins of a copy of a letter sent by the British political agent in Kabul to the governor of Bombay in 1840. The term was popularized by **Rudyard Kipling** in his novel *Kim*, published in 1901.

In summary, it is important to emphasize that for Great Britain the principal objective was the retention and expansion of British India – a vital colonial possession regarded as the 'jewel in the crown' of the empire. The British elite feared a potential Russian invasion from the north, as all historical invasions of India had been launched from the interior regions of Central Asia (Alexander the Great, Babur, et al.). Moreover, Great Britain sought to prevent the consolidation of Russian power along its southern frontiers and to secure access to Central Asian commodities, particularly cotton.

The British presence in India exerted a multifaceted impact on the political, economic, social, and cultural spheres of the country. Its outcomes were contradictory and had long-term consequences.

The actual conclusion of the confrontation was effected by an agreement between Russia and Great Britain, signed in Saint Petersburg on 18 (31) August 1907. This treaty delineated spheres of influence in Asia and constituted a turning point in the balance of power on the eve of the First World War.

¹ Fursov K. A. Imperial Economic Policy in Russian Turkestan and British India: Similarities and Differences // *Vostok, Oriens*. 2010 No. 6, p. 40.

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数字时代的音乐新闻：流派结构与功能系统的具体特征
**MUSIC JOURNALISM IN A DIGITAL AGE: GENRE STRUCTURE
AND THE SPECIFICS OF FUNCTION SYSTEM**

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摘要：本文旨在探讨当代数字媒体传播空间中音乐新闻体裁结构的具体特征，并识别推动其转型的因素。音乐新闻的多体裁特性既源于文化生活事件的多样性，也源于其与社交网络、视频托管平台和即时通讯服务的融合。本研究着重分析了体裁与信息触发因素（事件）之间的关联，这些关联反过来又影响着该传播模式下的特定话语实践。

关键词：音乐新闻，数字化，大众传媒，体裁转型，目标受众，事件。

Abstract. *This article is dedicated to examining the specifics of the genre structure of music journalism within the communicative space of contemporary digital media, and it identifies the factors driving its transformation. The polygenre nature of music journalism is determined both by the diversity of cultural life events and by its integration with social networks, video hosting platforms, and messaging services. Within the scope of the study, correlations between genres and informational triggers (events) are identified, which, in turn, influence specific discursive practices in this mode of communication.*

Keywords: *music journalism, digitization, mass media, genre transformation, target audience, event.*

Introduction

The contemporary media environment constitutes a complex system wherein digital technologies play a decisive role in transforming traditional forms of engagement with information and cultural content. The music sector has experienced one of the most radical transformations in the digital era, resulting in the emergence of a diverse system of specialized internet resources. These resources have not only become an alternative to traditional channels for distributing musical content but have also established a fundamentally new communicative environment characterized by unique typological features, genre specificity, and operational mechanisms.

The digitalization of musical culture has given rise to a phenomenon that can be described as a parallel reality of musical communication, in which the traditional roles of creator, distributor, and consumer of content are continually reconfigured. The operation of online musical resources is conditioned by the complex interplay of technological, economic, social, and cultural factors, which generate a unique dynamic in the consumption and production of musical content within cyberspace [4]. The media environment shapes a distinctive perception of musical content, wherein informational value frequently yields to spectacle and emotional components, reflecting overarching trends in contemporary television broadcasting characterized by its orientation toward mass audiences and audience ratings [3].

The digital environment has expanded the requirements for the format of content presentation. As noted by researcher O.A. Dmitrieva, “in the online environment, the professional competencies of the journalist undergo transformation. A contemporary music journalist must be a multimedia specialist: producing texts, working with video and audio content, conducting live broadcasts, and managing the publication’s social media accounts” [1].

The research methodology is conditioned by the complex multi-level nature of the studied phenomenon and represents a set of interdisciplinary methods, with priority given to observation and description methods, the inductive-deductive method, and discourse analysis.

Main part

Before addressing the genre structure of musical internet resources, it is essential to highlight their fundamental distinction from traditional media with regard to interactivity and personalization. Modern internet platforms function on the principle of multi-vectority, enabling users to navigate nonlinearly within the information space. The algorithmic recommendation system integrated into most music services analyzes user behavioral patterns, generating an individualized content stream that fundamentally alters the logic of music consumption [8].

The functional differentiation of musical internet resources occurs along several primary directions. Streaming services such as Spotify and Yandex.Music employ a subscription-based content access model, providing users with practically unlimited selection of musical compositions without the necessity of local storage. These platforms function on the basis of complex machine learning algorithms that analyze musical preferences and audio characteristics of works to create personalized recommendations.

A fundamentally different mechanism of operation is demonstrated by resources targeted at the music community, such as SoundCloud and Bandcamp. Their functional specificity consists in the creation of infrastructure for direct interaction between musicians and their audience, thereby minimizing intermediary links [7]. These platforms function as social ecosystems where not only the distribution of

musical content takes place, but also the formation of specific communities of interest, the exchange of experience, and professional communication among musicians.

In the context of information overload, a key factor determining the success of a musical project is not only the quality of the content but also the effectiveness of the algorithms governing its dissemination. Music platforms operate as complex cognitive filters that determine which content is presented to the user, thereby creating a specific ‘attention funnel.’ This mechanism underpins the phenomenon of virality in musical content, wherein certain works experience exponential spread through recommendation systems and social networks.

The system of online music resources is characterized by intensive interaction with other digital platforms. Integration with social networks, video hosting platforms, and messaging services creates a multilayered structure for content distribution, whereby musical works circulate through diverse communication channels. This mechanism of cross-platform content circulation establishes a new paradigm of music consumption, distinguished by fragmentation, multimodality, and transmediality.

When analyzing the specifics of the operation of musical internet resources, the phenomenon of algorithmic content curation merits particular attention. Unlike traditional media, where content selection was conducted by professional editors and program directors, on digital platforms this role is fulfilled by machine learning algorithms. These algorithms analyze not only explicit user preferences (such as likes and playlist additions), but also implicit behavioral patterns (listening duration, frequency of track skipping), thereby constructing a multidimensional model of musical preferences.

The functional characteristic of algorithmic curation consists in its capacity to detect non-obvious correlations among musical preferences, thereby enabling the recommendation of content that may potentially interest the user but lies outside their usual sphere of attention. This mechanism establishes a distinct balance between the familiar and the novel, providing a comfortable domain of musical consumption enriched with elements of surprise and discovery.

The specificity of online music platforms is also evident in the feedback mechanisms existing between content creators and consumers. Comments, ratings, the ability to create user playlists and their public sharing constitute a new model of musical communication, wherein the boundaries between content production and consumption become increasingly blurred. The user functions not only as a passive recipient but also as an active participant in the formation of musical culture, generating their own interpretations and contextual frameworks for the reception of musical compositions.

Contemporary digital platforms are characterized by an unprecedented volume of accessible music, with thousands of new tracks uploaded daily to streaming

services. In these circumstances, the critical function of music online platforms lies not so much in providing access to content as in ensuring effective navigation within the information space. This function is realized through a complex system of filtering, categorization, and recommendations that generate individualized 'maps' of the musical landscape for each user [2].

Particular attention should be given to the functional dichotomy between the global and the local within music online platforms. On one hand, digital platforms enable the global dissemination of musical content, eliminating geographical and cultural boundaries. On the other hand, personalization algorithms frequently consider regional specificities and the user's cultural context, generating distinct 'information bubbles' that reflect local musical traditions and preferences. This dialectic between the global and the local establishes a distinctive dynamic in the circulation of musical content within the digital environment.

The functional specificity of musical internet resources is also evident in their ability to integrate diverse formats and modalities. Modern platforms merge audio content with visual components, textual information, and social interaction features, thereby creating an immersive multimedia experience. This convergence of various media formats transforms the fundamental nature of musical perception, making it more contextualized and interactive.

In analyzing the typological characteristics of musical internet resources, it is essential to emphasize their functional flexibility and adaptability. In contrast to traditional media with fixed formats and genres, digital platforms exist in a state of continuous evolution, responding to shifts in user preferences, technological innovations, and market dynamics. This flexibility in functional structure enables music digital platforms to effectively incorporate new forms of content and modes of audience interaction.

Music online publications constitute a dynamically evolving segment of the Russian media sphere, distinguished by a diversity of formats, content creation approaches, and methods of audience engagement. In the context of digitalization and evolving methods of information consumption, these specialized media adapt to new realities, thereby forming distinctive typological features. An analysis of contemporary Russian online music publications identifies key typological traits that define their functioning and role within the media landscape.

Within the scope of this article, Russian music media resources of various types were examined, including independent portals, social media representations, Telegram channels, and music sections of major publications. Among these are Zvuki.ru, The Flow, InterMedia, Muzobozrenie.ru, JazzPeople, InRock, Afisha Daily, Colta.ru, Musical Express, Soyuz Music Magazine, Music Business Russia, Novaya muzyka, and others.

The genre structure of contemporary musical online publications reflects general trends in the transformation of media texts in the digital environment, combining traditional journalistic formats with innovative approaches to the presentation of musical content. The analysis of Russian musical online media reveals key genre characteristics and patterns of their development.

The first significant trend is the transformation of traditional genres of music criticism. Reviews in the digital environment become more concise and dynamic, integrating multimedia elements and direct links to musical content. In the publications Afisha.Daily and The Flow, reviews are supplemented with audio excerpts and music videos. In the Telegram channels WARHOL and Broken Dances, they transform into concise annotated recommendations with personalized evaluations.

The analysis of specific materials corroborates this trend. Thus, in the review of Saluki's album *Wild Ea\$t* in Afisha.Daily, critic Anton Serenkov not only presented a textual analysis but also integrated the full version of the album via the services VK Music, Yandex Music, and Zvuk. He additionally included the music video for the song "Ogney." This format enables the reader to simultaneously familiarize themselves with the critic's viewpoint and listen to the musical material under discussion.

On the platform 'The Flow,' the text titled 'How Playboi Carti Became a Pop Idol: Language, Style, and Cult,' dated April 30, 2025, contains not only analytical excerpts but also embedded tracks from 'Yandex Music,' allowing the verification of the critic's observations directly within the reading process. Additionally, the material is enhanced with an interactive hyperlink to other texts on the platform, thereby establishing a fully integrated context for the perception of the contemporary music scene.

Within the Telegram channel 'PRNRP,' the review format acquires an even more condensed form. For example, the album review of 'Emoji Girl' dated April 21, 2025, is presented in the format of a brief digest emphasizing four key tracks, the author's assessment, and a direct link to streaming platforms. The length of such a review seldom exceeds 1000 characters, which corresponds to the requirements of the modern audience for rapid information consumption. 'Broken Dances' advances this approach further by proposing a 'one-paragraph review' format. In the publication titled '13 of My Favorite Russian Rap Beats' dated November 16, 2023, the channel's author managed to characterize the track's concept, sound, and instrumental arrangement within a single paragraph.

A significant example is the transformation of reviews at Afisha Daily, where in the column 'What happened to music,' critic Lesha Gorbash creates a hybrid format that combines elements of a review and a playlist with succinct commentary. The publication dated April 29, 2025, on new releases includes embedded players and minimalist descriptions [2].

A comparable evolution of formats is evident in the publications Intermedia and Zvuki.ru, where traditional reviews are enhanced by interactive features such as reader surveys, rating systems, and the capability to leave comments directly on individual sections of the text. This transforms the review genre from a monologic utterance into a dialogic format.

Another distinctive feature is the predominance of informational genres over analytical ones. News briefs, announcements, and press releases constitute the core content of most publications, often incorporating elements of evaluation and interpretation. This trend is particularly pronounced in the VKontakte communities 'MOTHERLAND,' 'Rodnoy Zvuk,' and 'TOASTER.' Within the 'MOTHERLAND' community, the informational report on the release of Shortparis's new album is accompanied by the author's commentary that 'the group continues to rethink industrial sound through the prism of Russian reality,' which serves as an interpretative element. In a similar manner, the publication about the Auktyon concert is complemented by a subjective opinion. On the Rodnoy Zvuk public platform, the note regarding the release of the track by the artist Antoha MC includes not only factual information but also a characterization of the sound as 'an unexpected turn towards an acoustic sound with elements of jazz.' Furthermore, TOASTER, in the announcement of the TOASTER x GAS:ON concert, provides an emotional appraisal of the lineup as 'not merely a gathering, but a place where a new scene is born,' thus transcending mere informativeness.

Another trend is the development of diverse interview formats. Alongside classical question-and-answer formats, video interviews, podcasts, and "live conversations" on social networks are gaining popularity. Publications such as The Flow, Rap.ru, and Afisha. Daily experiment with interview formats by integrating multimedia elements and creating interactive forms of audience engagement.

It is also necessary to highlight the emergence of specific promo-genres: authorial playlists, music charts, and thematic compilations. The Telegram channel "а можно потанцевальной?" regularly publishes curated playlists of electronic music integrated with Spotify and Apple Music, where the authors group new tracks by mood, era, or style. One of the recent playlists, "Favorite Indielis," has accumulated over a thousand saves among subscribers. The channel "VK Music" employs integration with the platform of the same name, offering personalized selections of Russian artists. Their weekly column 'Friday Release' showcases new releases with detailed commentary and direct listening links, thereby enhancing audience engagement with the platform's content. 'ENCORE' compiles thematic rankings, such as 'Friday Releases,' which are accompanied by professional reviews and streaming links.

In conclusion, attention should be drawn to the development of experimental multimedia genres that integrate text, audio, video, and interactive elements. Musical

longreads and multimedia projects emerge in publications with a developed technical base (Afisha.Daily, VSRAP), creating an immersive experience for the audience.

The genre structure of musical online media is determined by their typological characteristics. Commercial projects (Afisha.Daily, VK Music) exhibit the greatest genre diversity. Independent media (Fast Food Music, TFTO) often concentrate on a particular genre. Telegram channels, constrained by the platform's functionality, have developed specific genre forms that combine conciseness with personalized evaluation [2].

Platform membership also influences genre specificity. Websites exhibit greater genre variability due to their technical capabilities. VK communities leverage platform functionalities to create interactive formats. Telegram channels cultivate a specific style in which informational messages are combined with personal recommendations.

The thematic orientation of publications correlates with genre priorities. Media outlets specializing in hip-hop («The Flow») cultivate the interview genre. Publications devoted to electronic music («а можно потанцевальной?») place emphasis on promotional genres. Generalist media seek to encompass a wide spectrum of genres, adapting them to the specifics of the respective domains covered.

A significant trend is the convergence of genres, wherein traditional forms combine to produce hybrid formats. A review may incorporate elements of an interview, a news item is supplemented with analytical commentary, all of which is integrated with multimedia components.

The digital ecosystem within which musical online publications exist determines numerous aspects of their operation. One of the key characteristics of the contemporary phase is information overload: dozens of albums and singles are released each week, and the stream of music news is continuous. In these circumstances, music media fulfill the role of navigators for the audience, selecting the most significant events and releases. For example, the section 'What Happened to Music' in Afisha Daily provides a regular overview of the key weekly releases, accompanied by concise descriptions and embedded audio players. These overviews enable readers to orient themselves within the abundance of new material, while the editorial team effectively assumes a curatorial function.

Conclusion

In an era when algorithmic recommendations of streaming services automatically generate playlists, music media endeavor to supplement them with human expertise and critical insight. Publications offer curated content selection and thereby preserve their significance in the digital environment. The practice of creating compilations and rankings (such as curated playlists from the Telegram channel «а можно потанцевальной?») or charts from VK Music) demonstrates that media can promote artists as effectively as algorithmic mechanisms. Accordingly, music

online media act as expert curators, supplementing the algorithms of streaming platforms with substantive assessments of new material.

Digitization has transformed traditional channels of information dissemination within editorial departments. Currently, much news originates not from press releases, but directly from the artists themselves via social media. Artists announce new releases, tours, or significant events on platforms such as «VK» or «YouTube», bypassing intermediaries. Significantly, the iconic duo Daft Punk announced their disbandment in 2021 directly to the public through their own «YouTube» video titled 'Epilogue,' after which specialized media outlets subsequently disseminated this news. Journalists must respond promptly to such announcements, effectively transforming from exclusive sources of information into retransmitters of messages from the artist.

At the same time, the importance of the editorial analytical function intensifies. The audience often learns the news simultaneously with journalists; thus, the publication aims to augment the bare fact by providing context, insights from industry experts, historical perspective, or a critical assessment of the event. The role of the music journalist is increasingly shifting from informer to interpreter and verifier: it is important not only to promptly report the news but also to verify its authenticity and explain its significance for both the industry and the audience. Thus, music media retain their role as carriers of professional opinion, providing readers with a deeper understanding of ongoing developments in music.

Many editorial teams are developing cross-platform projects. For instance, the team at «The Flow» supplements written reviews on their website with 15-minute video analyses on YouTube, while materials from «Afisha Daily» are adapted for various platforms—from audio podcast versions to short video clips for social networks—thus enabling engagement with the broadest possible audience.

Concurrently, the importance of content visualization and interactivity is increasing. Vivid illustrations, original design, and multimedia elements have become essential components of publications in music media today. Concert photographs, performance videos, and infographics enhance the attractiveness of materials and their shareability on social networks. Furthermore, modern platforms facilitate active audience engagement in discussions. Several publications incorporate interactive features: polls, rating systems, and commenting capabilities embedded directly within the text. Such an approach converts the journalist's monologue into a dialogue with the reader. For instance, on the websites Intermedia and Zvuki.ru, reviews are complemented by voting and comments, thereby transforming the traditional genre into a more personalized and dialogic format of interaction [6].

The specifics of the functioning of musical online media in the digital age are manifested in the ongoing transformation of forms and approaches: from curated content selection and immediate news responsiveness to multiplatform presence

and interactive engagement with the audience. A successful publication combines technical innovation with the maintenance of a critical perspective and analytical depth, enabling it to remain relevant and influential within the rapidly evolving digital media landscape.

Conclusions

Therefore, the genre structure of contemporary online music media reflects both the evolution of traditional formats and the emergence of new ones. The key trends are as follows: the transformation of classical critical genres, the predominance of informational content, the development of various interview formats, the formation of promotional genres, the emergence of experimental multimedia formats, and the convergence of genres. Genre characteristics are determined by a set of factors, including the typological features of publications, their platform, thematic orientation, and technical capabilities, which underpin the diversity of approaches to content organization in contemporary online music journalism.

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不同的沉默他人：跨文化交流对学术话语的挑战

**DISSIMILAR SILENT OTHERS: CROSS-CULTURAL
COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES FOR ACADEMIC DISCOURSE**

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摘要：本文探讨了“沉默”这一沟通现象在跨文化互动中作为身份建构要素的作用。文章以全球本土化教育环境（例如，一所面向全球推广教育项目的国际大学，以俄罗斯大学为例）中的多元文化课堂为背景，对“沉默”这一概念进行了跨文化研究。研究对象为来自南亚、东亚、西非和俄罗斯语言文化背景的学生。不同文化背景的学生和教师对“沉默”这一概念的理解、实践和运用各不相同。与被视为“沉默的异己者”的文化差异群体进行密切直接的接触，会给学术话语中的有效沟通带来挑战。如果缺乏与文化差异群体互动的经验，来自其他文化的教师和学生可能会对沟通中的“沉默”做出不同的解读、理解不足或误解。

本研究采用的研究方法包括参与式和非参与式观察、案例研究（包括“案例中的案例”方法）、自由联想实验、以民族志访谈为调查工具，以及从俄罗斯和巴基斯坦文化视角对研究结果进行双民族志解读。一系列跨文化案例揭示了一些误解、沟通失败以及文化冲击的实例，其高潮表现为在学术话语中遵循沉默惯例和突然打破基于沉默的习惯性行为。在教育机构多元文化课堂中进行的自由联想实验表明，不同文化背景的人在交流中对沉默的感知和实践存在一些差异。

关键词：沉默，文化差异显著的沉默者，跨文化交流，学术话语

Abstract. *The paper examines a communicative phenomenon of SILENCE as an element of enacted identity construction in cross-cultural interaction. SILENCE is explored cross-culturally in multicultural class settings within a glocal eduscape environment, i.e. in the conditions of an international university promoting educational programs worldwide (in a Russian university, as an example). The students*

involved are from South Asian, East Asian, West African, and Russian linguacultures. The concept of SILENCE is interpreted, translated into life, and practiced differently by students and faculty members from different cultures. Close and direct contacts with culturally dissimilar Others who are viewed as Dissimilar Silent Others pose challenges for appropriate and efficient communication in academic discourse. SILENCE in communication can be interpreted differently, under-interpreted, or misinterpreted by faculty members as well as students from other cultures if they lack previous experience of interaction with culturally dissimilar Others.

The research methods used for the study are participant and non-participant observation, case studies (including a “case-within-a-case” approach), free association experiment, ethnographic interviews as a tool of survey, and duoethnographic interpretation of the findings from the perspectives of Russian and Pakistani cultures. A number of cross-cultural cases provide some instances of misunderstanding, communicative failure, and culture shock at its climax expressed through adherence to the practice of SILENCE and a sharp departure from a silence-based habitual behavior in academic discourse. Free association experiment conducted in the multicultural class of an eduscape showed some differences in perception and practicing of SILENCE in communication.

Keywords: *SILENCE, dissimilar silent Others, culturally dissimilar Other, cross-cultural communication, academic discourse*

As a result of some new trends taking place in cultural globalization, in the eduscapes as educational spaces of international universities a changed demographics of participants is being discovered. It has a significant impact on academic culture and academic discourse. First, American and European universities, and now Russian ones too, have faced the challenges of such demographic globalization, or rather glocalization, where global trends are refracted locally and implemented in glocal products. It means that educational programs integrate global trends, national educational standards, and educational expectations of international students with various national and ethnic backgrounds.

International students bring to the educational environment their own educational goals and objectives, intentions and expectations regarding learning, academic priorities and preferences, desired forms and methods of teaching, based on their previous experience. They introduce behavioral practices and communication styles that are alien to the host academic environment. These practices and styles affect the academic discourse and put faculty members in a difficult position of choosing alternative technologies and forms of teaching, as well as communication strategies in the classroom. Some of such dramatically different practices are silence and silent communication as a behavioral orientation and meaningful construct of interaction experienced by Russian faculty members in contact with Asian students.

Differences in communication extend beyond purely academic forms and models of communication. They extend to all types of interactions: they begin with forms of address and greetings, and end... nowhere!

Silent Others in a multicultural class have become a challenge for faculty members. Classroom activity of students may not only be an element of control affecting the interim assessment and/or the final grade for the course but it is a regular basis for many forms of teaching/learning activities, e.g. project presentation and discussion, teamwork, debates, various competitive activities in which verbally expressed proactivity from the part of the students is of crucial importance.

Basically, at the core of misconception and misinterpretation of silence as a meaningful construct of communication in intercultural or cross-cultural settings lies the challenging and complex issue of the mindset of the Other (the 'mental program' of culturally dissimilar Other).

Silence as communication has become a factor of success and failure of the teacher in class.

While colleagues in a Russian monocultural class share the experience of "*la paresse pédagogique*" ("*pedagogic laziness*") – a metaphor standing for the teachers' joy and satisfaction when their students sustain teamwork activities, complete analytical tasks, debate, and move towards a successful outcome without their teachers' active involvement, assistance, or advice, teachers in multicultural classes with the majority of East Asian students feel challenged. They have to be active and proactive in "activating" their students, developing new training resources, and preparing alternative options of their seminars in case debating or other discussion-based activities fail. East Asian (e.g., Chinese) students choose to stick to silence both in class, and in out-of-class activities. They do not ask for clarifications of home assignments, do not ask for feedback, do not argue if they disagree with their classmates and teachers, they do not advise the teacher on anything.

Compared to them, South Asian students being patient and respectful in class may come to the professor during the break or after the seminar and initiate advice ("*Could you limit the time of speaking per participant?*", or "*Do not allow talking on off-topics*", etc.). Chinese students look passive, indifferent, and uninterested; they are silent, calm, looking down at their notebooks or pads, as if avoiding eye contact with the teacher. When they get criticism, they never attempt to argue and defend their position. They never correct the teacher.

By way of comparison, West African students (from Nigeria, Ghana, or Gambia) may initiate criticism in class and ask the teacher not to discuss certain issues if they feel them uncomfortable or diverting from the main topic of the seminar.

Discussing sociolinguistic norms applicable to classroom situation Ikuko Nakané points out that in Asian cultures, students are not to challenge their teachers, but are expected to attend and receive knowledge. Referring to other researchers,

Nakane goes on to discuss that students from East Asian cultures are expected to behave as respectful and silent recipients of the teacher's knowledge. They apply the same behaviour to the new educational environment of Western universities, display marked passivity and silence (Nakane, 2007, p. 20).

As Gao and Ting-Toomey explain, communication as a gift of talking is not a universal practice. It pertains only to a "privileged" few, and this cultural orientation explains why communication has not been given attention in the Chinese academic domain. They also point out that in the Chinese linguaculture there is no a single term that corresponds to "communication". There are only a few translated equivalents of the concept that stand for "to exchange", "to disseminate", and "to connect" (Gao & Ting-Toomey, 1997, p. 5). Further on, they argue that the primary functions of communication in Chinese culture are to maintain relations, to reinforce role and status differences, and to preserve harmony within a group. Chinese communication serves affective and relational purposes. Gao and Ting-Toomey also argue referring to other researchers that hierarchy plays an important part and it is the role of communicator but not the self, that determines the behavior (Gao & Ting-Toomey, 1997, p. 6). This consideration explains the silent behavior of Chinese students in a Russian eduscape: they act from the position of guest students in respect to host faculty members, apart from other value orientations that make them behave in a humble and modest way sticking to the mode of silence. Besides, "a spoken 'voice' is equated with seniority, authority, age, experience, knowledge, and expertise. As a result, listening becomes a predominant mode of communication" (Gao & Ting-Toomey, 1997, p. 42).

One of the methods we applied for the research is case study. Our cases are real-time real-place situations observed by us in the eduscape settings of a Russian university. Our cross-cultural case is a real situation of interaction based on a communicative act with participants from different cultures, and in which a conflict of values and/or beliefs is manifested. Below are some examples of cases illustrating the phenomenon of SILENCE:

(1) A Japanese female student selected a course, attended several classes, always chose a seat away from other students and always kept silent. After some seminars she stopped attending. After some time (another form of silence!) she forwarded a long letter to her professor, in which she wrote disparagingly about herself, saying that she had not completed the assignments on time as elements of control, and this fact did not allow her to continue attending classes. *"You spent a lot of your precious time on me, explaining how to complete the assignments, but I demonstrated disrespect, irresponsibility, incompetence, laziness, unreliability!"*.

(2) A Taiwanese female student, even after repeated explanations from the teacher about activity in class as an element of control, preferred to get a zero as her score rather than force herself to get involved in discussions in the classroom.

“When I hear my voice in a classroom with many other students listening to me, I feel like I can faint!”. *“If I realize that I am wrong and answer in public not what is expected of me, I am ready to die or disappear!”*. The student offered to the teacher her own alternative solution to the issue of activity in class: *“Will you allow me to answer after class? Or may I answer in writing?”*. She also shared another fear of hers: *“If I do not complete my homework on time, I would rather not come to class than lose face in public, explaining why I did not complete it!”*.

Discussing this case the following year, students from West Africa (Nigeria) did not support the idea of individualization of training for dissimilar Silent Others (by email, or in writing, or after class individually) because *“it was their choice to get enrolled in an international university in a Master’s program, so it is their responsibility; rules and regulations are set for everyone; besides, public speaking competence is a soft skill expected to be developed in Masters. There should not be any exceptions!”*

(3) A Taiwanese male student has always kept silence in class. He attended all the seminars, completed all home assignments in due time, but preferred to keep silent in class. Whenever the teacher asked him to comment on some issue, he would always blush and speak in a shaky voice. It was obvious that speaking wasn’t his strong suit or his favorite activity. However, after a month and a half of internship at a Russian organization, during his final project presentation, he acted very confidently and seemed to be quite critical of his Russian experience. He openly criticized his communication with Russians at his workplace. After the seminar professor told him that she could hardly expect such explicit and direct criticism from him and asked what made him change his communicative behavior so dramatically. He said: *I am just tired of Russia and Russians! Though I was offered a job, I don’t want to stay. I want to go home! I don’t want it anymore!* It looked like it was a delayed and progressing culture shock (cultural fatigue) at its climax. His usual patience and endurance were exhausted! Silence as a social and cultural norm had lost its value. This case is primarily about silence, but also about an identity crisis! Psychologically, the longer you remain silent, the harder it is to initiate communication, the harder it is to break your personal silence! But he did it, and his change surprised everyone.

(4) A Chinese female student kept silent refusing to participate in a seminar discussion when the professor suggested that the students should critically consider the proposed issue. After the class, the student explained her position: *“I cannot argue with the professor! The professor is a Teacher! You do not argue with a Teacher!”*

(5) During a lively discussion about cultural stereotypes, in which students from a multicultural class actively and enthusiastically participated, a student from Afghanistan turned to two of his Chinese classmates, who were listening but

not participating in the discussion: “*Why are you keeping silent? Why don’t you express your opinions?*” The Chinese students looked at each other, smiled, but remained silent. The teacher attempted to interfere: “*All individual comments are absolutely voluntary! Apparently, silence is your conscious choice!?*” However, the Chinese students continued to remain silent.

(6) During the defense of their projects at the exam, students presented reports on the results of their research. All speakers, while defending their projects, tried to speak freely or with minimal reliance on the text on the screen, confidently navigating the structure and content, and maintaining eye contact with the audience. The presentation of the Chinese students stood out from the general style and atmosphere oriented towards discussion, and evidently reduced the interest of the audience in their research. They were reading their texts from their phones, without taking eyes off the screens and without addressing the audience. Even after the teacher asked them not to read, but to discuss, explain, and comment, they continued reading and avoiding eye contact with the audience. Equally, they never asked questions after other students delivered their reports. They always preferred to keep silent.

(7) The professor discovered that she had been mispronouncing a Taiwanese student’s name throughout the whole course of studies. “*Why did she keep silent for so long? Why didn’t she ever correct me?*” the professor asked another Taiwanese student. “*Because you’re a teacher!*” he replied.

(8) The professor confused two Chinese students who looked exactly alike (from her Russian perspective) and approached one to discuss her research project, believing she was addressing the other. The student listened silently, only occasionally repeating “*Maybe*”. She never pointed out the professor’s obvious mistake.

Further on, some of the SILENCE cases were offered for discussion in the following year for another multicultural group of students. We share the idea of the pragmatic value of case studies expressed by Jan Chrastina who argued that the key advantages of a case study in educational and social science research are its flexibility, memorability and reproducibility, a high degree of conceptual validity, [...], lower theoretical demands (compared to other qualitative research designs). A case study allows the researcher to model more complex causal relationships, recognize and understand human behavior and thereby analyze the “unique phenomena of unique cases” (Chrastina, 2022, p. 172). We also analyzed the concept of SILENCE with students in the context of real-class communication situations. That was a “case-within-a-case” approach. As Anna Wierzbicka argues, “to show that a particular word is of special importance in a given culture, one has to make a case for it. Evidence is necessary for each such claim...” (Wierzbicka, 1997, p. 16).

Collecting, observing, analyzing, and interpreting cases of silence in a multi-cultural class provoked comparison and brought us to some conclusions that further on were supported by the students' comments. For East Asians SILENCE is the concept of universal communication with the outside world (with the Universe), it is striving for harmony, balance, and universal peace. They do not visibly differentiate between public and private communicative behaviors. For South Asians SILENCE is a selective strategy of communication for public face-saving that can differ from a private talk on the same topic. They may be silent in class producing the air of respect, modesty, and concern for the opinions of others but in private communication with a teacher they may criticize other fellow-students, complain and even advise teachers on their activities.

(9) As one of the cases, a student from Pakistan always being very active (and proactive) in class and supportive of the professor, silent when not asked, came up during the break in the seminars and advised the professor to regulate the students' comments on the discussed topics by limiting the time for their voiced arguments.

Misunderstanding sometimes occurs from the part of faculty members due to some limited exposure not only to national or ethnic cultures, but to modern trends in those cultures, including popular culture.

(10) As a case, a male Chinese student never speaking in class but coming to communicate with his teacher after the seminar to ask questions or to check the correct understanding of the phenomena under discussion, came to class one day with his hair dyed blond, and after a while, with his hair colored pink. The teacher's confused feelings prompted some communicative contradiction: the student was not speaking in class out of shyness and modesty with the desire not to attract the attention of the audience but by dyeing his hair he achieved the opposite – attracted everyone's attention by his changed appearance. In the follow-up discussions of the case students in another class came to the agreement that silence in class is about the Chinese student's national identity while dyeing hair blond and pink is about some youth culture or pop culture (fandom) identity not associated with the culture-induced silence.

Some East Asian students in discussion of previously collected cases presented to them in class, insisted that in some of their national universities active speaking practices in class are introduced that allow them to get used to "Western" academic discourse and develop speaking competences (staying away from traditional 'silent mode') which are very important for educational mobility.

SILENCE is interpreted by us as one of cultural and social values, and for testing the status of values in the mental program of young generations, a free association experiment is viewed as appropriate. It is a way to better understand communicators in real-life situations in which they act out their identities and mentalities.

To comprehend the difference in interpretation of SILENCE by culturally different Others in a multicultural class we conducted a free association experiment. A concept of SILENCE was announced to the class, and the students were instructed to write down from 3 to 5 associations (words or word combinations) referred to the SILENCE concept. According to the frequency of the respondents' references their nominations were grouped into the core and the periphery. The respondents were encouraged to put down any association that comes to their minds during a short session without any censorship or pressure. Free association experiment helps to find out what the respondents really think, feel, and believe, and it is instrumental in exploring identity, mentality, and worldview of the research participants.

The free association experiment conducted in multicultural classes and supported by follow-up discussions showed some basic distinction. East Asians and South Asians refer to SILENCE as a positive communicative practice, while West Africans (Nigerians, Ghanaians, Gambians) and Russians consider SILENCE a negative phenomenon indicating bad causes and bad effects.

As for some specific associations, East Asian students (Chinese and Taiwanese) prioritized *politeness, patience, face-saving, kindness, modesty, humbleness, harmony, peace*. South Asian students (Pakistanis, Indians, Afghans) highlighted *honor, dignity, respect, wisdom, discipline, reticence, safety, hiding the truth*. West African students (Nigerians, Ghanaians, Gambians) stressed *sorrow, sadness, tranquility, shame, disagreement, danger, uncertainty avoidance, lack of self-confidence, cowardice*. Russian students pointed out *alienation, rejection, asymmetry, fear, loneliness, isolation, darkness, discomfort, lack of interest*.

Although all cultures studied are classified as collectivistic, high-context, and shame-based (versus individualistic, low-context, and guilt-based), the scores of these cultural dimensions vary across these cultures. Meanwhile, the differences in priorities in free associations regarding SILENCE are more or less obvious: East Asian politeness and patience vs South Asian dignity and honor vs West African sorrow and sadness vs Russian alienation and rejection.

Alienation in communication is, first of all, the rejection of the Other or hostility towards the Other (Gonotskaya, 2019, p. 61). Russian students who had no previous experience of direct (face-to-face) communication with their Chinese colleagues confessed that the silence of their Chinese fellow-students felt like alienation and rejection of Russians and Russianness. For them silence meant absence of communication while for the Chinese it was communication of politeness of guests towards hosts. Problems of alienation and rejection of the dissimilar Other are particularly related to situations of closeness to culture and distance from culture, known as the emic approach or view from within the cultural code and the etic approach or view from outside the culture when interpreting communicative acts and events, as well

as the beliefs and values that underlie them (Geertz, 2017). As for asymmetry, it signifies inequality, lack of mirror-like interaction, power relations, dependence, and superiority. Russians felt that in their interactions with the Chinese, they were forced to assume a position of power, whereas they expected equality.

The limitations of our free association experiment stem from the limited number of respondents (68 participants from all the cultures mentioned above) and the large number of unique associations produced by them. The associations mentioned above are repetitive and occur three or more times in the participants' responses.

We believe that the practical significance of this study lies in the fact that it contributes to the reconstruction (or rather deconstruction) of the identity of culturally dissimilar Others (specifically, Silent Others) in the global eduscapes of international universities, where dissimilar cultures come into close contact and have a strong influence on academic discourse.

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创意产业作为发展家庭休闲文化的平台
**CREATIVE INDUSTRIES AS A PLATFORM
FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY LEISURE CULTURE**

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摘要：本文分析了创意产业作为现代家庭休闲文化发展的重要平台。研究创意产业作为休闲发展平台的重要性，源于家庭休闲及其组织方式的关键性。这一过程通过将家庭融入创意休闲环境，有助于构建未来图景，并促进社交和人际互动。

如今，娱乐和创意领域如同纽带，将企业的文化和商业诉求与公民（尤其是家庭）的自我发展和精神成长需求联系起来，为充分发挥个人创造潜能创造了条件。

在创意产业的帮助下，家庭休闲文化的组织和发展形式正在发生转变，并融入现代休闲娱乐文化环境，逐步迈向数字化空间，其特征体现在以下几个方面：强度高、互动性强、沉浸感强、形象化和直觉性强。

关键词：创意产业，休闲文化，家庭，休闲服务，游戏产业，模型化商业。

Abstract *The article provides an analysis of the creative industries as a modern and important platform for the development of the family's leisure culture. The relevance of the study of creative industries as a platform for the development of leisure is dictated by the key importance of family recreation and approaches to its organization. This process contributes to the image of the future through the inclusion of the family in the environment of creative leisure, as well as stimulates socialization and interpersonal interaction.*

Today, the spheres of entertainment and creativity act as a link that combines the culture and commercial aspirations of business with the interests of citizens, in particular the family to self-development and spiritual growth, creating conditions for the full realization of the creative potential of the individual.

The forms of organization and development of the leisure culture of the family with the help of creative industries are transformed and integrated into the modern environment of recreation and entertainment culture, progressively moving into digital space, manifested through the following characteristics: intensity, interactivity, immersion, imagery and intuition.

Keywords: *creative industries, leisure culture, family, leisure services, gaming industry, modeling business.*

In the context of the modern stage of the formation of Russian society, the innovative transformation of the sociocultural space, in which the system of upbringing, socialization and personal growth is being built, is gaining priority importance.

Current trends dictate new roles and functions to culture, which is increasingly manifested as a significant factor in economic, cultural, creative, family, spiritual and educational progress and a platform for the creative potential of the modern Russian family.

According to the provisions of the federal law "On the Basics of Legislation of the Russian Federation on Culture" and "Concepts for the Development of Creative (Creative Industries) and Methods for Ensuring Their State Support in Large Urban Centers and Megacities until 2030," it is necessary to explore the prospects for updating social and cultural spheres and stimulate the development of creative industries through the introduction of new projects. This initiative comes from the Ministry of Culture of Russia [6].

Creative industries are usually seen as the ability to find original and innovative approaches to achieving their goals. The increased interest of researchers and professionals in supporting the development of creative spaces reflects a shift in theoretical ideas about creativity - today it and creativity are perceived as a set of areas of work that have a significant impact on the social, cultural and educational development of society. Due to their great resource potential, creative industries are increasingly influencing various aspects of people's lives, including the institution of the family.

Modern scientific works reveal the theoretical aspect of the concept of creative industries related to activities in the social and cultural spheres. So, for example, according to the point of view of G.A. Avanesyan, the main elements of creative industries are: leisure centers for family and youth, recreation centers and clubs, the entertainment industry, the music industry, theatrical performances, concerts and circus performances, the production of audiovisual content, amusement parks, etc. [1].

Creative industries are an important engine for the successful development of the entire socio-cultural sphere. The integration of creative industries into the practice of cultural and leisure activities contributes to the use of creative solutions to promote the leisure culture of the family. At the same time, it should

be noted that such a transformation opens up new platforms for personal growth and self-realization of the family, especially the young one with the prospect of strengthening the heritage, traditions and values of the culture of leisure [7].

The development of the leisure culture of the family in Russia is closely connected with the desire of the state to increase the role of family values in socio-cultural progress. This growth is impossible without mastering the generation of a young family with common cultural ideals and moral principles.

An important role in the formation and improvement of the culture of a modern young family is played by leisure activities, the essence of which, according to A.D. Zharkov, is always determined by the need for society in the openness and creativity of social relations.

Leisure culture contributes to the development of family potential in various forms of socially useful activity and helps to effectively organize free time. Uniting families in the sphere of cultural leisure of the institution, they try to reveal their talents and give the opportunity to freely express themselves in creativity, which, according to A.D. Zharkova. It is a prerequisite for productive work in modern creative industries [5].

Russian scientists made a significant contribution to the study of the phenomenon of leisure, among them B.S. Erasov, I.N. Eroshenko, A.D. Zharkov, T.G. Kiseleva, Yu. D. Krasilnikov. B.S. Erasov noted the transformation of the social and cultural platform, where the socio-cultural formation of the individual has always occurred and is taking place. He points to factors affecting the cultures of family relations, such as readiness for new experiences of communication and interaction, acquiring creative skills and changing the role of the family, active participation in social and socio-cultural life, overcoming passivity and striving to create a leisure culture of the family in the context of creative industries [4].

Plato believed that creative art should play an important role in leisure. Young people, properly raised by their parents and teachers of gymnasium schools, devoted most of their free time to philosophical discussions and the study of sciences. Developing reason and wisdom in themselves, they found happiness in leisure, which contributed to the strengthening of the state, maintained order and ensured creative and harmonious relations between family and society [9].

Aristotle shared Plato's view regarding the importance of the leisure culture of man and his family. Leisure activities are primarily activity. He wrote that life is inseparable from action, because the action itself is a manifestation of life. Based on Aristotle's reasoning that human existence is impossible without activity and the achievement of happiness as the main goal, it becomes obvious what character a free human activity should have. The philosopher considered creative and aesthetic rest the pinnacle of virtue or one of the ways to gain it [2].

The family's leisure culture was perceived as a sacred phenomenon and served as an indicator of the creative and spiritual qualities of children and parents. During the leisure period, knowledge and intellectual growth took place. Leisure is related to the game, it contains key elements of creativity and creativity embodied in the independence of thinking, creative imagination and self-improvement, thereby bringing a person closer to the ideal. Thanks to leisure activities, the family acquires new sources of skills and knowledge, and gaming tools become a platform for creating creative industries.

Leisure researcher G. G. Voloshchenko, within the framework of the cultural and historical approach, determines the aspects of leisure activities, she says that today one can observe a difficult combination of various ways of spending free time, which have a significant impact on daily and good time for the family. At the same time, in the life of people there is a place for noble, festive entertainment, and the heights of rest. The abundance of cultural trends and a wide range of activities have become an important sign and reflection of the level of creativity and creativity of modern families [3].

Cultural activity is characterized by a number of functions that manifest themselves in providing a variety of forms of leisure for the family. According to the Russian researcher, Professor Yu.A. Streltsov, the key sociocultural roles of leisure form an interconnected triad, including stages of recovery, entertainment and development.

Recovery is aimed at returning energy and relaxation, reducing fatigue. Entertainment is designed to fill your free time with positive emotions and bright events that stimulate activity. Development, on the other hand, provides a chance for personal enrichment and cultural progress through a family leisure culture outside of work and study.

The roles of the creative industry of leisure culture are definitions of its main characteristics, revealing the social and individual meaning, which is to create conditions for the implementation of the needs of the family and society during structured recreation.

The key role in the creative industry as a platform for the development of leisure culture should be attributed to pleasure (hedonism) - this function inherent in any activity of organizations and institutions, which is emphasized in the theory of socio-cultural activity as a "function of joy"

A hedonistic function, which is considered a "joy function," it determines a person's motivation to participate in leisure activities. Support for this aspect is facilitated by the creation of a gaming environment provided by organizations of creative industries of the culture of leisure activities. This involves the direct involvement of visitors, family in the unique atmosphere created in cultural centers, parks and other creative and entertainment areas.

The game is the main way of interaction between the consumer and the creative industry of leisure culture, allowing you to experience emotions, expand your horizons, restore your physical and spiritual energy and improve.

As a result, a complex system of functions of the creative leisure industry is being formed, which determines not only the classification of organizations, institutions, cultural and leisure centers, but also the choice of priority areas of their activities.

The basic, hedonic aspect covers key and special functions:

1. personality development (implying an increase in the level of requests and disclosure of potential).
2. training (including the application of new knowledge about the world and the development of useful skills).
3. recovery (providing relaxation, stress reduction and energy return).
4. Rest and entertainment (involving a change in activity).
5. Communication (contributing to the strengthening of social contacts and the elimination of obstacles in communication) [12].

The variety of functional tasks of the creative leisure industry determines its important position in the culture of recreation and entertainment of the family. As one of the cultural and creative industries, it is simultaneously cultural and mass, family and has the potential to personalize the choice of leisure, which contributes to an increase in value - time, which is devoted to active participation in the life of society and creative development [11, 13].

Modern researchers seek to systematize the creative industries of leisure culture using various parameters: the nature of content and types of activity, the time frame and types of leisure activities. As noted by L.V. Secretova, the sphere of cultural leisure on the platform of creative industries is based on the content of events, events, tasks and areas of their application [8].

The defining features in the classification of creative leisure industries are the offered services and products of a cultural and leisure nature:

1. media sphere;
2. cinema, video content creation and television;
3. the music sector;
4. publishing activities;
5. art business (including galleries and exhibition spaces);
6. holding concert events and entertainment programs of various formats;
7. gaming industry;
8. Theaters, concert halls and circuses;
9. event industry - development and conduct of events and advertising campaigns
10. organization of quests of various types: specialized clubs and agencies;
11. Leisure locations, including centers, clubs, entertainment complexes, discos and cacaorke - bars that provide opportunities for communication and self-realization;

12. modeling business, beauty contests and similar initiatives;

13. New trends in the theater: audio performances, full immersion performances (immersive theater), experimental venues, street theater performances, individual performances;

14. Traditional crafts are one of the aspects of the creative leisure industry, reflecting folk art, in which national traditions and customs are clearly manifested. They emphasize the uniqueness of the artistic heritage and the individual approach of the authors.

The trend of cultural and leisure time is transforming and integrating into an online environment defined by five key characteristics: intensity, interactivity, immersion, imagery and intuitiveness.

Internet leisure services are available in the form of gaming platforms, film and video content, artistic projects, virtual tours and the like. However, according to experts, this promising and involved area has not yet been established as an independent and educational area within the framework of creative leisure industries, it requires study, determination of principles, terminology and other research aspects.

15. Active recreation is increasingly perceived as an indicator of the high status of creative industries of leisure culture. New forms and destinations of outdoor activities are offered by travel companies that include elements of extreme sports: flyboarding, volcano riding, parkour using trampolines and kitewing;

16. Drag Racing - high-speed competitions at a direct distance and street racing (Street Racing/Street Challenge) - city races, including movement between control points with the performance of certain tasks and recording results through photography;

17. Amusement parks are an important component of the creative leisure industries, including various sections: amusement parks, natural parks of Russia, outdoor parks, theme parks, ethnocultural parks and eco-parks.

Each park is a creative space where objects are created, united by a common idea. Attractions and play areas are harmoniously integrated into the environment and design, creating the right atmosphere and emphasizing the main theme;

18. anime culture offers a unique form of entertainment - cosplay, which consists in reproducing images of anime characters;

19. Animation as a form of leisure is aimed at restoring energy and obtaining positive emotions, offering tourist routes with animation elements, animation services within hotels and an animation program in hotels;

20. Cultural tourism is one of the directions in the field of creative leisure industries that meets the needs of tourist and excursion activities, for example, audio promenades, excursions-shows, excursions-performances, excursions-theatricalization, excursions-quests [10].

In the tourism industry, which is part of the creative industry, projects are being successfully implemented that reorient interest from a simple acquaintance to an entertaining and emotional experience when visiting historical sites or attractions.

The importance of studying the issue of creative industries as a platform for the development of leisure culture is due to the important role of the development of the leisure culture of the family and the methods of its organization and implementation - in the process of shaping the image of the future by integrating the modern family into the culture of creative recreation and entertainment, socialization and interaction.

Today's appearance of this area is being formed under the influence of the entertainment industry, the emergence and growth of which were the result of global trends, processes of commercialization of recreation and rationalization of culture, coupled with rapid progress in technology and the creative sector of the economy.

Modern leisure-oriented creative industries are designed to become a platform where the business interests of entrepreneurs and the needs of people for intellectual and spiritual enrichment, especially families, are combined, and where the potential of human creativity is unleashed.

This direction focuses on concepts that combine the efforts of cultural activities and creative industries. Today, an important task is being solved for cultural and educational institutions in the framework of creating a nationwide system for the formation of creative personnel, based on rich Russian traditions, and improving the level of qualifications of specialists in all areas of culture.

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技术创新在文化遗产保护与诠释中的应用：乌兹别克斯坦国家应用艺术与
手工艺史博物馆的经验

**TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS FOR THE PRESERVATION
AND INTERPRETATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE:
THE EXPERIENCE OF THE STATE MUSEUM OF APPLIED ARTS
AND HISTORY OF HANDICRAFTS OF UZBEKISTAN**

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摘要：数字技术的飞速发展正在改变当代文化遗产的保护、记录、诠释和传播方式。博物馆越来越多地采用创新技术解决方案，以提高藏品的可及性，增强参观者的参与度，并确保历史文物和建筑古迹的长期保存。本研究以位于塔什干历史悠久的波洛夫采夫故居内的乌兹别克斯坦国家应用艺术与手工艺史博物馆为例，探讨了博物馆实践中的技术创新。

研究分析了数字保存技术的应用，包括三维文档、数字孪生、虚拟导览和在线藏品，以及新兴的博物馆交流工具，例如智能眼镜、增强现实系统和基于人工智能的翻译耳机。研究重点关注这些技术在提高国际参观者的可及性、支持博物馆多语种交流以及拓展文化遗产诠释机会方面的作用。

该研究表明，数字技术的融合不仅有助于博物馆藏品和建筑遗产的保护，还能促进博物馆与观众之间新型互动模式的发展。研究结果强调了将传统博物馆实践与创新技术相结合的重要性，以增强博物馆在数字时代发挥的教育、文化和传播功能。

关键词：文化遗产，博物馆学，数字保存，数字孪生，虚拟博物馆，智能眼镜，人工智能，博物馆无障碍，乌兹别克斯坦国家应用艺术与手工艺史博物馆。

Abstract. *The rapid development of digital technologies is transforming contemporary approaches to the preservation, documentation, interpretation, and dissemination of cultural heritage. Museums are increasingly adopting innovative technological solutions to improve the accessibility of collections, enhance visitor engagement, and ensure the long-term preservation of historical objects and architectural monuments. This study examines the experience of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History*

of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan, located in the historic Polovtsev House in Tashkent, as a case study of technological innovation in museum practice.

The research analyses the application of digital preservation technologies, including three-dimensional documentation, digital twins, virtual tours, and online collections, as well as emerging tools for museum communication such as smart glasses, augmented reality systems, and artificial intelligence-based translation headphones. Particular attention is paid to the role of these technologies in increasing accessibility for international visitors, supporting multilingual museum communication, and expanding opportunities for the interpretation of cultural heritage.

The study demonstrates that the integration of digital technologies contributes not only to the preservation of museum collections and architectural heritage but also to the development of new forms of interaction between museums and audiences. The findings highlight the importance of combining traditional museum practices with innovative technological approaches in order to strengthen the educational, cultural, and communicative functions of museums in the digital age.

Keywords: *cultural heritage, museum studies, digital preservation, digital twins, virtual museums, smart glasses, artificial intelligence, museum accessibility, State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan.*

Introduction

The preservation of cultural heritage has become one of the most important challenges facing museums in the twenty-first century. Globalization, increasing visitor expectations, technological development, and the vulnerability of cultural objects to environmental, social, and human-induced factors require museums to adopt new strategies for documentation, conservation, and public engagement. In recent years, digital technologies have emerged as powerful tools that enable museums to preserve cultural heritage while simultaneously expanding access to collections and improving the quality of visitor experiences. (Pekarik & Doering, 2021; Chang, 2021)

International organizations and museum professionals increasingly recognize that digital transformation is not limited to the digitization of collections. Rather, it represents a comprehensive process that includes the creation of digital archives, virtual exhibitions, three-dimensional documentation, interactive educational resources, and innovative communication platforms. (Trichopoulos, Konstantakis & Caridakis, 2024) Such technologies enable museums to reach wider audiences, facilitate scholarly research, and provide alternative modes of access for individuals who are unable to visit museums physically.

The State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan occupies a special place within the cultural landscape of the country. Constructed at the turn of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, the Polovtsev House represents one

of the most significant examples of the synthesis of traditional Uzbek craftsmanship and European architectural planning in Tashkent. Today the building functions not only as a museum space but also as a heritage object requiring continuous conservation and documentation. (Abduxolikov et al., 2022) The museum is located in the historic Polovtsev House, one of the most significant architectural monuments of late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century Tashkent. (Ashurbayeva, 2025) The building itself represents an outstanding example of the synthesis of traditional Uzbek decorative arts, including wood carving, ganch decoration, ornamental painting, and architectural craftsmanship. In addition to preserving a rich collection of applied arts and handicrafts, the museum serves as an important centre for the study, interpretation, and popularization of Uzbekistan's cultural heritage. Museums worldwide are increasingly redefining their social and educational functions in accordance with contemporary museum principles (ICOM, 2022).

The growing number of domestic and international visitors has created new demands for museum accessibility, multilingual communication, and interactive interpretation. In response to these challenges, museums worldwide are increasingly implementing digital solutions, including three-dimensional scanning, photogrammetry, virtual tours, augmented reality technologies, wearable smart devices, and artificial intelligence-based translation systems. These innovations make it possible to preserve both tangible and intangible aspects of cultural heritage while creating new opportunities for visitor engagement.

The purpose of this study is to analyse the role of technological innovations in the preservation and interpretation of cultural heritage through the example of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan. Particular attention is devoted to three interconnected areas of technological development: digital preservation technologies, digital interpretation tools, and technologies that enhance museum accessibility (Li et al., 2024; Trichopoulos et al., 2024; Agranovich et al., 2024) for diverse audiences.

Materials and Methods

The study is based on a case-study approach focusing on the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan. The research combines qualitative analysis of contemporary museum practices with an examination of technological solutions currently applied or proposed for implementation within the museum environment.

The methodological framework includes several complementary approaches. First, a comparative analysis of international scholarly literature on digital heritage preservation, museum communication, wearable technologies, and artificial intelligence applications in museums was conducted. Particular attention was paid to studies addressing three-dimensional digitization, augmented reality systems, smart glasses, AI-assisted translation technologies, and visitor accessibility.

Second, observational methods were employed to examine the museum environment and evaluate the potential integration of technological solutions within the architectural and exhibition context of the Polovtsev House. The analysis considered both the preservation requirements of the historic building and the educational functions of the museum.

Third, the study utilized a technological assessment approach to evaluate the opportunities and limitations of selected innovations, including digital twins, virtual tours, smart glasses, and AI translation headphones. These technologies were analysed in relation to three key objectives: preservation of cultural heritage, interpretation of museum collections, and accessibility of museum information for local and international visitors.

The combination of these methods provides a comprehensive understanding of how technological innovations can support the sustainable development of museum institutions while preserving the authenticity and cultural significance of heritage sites.

Results and Discussion

Digital Preservation of Cultural Heritage

One of the primary challenges facing museums today is the long-term preservation of cultural heritage objects and historical architectural environments. Traditional conservation methods remain fundamental; however, they are increasingly complemented by digital technologies capable of documenting cultural assets with a high degree of accuracy and accessibility.

For the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan, located in the historic Polovtsev House, digital preservation represents a particularly significant direction of development. The building itself is an important monument of architectural and decorative art, distinguished by carved wooden ceilings, ornamental painting, ganch decoration, and unique examples of traditional craftsmanship. As with many historic structures, the preservation of these elements requires continuous monitoring and documentation.

Three-dimensional scanning and photogrammetry have become among the most promising methods for documenting museum collections and architectural heritage. These technologies enable the creation of accurate digital replicas (Itmus, 2019; Sketchfab Museums, 2024) of objects and interiors while preserving information about their geometry, dimensions, colours, and decorative details. Unlike conventional photography, three-dimensional models allow researchers and museum professionals to examine an object from multiple perspectives and conduct virtual measurements without direct physical contact.

The creation of digital twins is particularly important for museum collections and historic buildings. Digital twins can function as comprehensive information systems containing visual, historical, technical, and conservation-related data. In

the case of the Polovtsev House, the development of a digital twin would contribute not only to documentation but also to the preservation of architectural knowledge for future generations. Similar approaches are increasingly employed by museums and cultural heritage institutions worldwide (Itmus, 2019) as part of broader digital preservation strategies.

Digital documentation also creates opportunities for virtual restoration and reconstruction. Lost decorative elements, damaged architectural features, or inaccessible spaces can be digitally reconstructed on the basis of archival materials, historical photographs, and scientific analysis. Such practices provide valuable tools for research while minimizing intervention in the original historic fabric.

Digital Interpretation and Visitor Engagement

While preservation remains a fundamental museum function, contemporary museums are equally concerned with interpretation and communication. The effectiveness of museum interpretation directly influences visitor engagement, educational outcomes, and public understanding of cultural heritage.

The integration of virtual tours has significantly expanded opportunities for museum communication. Virtual environments allow users to explore museum spaces remotely, making collections accessible to audiences who are geographically distant or physically unable to visit. The development of panoramic technologies and immersive interfaces (ACDF & Google Arts & Culture, 2019) has transformed virtual museum experiences from simple photographic presentations into interactive educational platforms.

For the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan, virtual tours provide an opportunity to present both museum collections and the architectural significance of the Polovtsev House to international audiences. Through digital environments, visitors can examine exhibition halls, decorative interiors, and selected museum objects while receiving contextual information about their historical and artistic significance.

Another promising direction is the implementation of smart glasses and augmented reality technologies. Unlike traditional information panels or audio guides, smart glasses provide contextual information directly within the visitor's field of vision. Such systems can display historical reconstructions, (Trichopoulos et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024) object descriptions, translations, and multimedia content while preserving the continuity of the visitor's interaction with the museum environment.

The application of augmented reality is particularly valuable in historic buildings. In the Polovtsev House, AR technologies could enable visitors to visualize historical interiors, observe lost decorative elements, and explore different stages in the building's transformation over time. These technologies support a deeper understanding of cultural heritage (NazzAR Museum, 2024) by connecting physical objects with digital narratives.

Accessibility and Artificial Intelligence in Museum Communication

The growing internationalization of cultural tourism has increased the importance of multilingual museum communication. Museums are increasingly expected to provide information that is accessible to visitors from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Artificial intelligence-based translation technologies offer new opportunities (Agranovich et al., 2024) for overcoming language barriers. Recent developments in AI-assisted speech recognition and machine translation have made it possible to provide real-time interpretation during guided tours. Wireless headphones equipped with AI translation systems (Agranovich et al., 2024) can convert a guide's speech into multiple languages while maintaining the continuity of the guided museum tour.

For museums in Uzbekistan, where international tourism continues to grow, such technologies may significantly improve visitor accessibility. The State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan receives visitors from different countries whose familiarity with local languages varies considerably. AI translation systems can support communication without requiring separate tours for each language group.

The integration of AI translation headphones with smart glasses creates an especially effective communication environment. Visitors can simultaneously receive audio translations and visual information (Li et al., 2024; Trichopoulos et al., 2024) in their preferred language. Such an approach enhances comprehension, increases visitor confidence, and promotes a more inclusive museum experience.

In addition to multilingual communication, these technologies support accessibility for visitors with disabilities. Visual subtitles can assist individuals with hearing impairments, while audio descriptions can provide additional support for visitors with visual limitations. Consequently, digital technologies contribute not only to communication efficiency (Chang, 2021) but also to the broader social mission of museums.

Challenges and Future Perspectives

Despite their considerable advantages, technological innovations also present challenges. The implementation of digital systems requires financial investment, staff training, technical maintenance, and regular software updates. Museums must also address issues related to data preservation, cybersecurity, and the long-term sustainability of digital resources.

Another important consideration concerns the balance between technological innovation and authenticity. Digital tools should complement rather than replace direct encounters with cultural heritage. (Pekarik & Doering, 2021) The primary objective of technological innovation in museums should remain the enhancement of understanding, accessibility, and preservation rather than the creation of technological experiences for their own sake.

The experience of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan demonstrates that technological innovation can support all

major museum functions simultaneously. Digital twins strengthen preservation strategies; virtual tours and augmented reality improve interpretation; and artificial intelligence technologies enhance accessibility and international communication. Together, these developments contribute to the formation of a modern museum model capable of preserving cultural heritage while responding to the expectations of contemporary audiences.

Conclusion

The rapid development of digital technologies is significantly transforming contemporary museum practice and expanding opportunities for the preservation, interpretation, and dissemination of cultural heritage. The case of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan demonstrates that technological innovation can effectively support the core functions of a museum while preserving the authenticity and historical significance of cultural objects and architectural monuments.

The study has shown that digital preservation technologies, including three-dimensional documentation, photogrammetry, and digital twins, provide new mechanisms for recording and safeguarding museum collections as well as historic architectural environments. In the context of the Polovtsev House, these technologies create additional opportunities for documenting decorative elements, monitoring conservation conditions, and preserving information about the building for future generations.

The research also highlights the growing importance of digital interpretation tools. Virtual tours, augmented reality applications, and smart wearable devices contribute to a more engaging and informative visitor experience by connecting physical heritage with digital content. These technologies enhance educational outcomes and facilitate a deeper understanding of museum collections and historical spaces.

Particular attention has been paid to accessibility and multilingual communication. Artificial intelligence-based translation technologies and smart communication devices can significantly reduce language barriers and support the participation of international audiences. Their implementation is especially relevant in the context of increasing cultural tourism and expanding intercultural dialogue among visitors from different countries.

At the same time, the successful integration of technological innovations requires a balanced approach that combines digital solutions with traditional museum principles. Technology should not replace direct interaction with authentic cultural heritage but rather strengthen its preservation, interpretation, and accessibility.

The experience of the State Museum of Applied Arts and History of Handicrafts of Uzbekistan confirms that digital transformation is becoming an essential component of sustainable museum development. Future research may focus on the practical implementation of digital twins, augmented reality systems, and artificial

intelligence technologies within museum environments, as well as on evaluating their long-term impact on visitor engagement and heritage preservation. The presented case may serve as a model for the digital transformation of museum institutions in Uzbekistan and other SCO member states.

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当代乌兹别克斯坦的区域现代主义与文化认同：布哈拉文化空间中的泽利姆汗·赛义德诺夫艺术遗产

**REGIONAL MODERNISM AND CULTURAL IDENTITY IN
CONTEMPORARY UZBEKISTAN: THE ARTISTIC HERITAGE
OF ZELIMKHAN SAIDJANOV IN THE CULTURAL SPACE OF
BUKHARA**

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摘要：本研究探讨了泽利姆汗·赛义德诺夫作为中亚地区现代主义重要代表人物的艺术遗产，并考察了他对当代乌兹别克斯坦文化认同形成所做出的贡献。研究聚焦于布哈拉独特的历史和视觉环境中，当地文化传统与现代主义艺术表达之间的关系。研究特别关注艺术家对城市空间的诠释、其表现性变形的运用，以及心理意象在塑造其个人艺术语言中的作用。

本文将赛义德诺夫的作品置于更广阔的地区现代主义背景下进行分析，强调了当地文化记忆与现代艺术实践之间的互动。研究认为，艺术家的作品展现了一条不同于主流艺术中心、却又与中亚文化景观紧密相连的现代主义发展路径。通过对部分版画和绘画作品的分析，研究揭示了赛义德诺夫如何将布哈拉的视觉体验转化为一种既体现历史延续性又体现创造性创新的个人艺术叙事。

研究表明，泽利姆汗·赛义德诺夫的艺术遗产是乌兹别克斯坦文化资本的重要组成部分，并有助于探讨当代关于区域认同、艺术多样性以及在全球文化进程中保护地方文化传统的问题。

关键词：区域现代主义，文化认同，布哈拉，泽利姆汗·赛义德诺夫，乌兹别克斯坦当代艺术，文化记忆，艺术遗产，中亚艺术。

Abstract. *The study explores the artistic heritage of Zelimkhan Saidjanov as a significant representative of regional modernism in Central Asia and examines his contribution to the formation of cultural identity in contemporary Uzbekistan. The research focuses on the relationship between local cultural traditions and modernist artistic expression within the unique historical and visual environment of Bukhara. Particular attention is devoted to the artist's interpretation of urban*

space, his use of expressive deformation, and the role of psychological imagery in shaping an individual artistic language.

The article analyses Saidjanov's works within the broader context of regional modernism, emphasizing the interaction between local cultural memory and modern artistic practices. The study argues that the artist's oeuvre demonstrates an alternative trajectory of modernist development, distinct from major artistic centres yet deeply connected to the cultural landscape of Central Asia. Through the examination of selected graphic and pictorial works, the research reveals how Saidjanov transformed the visual experience of Bukhara into a personal artistic narrative that reflects both historical continuity and creative innovation.

The findings suggest that the artistic heritage of Zelimkhan Saidjanov represents an important component of Uzbekistan's cultural capital and contributes to contemporary discussions on regional identity, artistic diversity, and the preservation of local cultural traditions within global cultural processes.

Keywords: *regional modernism, cultural identity, Bukhara, Zelimkhan Saidjanov, contemporary Uzbek art, cultural memory, artistic heritage, Central Asian art.*

Introduction

The study of regional artistic movements has become an increasingly important direction within contemporary art history. In recent decades, scholars have demonstrated growing interest in forms of modernism that emerged outside the traditional centres of artistic production, challenging conventional narratives focused primarily on Western Europe and North America. Such approaches have contributed to a broader understanding of modernism as a diverse and multi-centred phenomenon shaped by local cultural conditions, historical experiences, and social contexts (Smith, 2009).

Within this framework, the artistic heritage of Central Asia occupies a distinctive position. The region has long served as a crossroads of civilizations, where diverse cultural traditions, religious influences, and artistic practices interacted across centuries. During the twentieth century, Central Asian artists developed unique creative approaches that combined elements of local cultural heritage with the formal innovations of modern art. These processes gave rise to regional forms of modernism that reflected both global artistic tendencies and local cultural identities (Weibel, 2015).

Among the historic cities of Uzbekistan, Bukhara represents a particularly significant cultural environment. Its architectural monuments, traditional neighbourhoods, decorative arts, and complex historical memory have shaped a distinctive visual culture that continues to influence contemporary artistic expression. Beyond its role as a historical and architectural centre, Bukhara functions as a

symbolic space in which cultural memory and artistic imagination intersect. As noted by Hakimov (2011), the artistic environment of Uzbekistan cannot be fully understood without considering the influence of local historical and cultural contexts on creative practice.

One of the most original representatives of Bukhara's artistic milieu was Zelimkhan Saidjanov, whose creative work occupies a unique place within the development of regional modernism in Uzbekistan. Although his artistic activity evolved during the late Soviet period, his works reveal a strong tendency toward individual artistic expression and formal experimentation. Rather than following the conventions of official artistic production, Saidjanov developed a visual language characterized by psychological intensity, expressive distortion, and a subjective interpretation of urban reality.

The significance of Saidjanov's artistic heritage extends beyond the history of regional art. His works offer valuable insight into the ways local cultural memory can be transformed into a contemporary artistic statement. Through the reinterpretation of familiar urban motifs, human figures, and symbolic imagery, the artist constructed a distinctive visual narrative that reflects the cultural identity of Bukhara while engaging with broader modernist concerns (Akilova, 2023).

The purpose of this study is to examine the artistic heritage of Zelimkhan Saidjanov as an expression of regional modernism and cultural identity in contemporary Uzbekistan. Particular attention is devoted to the relationship between local cultural memory, artistic innovation, and the representation of Bukhara as a cultural and symbolic space within the artist's oeuvre.

Regional Modernism and the Cultural Landscape of Bukhara

The concept of regional modernism has gained increasing attention within contemporary art historical scholarship as researchers seek to reconsider the geography of twentieth-century artistic development. Rather than viewing modernism as a phenomenon generated exclusively by major cultural centres, contemporary studies emphasize the existence of multiple modernities shaped by local historical and cultural circumstances (Weibel, 2015; Bourriaud, 2002). In this context, Bukhara represents a significant example of a regional cultural environment capable of generating distinctive artistic forms while maintaining a dialogue with broader modernist tendencies.

The historical fabric of Bukhara has long functioned as a source of artistic inspiration. The spatial organization of traditional neighbourhoods, the rhythm of narrow streets, the interplay of architectural volumes, and the rich decorative heritage of the city contribute to a unique visual atmosphere. Unlike monumental representations of urban space, Bukhara often appears in artistic interpretations as a place of memory, contemplation, and personal experience. Such qualities have influenced generations of artists whose work reflects the emotional and symbolic

dimensions of the city. Saidjanov's artistic development occurred within a broader circle of Bukhara-based artists who sought alternative modes of expression beyond officially sanctioned artistic conventions. Although each artist developed an individual visual language, their practices collectively contributed to the formation of a distinctive regional artistic environment that differed from the dominant cultural centres of the Soviet Union.

Fig. 1 - teahouse owner.
1970s.

Fig. 2 - figure at the gate.
1970s.

Fig. 3 - scene at the gate (repetition of the fragment in the 2000s)

The artistic practice of Zelimkhan Saidjanov emerged within this cultural environment. His works demonstrate a profound connection to the visual and psychological experience of Bukhara while simultaneously engaging with the formal language of modernism. The artist did not seek to reproduce the city through documentary accuracy. Instead, he transformed familiar urban motifs into expressive images shaped by subjective perception and emotional intensity.

This approach reflects a broader tendency characteristic of regional modernism in Central Asia, where local cultural traditions serve not as static historical references but as active components of contemporary artistic expression. Through this synthesis of cultural memory and artistic innovation, Saidjanov contributed to the development of a distinctive regional artistic language capable of articulating both local identity and universal human experience.

Artistic Language of Zelimkhan Saidjanov

A defining feature of Saidjanov's artistic heritage is the formation of a highly individual visual language based on expressive transformation rather than

descriptive representation. His artistic method departs from the conventions of academic realism and instead emphasizes psychological depth, emotional tension, and formal experimentation. Such an approach places his work within a broader modernist tradition while preserving a strong connection to local cultural experience (Krauss, 1985; Foster, 1996).

Particularly significant are the artist's graphic portraits created during the 1970s. These works reveal a conscious rejection of conventional portraiture. Rather than striving for physical resemblance, Saidjanov focuses on the emotional condition of the individual. Facial features are simplified, distorted, or fragmented, while colour and line become independent expressive elements. The resulting images function not merely as portraits but as psychological studies of human vulnerability, isolation, and inner reflection.

Fig.4. sacrifice (70s)

Fig.6. boy in an interior (70s)

Fig.7. renovation of an old house (from the 80s)

A particularly important characteristic of Saidjanov's early graphic works is what may be described as an "image without likeness." This tendency corresponds to broader discussions of modernist subjectivity and the rejection of mimetic representation (Foster, 1996; Groys, 2008). The artist deliberately distances himself from the traditional principles of portrait resemblance. Human figures are stripped of individual biographical specificity and transformed into carriers of emotional and psychological states. Through distortion, simplification, and fragmentation of facial features, Saidjanov constructs images that function as visual metaphors rather than portraits in the conventional sense. This strategy reflects a broader modernist aspiration to reveal inner experience rather than external appearance and became one of the defining features of his artistic language during the 1970s.

The series commonly referred to as "Alleyway Characters" occupies a special place within the artist's oeuvre. In these works, urban space ceases to function as

a realistic environment and instead becomes a metaphorical landscape of memory. The narrow streets of old Bukhara are transformed into symbolic spaces populated by figures whose identities appear suspended between reality and recollection. Through deliberate deformation of form and restrained colour relationships, the artist creates an atmosphere of introspection and emotional ambiguity.

The alleyways depicted in these works should not be understood as documentary representations of Bukhara's urban fabric. Rather, they function as psychological spaces shaped by memory, solitude, and subjective perception. The artist transforms the traditional quarters of the old city into symbolic environments where human presence acquires an existential dimension. In this sense, urban space becomes an active participant in the construction of meaning, reflecting the artist's personal experience of the city and its cultural memory. Such interpretations resonate with contemporary approaches to artistic space as a carrier of memory and experience (Assmann, 2011).

An important aspect of Saidjanov's artistic method is his treatment of human figures as carriers of cultural memory. His characters often transcend individual identity and acquire archetypal qualities. They represent collective experiences shaped by the social and cultural environment of Bukhara rather than specific biographical narratives. This transformation from individual portrait to cultural archetype reflects the artist's broader interest in the relationship between personal experience and collective memory.

The expressive qualities of Saidjanov's graphic works further reinforce this interpretation. Executed in charcoal, ink, and mixed techniques, many drawings retain an intentional incompleteness. Rather than presenting finished and polished images, the artist allows traces of the creative process to remain visible. This openness of form contributes to the emotional intensity of the works and encourages active engagement on the part of the viewer.

Through these artistic strategies, Saidjanov developed a visual language that combined modernist experimentation with a profound sensitivity to local cultural experience. His works demonstrate that artistic innovation can emerge from regional contexts without losing its capacity to engage with broader artistic discourses.

Cultural Memory and the Construction of Local Identity

An important aspect of Saidjanov's artistic heritage is the relationship between cultural memory and the construction of local identity. Unlike official artistic narratives that often emphasized generalized ideological imagery, the artist's works are deeply rooted in the visual and emotional experience of a specific cultural environment. Bukhara appears in his oeuvre not merely as a geographical location but as a symbolic space shaped by historical memory, everyday experience, and personal perception. The relationship between memory, identity, and artistic representation has been extensively discussed in cultural memory studies (Assmann, 2011).

The old city occupies a central position within Saidjanov's artistic imagination. Architectural fragments, narrow alleyways, enclosed courtyards, and human figures emerge as recurring motifs that structure the visual language of his works. Particular significance should be attributed to the recurring appearance of local archetypal figures. Characters such as the kharbon (donkey driver), tea-house visitors, and anonymous residents of the old quarters transcend their everyday identities and become symbolic embodiments of collective cultural memory. Through these figures, Saidjanov constructs a visual narrative of Bukhara that is rooted not in official historical representation but in lived experience and social memory. However, these elements are rarely presented as documentary representations. Instead, they function as carriers of cultural associations and emotional meanings. Through processes of formal transformation and expressive distortion, the artist reconstructs the city as a psychological landscape rather than a physical environment. Similar mechanisms of cultural representation may be observed in broader discussions of local identities within contemporary art (Smith, 2009).

Such an approach reflects broader mechanisms of cultural memory. As contemporary cultural studies suggest, memory is not limited to the preservation of historical facts but is continuously reconstructed through visual, symbolic, and artistic practices. In Saidjanov's works, Bukhara becomes a space where personal experience intersects with collective cultural memory. The city is perceived not as a static historical monument but as a living cultural organism that continues to shape artistic consciousness (Assmann, 2011).

This characteristic distinguishes Saidjanov's artistic practice from purely ethnographic representations of local culture. Traditional motifs in his works do not function as decorative signs intended to reproduce historical authenticity. Instead, they are transformed into elements of a contemporary artistic language capable of expressing complex psychological and cultural meanings. Through this process, local cultural heritage becomes an active participant in modern artistic discourse.

The significance of Saidjanov's artistic legacy extends beyond the history of regional art. His works contribute to the preservation of cultural identity by offering an alternative visual narrative of Bukhara. At a time when processes of globalization increasingly influence cultural production, such artistic practices acquire particular importance as forms of cultural self-representation and local historical memory.

The experience of Saidjanov also demonstrates that regional artistic traditions can generate innovative forms of modern expression. His oeuvre challenges the perception that artistic innovation emerges exclusively within major cultural centres. On the contrary, the cultural environment of Bukhara provided conditions for the development of an original artistic language capable of combining local experience with broader modernist concerns.

The Artistic Heritage of Saidjanov in Contemporary Cultural Discourse

Today, the artistic heritage of Zelimkhan Saidjanov may be considered an important component of Uzbekistan's cultural capital. Interest in regional artistic histories has increased significantly in recent years as scholars, museums, and cultural institutions seek to expand existing narratives of twentieth-century art. Within this process, the study of local artistic movements contributes to a more inclusive understanding of cultural diversity and artistic development in Central Asia.

The preservation and interpretation of regional artistic heritage have become especially relevant in contemporary cultural policy. Artistic archives, private collections, museum exhibitions, and scholarly research play an important role in maintaining cultural continuity and strengthening historical awareness. In this context, Saidjanov's works represent not only individual artistic achievements but also valuable documents of cultural memory reflecting the transformation of Bukhara's visual environment during the second half of the twentieth century.

The growing international interest in alternative modernisms creates new opportunities for the study of artists whose work developed outside dominant artistic centres (Weibel, 2015; Groys, 2008). Contemporary discussions on global modernism increasingly recognize the importance of local artistic experiences and regional cultural identities. Saidjanov's artistic practice may therefore be examined within broader debates concerning multiple modernities, peripheral modernisms, and the diversity of twentieth-century artistic expression.

Conclusion

For contemporary Uzbekistan, the study of regional artistic heritage contributes to the formation of a more complex and multifaceted cultural narrative. The artistic legacy of Zelimkhan Saidjanov demonstrates that local cultural environments possess significant creative potential and remain important sources of artistic innovation. Through the preservation and scholarly interpretation of such heritage, it becomes possible to strengthen cultural identity while simultaneously integrating (Foster, 1996; Groys, 2008) regional artistic histories into international academic discourse.

Saidjanov's artistic practice demonstrates how subjectivity functioned as a form of cultural and aesthetic autonomy within the regional artistic environment of late Soviet Bukhara.

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古俄语中主动和被动现在分词作为谓语的用法（与闪米特语系语言的比较）

**THE USE OF ACTIVE AND PASSIVE PRESENT PARTICIPLES
AS PREDICATES IN OLD RUSSIAN (IN COMPARISON WITH
SEMITIC LANGUAGES)**

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摘要：本文以不同时期的古俄语文献为研究对象，探讨了古俄语中主动和被动现在分词在谓语功能上的使用特征。文章还对古俄语与苏美尔语和闪米特语进行了比较分析。研究表明，古俄语中主动和被动现在分词的形式相当普遍。这类分词以及其他动词谓语的构成可以追溯到孤立的苏美尔语。然而，与圣经希伯来语和现代希伯来语（闪米特语）中的对应词不同，古俄语现在分词最初是作为复合名词谓语的名词成分，与系动词“是”连用。后来，随着俄语的演变，复合名词谓语中只保留了过去时被动分词的形式，这与印欧语系的语言结构相符。而现在分词在复合名词谓语中的形式则消失了，仅作为释义而存在。古俄语中以-ch结尾的分词形式也已消失或演变为形容词。在翻译中，这些分词形式通常被相关的动词所取代。

关键词：分词，谓语，古俄语，苏美尔语，希伯来语。

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the features of the use of active and passive present participles in the function of the predicate in Old Russian on the material of monuments from different periods. A comparative analysis is conducted with Sumerian and Semitic languages. It has been established that the forms of the present tense active and passive participles were quite common in the Old Russian language. The formation of such participles, as well as other verbal predicative names, can be traced back to the isolated Sumerian language. However, the Old Russian present participle, unlike its counterparts in Biblical and modern Hebrew (Semitic languages), was primarily used as a nominal component of a compound nominal predicate, accompanied by the linking verb “to be.” Later, in the process of the Russian language’s evolution, only the forms of past-tense passive participles remained in the compound nominal predicate, which is in line with the Indo-European system. The forms of present-tense participles in this function*

have been lost and remain only as definitions. The forms of participles with Old Russian suffixes ending in -ch have also been lost or have become adjectives. In translation, these participle forms are usually replaced by related verbs.

Keywords: *participle, predicate, Old Russian, Sumerian, and Hebrew.*

The use of participial forms as predicates is a rather widespread phenomenon in Indo-European languages. Here, one should first and foremost recall the complex verbal forms of most Western-type languages, where the second perfective participle is actively used to form the perfect, pluperfect, future perfect tense, and their analogues. As for the Russian language, the Indo-European perfect participle II mostly corresponds to the past passive participle, such as «сказанный», «сделанный», and others, the short form of which is still employed as the nominal component of the compound nominal predicate. Such a form is derived from transitive verbs, for example, «рисовать» – «нарисованный» ('to paint' – 'painted'); as a nominal component of a compound nominal predicate, it is predominantly used in the short, indeclinable form (was) «нарисован» ('painted'). This type of usage of the past passive participle (analogous to the Indo-European Participle II) constitutes the norm.

In the present article, we examine the usage of another type of participles within the predicate, either as a nominal component or as the sole component. This is a present tense active voice participle, for example, «идущий» (going), «говорящий» (speaking), and others. Moreover, such participles can be formed from both transitive and intransitive verbs. For modern Russian, as well as for many other Indo-European languages, the use of present tense active voice participles (analogous to the Indo-European participle I) as predicates is atypical; however, in Old Russian, such constructions were fairly widespread.

The objective of the article is to investigate the common prerequisites for the formation of participial predicative constructions in Indo-European and Semitic languages, based on material from the isolated ancient Sumerian language; to determine the features of the usage of active and passive present participles in Old Russian texts; to identify the reasons for the loss of these forms; and to conduct a comparison with certain Semitic languages (Biblical and Modern Hebrew).

To identify the features of usage of this type of participles in the history of the Russian language, it is necessary to briefly examine the general history of the formation of participial forms in one of the oldest deciphered isolated languages, as well as to make a comparison with the Semitic languages.

In the **Sumerian** language (which represents an agglutinative type and, simultaneously, the oldest linguistic stage), there existed a unique form of verbal noun that was still an indeterminate verbal noun (participle, infinitive, gerund, deverbal adjective), positioned on the boundary between noun and verb; It could function

as the predicate in a nominal sentence. For example, the phrase *lú du-du-zu* can be translated into both nominal and verbal variants: ‘a person knowing vagrancy’ / ‘a person walking-walking to know’ [5, p. 180]. I.T. Kaneva designates such forms as non-finite verb forms, which comprise either a pure verbal root or a root with the suffix *-a* [5, p. 179]. The uniqueness of these forms lay in the fact that the ancient verbal root simultaneously encompassed the properties of both a noun and a verb [5, p. 179]. It is probable that this nominal formation can be considered a certain predicative substrate that might have existed in the most ancient stage of various Indo-European and Semitic languages and subsequently developed both verbal and nominal functions. However, the predominance of particular functions within this formation led to the fact that, in languages of different branches, this verbal noun was used either as part of complex tense forms with a copular verb or independently functioned as a predicate in nominal constructions [1, p. 151].

In **Semitic languages** the system of verbal tenses has traditionally not exhibited the familiar developed structure characteristic of Indo-European languages based on three primary forms: present, past, and future. “The verb in numerous Semito-Hamitic languages does not possess the category of tense” [2, p. 429]. Since Ancient Egyptian, temporal reference has been primarily confined to the notion of perfective/imperfective aspect. The noun and the verb constituted two extensive lexical classes, between which there was a profound morphological distinction. Nevertheless, the categories of noun and verb exhibit a profound mutual influence, and in many cases it is possible to trace the derivation of verbal forms from nominal bases and, conversely, many nouns from verbal bases [3, p. 180].

In Semitic languages, there were two conjugated verbal forms that denote the aspect of completeness/incompleteness of the action. At present, these forms are also related to the expression of tense. Thus, in later (post-biblical) Hebrew, the imperfect form became fixed for expressing the future tense, while for the present tense a new form formed from a pronoun *and a* participle began to be used, for example: *ʾanī hōlēk* “I am going,” *ʾattā hōlēk* “you are going,” *hū hōlēk* “he is going,” *ʾahnū hōl(e)kīm* “we are going,” etc.” [3, p. 190]. The use of the pronoun in this case is necessary because Hebrew, both Biblical and modern, does not possess explicit declensional forms. Accordingly, the present participle combined with a noun or pronoun constitutes a form of nominal sentence in which the participle, analogous to the Russian *-л* participle, functions as the predicate. According to B.M. Grande, ‘such combinations in Biblical texts occur to denote an action in the present, occasionally an unfinished action in the past;’ In later periods, as well as in contemporary literary language, these combinations represent a grammatical form of the present tense of the verb, whereas the old imperfect denotes the future tense, and the perfect — the past tense, irrespective of the completeness or incompleteness of the action” [3, 190].

Thus, it may be concluded that in certain Semitic languages the participial form, used to designate the present tense in place of a finite verb form, has historically occupied an intermediate position between completed and uncompleted action. This form can in part be compared to the use of the past participle in Indo-European languages; however, the present tense aspect of this form is a characteristic unique to Semitic languages. The principal difference between the Semitic present tense participle and the Indo-European past tense participle in -l- lies in the fact that the former, having already merged with the pronoun in Aramaic (which subsequently became a suffix), developed into a fully conjugated present tense form, whereas the latter persisted as an independent form following the dissolution of complex verbal constructions. Although, as noted above, the -l- participle could already function as a predicate without a copular verb in the pre-literate epoch [1, p. 194].

In Old Russian, as previously indicated, constructions comprising present tense participles (predominantly active voice) in combination with forms of the verb 'to be' were highly frequent. Such constructions are uncharacteristic for contemporary Russian. We will examine several examples of the use of participles as the nominal component of the compound nominal predicate. It is possible to immediately observe the following regularity: in contemporary Russian, the nominal component of a compound nominal predicate predominantly comprises the short forms of passive present participles.

Бъ есть **сѣдя** на нбсѣхъ и на престолю **славимъ** [from English 4, p. 165].

In the present example, the compound verbal predicate contains homogeneous nominal components: the short active present participle **сѣдя** and the **short passive present participle** **славимъ**. **The final form is derived from a transitive verb but is no longer employed in modern Russian.**

In the following examples, we observe an analogous situation, wherein archaic forms of the verb «быти» serve as the grammatical component of the predicate in the most ancient texts, whereas in contemporary

And there are churches standing (= stands) in the city of Korsun [6, p. 109].

The essence of (the Greeks) is cunningly **expressed** (= they say), and it is strange to hear them [6, p. 104].

The messenger sent his servants into the cave, the people who **are tribute giving** (= give) to Novgorod [6, p. 107].

The Drevlians sent their foremost men, numbering... to Olza. And he landed near Borichev in a boat. **For then** the running water (= water was flowing) was **near the Kiev mountain** [4, p. 45].

There was a forest and a great woodland near the city, and beasts **were hunting** (they hunted) [6, p. 9].

And he arrived at the place where the bare bones of his (the horse's) lay [4, p. 31].

You will be groaning and shaking (= they were groaning and shaking) to their very belly [6, p. 38].

And **they will be wandering** among the nations (= they will wander) [6, p. 96].

But for us, **offended ones** (= reprovéd ones) ... by those lawless Agaryans, while we await the grace of God and His glorious face [4, p. 135].

He neither would be a thief, nor a drunkard, nor a grain dealer, nor a thief, nor a robber, nor a fornicator, nor anyone who commits evil (= would not commit evil) [7, p. 161].

Prince Peter in Pskov was formerly a prince, and knew all the Pskovians, and was himself known as a Pskovian [9, p. 97].

In the last example, we observe the usage of an active present participle in place of a passive one derived from the verb 'to know' (we know). In contemporary Russian, instead of the participle, the adjective derived from the corresponding verbal root is employed: 'был знаком'.

Егда же несяхуть и къ гробу, предивно знамение бысть на небеси: **быша** три солнца **съяюче** (=shining) межи собою, а столпи трие стояще отъ земля до небеси [4, p. 18].

In this example, an archaic participial form containing the Old Russian suffix -юч- is evidenced. In modern Russian, such forms have predominantly been lost or have undergone adverbialization, subsequently passing into the class of adjectives: рабочий, горячий, кипучий, and others. A similar picture is seen in the following example:

Our villages and our towns were laid waste, **we were fleeing** (= were running) before our enemies [6, p. 95].

Know (= know), noble prince: the soul was created through divine inspiration [8, p. 64].

In this example, we observe an imperative form of the verb "to be."

And **Oleg possessed** (= possessed) the Polyans... and from the Ulich and Tiverci he had an army [6, p. 24].

And Yaropolk installed his posadniks in Novgorod and **held dominion** (= possessed) one in Rus [6, p. 74].

In the final examples, a short active present participle of masculine gender in the base form, lacking the suffix -ч/щ-, is employed, which externally aligns this form with the later adverbial participle.

Conclusions

According to the results of the conducted analysis, it has been established that the forms of active and passive present participles in Old Russian textual monuments were quite well attested. The prerequisites for the formation of such participles, as well as other verbal nominal forms of the predicative type, can be traced back to the

isolated Sumerian language. However, the Old Russian present tense participle, unlike the analogous forms in Biblical and Modern Hebrew (Semitic languages), was predominantly employed as the nominal component of the compound nominal predicate together with the copulative verb ‘быть’ (‘to be’). Subsequently, throughout the evolution of the Russian language, only passive past participle forms persisted within the compound nominal predicate, which entirely corresponds to the general Indo-European system. And the forms of present tense participles in this function were lost and remained only as modifiers. The participle forms with Old Russian suffixes -ч- also disappeared or shifted into the class of adjectives. In translation, all these participial forms are generally replaced by cognate verbs.

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HOLONYMS 作为中世纪高级建筑和行政文化的证据（基于 ABU' L-FAZL BAYHAQI 的“TARIKH-I BAYHAQI”和 AHMAD TUSI 的“AJA' IB AL-MAKHLUQAT WA GHARA' IB AL-MAWJUDAT”的材料）

HOLONYMS AS EVIDENCE OF THE HIGH ARCHITECTURAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE CULTURE OF THE MIDDLE AGES (BASED ON MATERIALS FROM ABU'L-FAZL BAYHAQI'S "TARIKH-I BAYHAQI" AND AHMAD TUSI'S "AJA'IB AL-MAKHLUQAT WA GHARA'IB AL-MAWJUDAT")

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本文致力于研究中世纪堡垒、宫殿和防御工事（dizh）的名称——即地名，以此作为中世纪建筑和行政知识高度发达的体现。研究以阿布法兹勒·白哈基的《白哈基史》（*Tarikh-i Bayhaqi*）和艾哈迈德·图西的《阿乔伊布·乌尔·马赫卢科特与加罗伊布·乌尔·马乌朱多特》（*Ajoib-ul Mahluqot and Garoib-ul-Mawjudot*）为依据。研究表明，这些文献除了包含历史和地理信息外，还包含作为地名的地物信息。地名属于行政地理对象的地名范畴，可作为历史遗迹进行研究，并可用于确定特定对象的地理位置。本文探讨了堡垒的历史渊源、堡垒建造中体现的高超工程技术、天文计算在堡垒建造中的应用、堡垒与水文资源的衔接、堡垒作为休憩和疗养场所的功能、堡垒建造的融资因素、堡垒起源的神话传说、堡垒作为防御工事和历史人物庇护所的作用、要塞和城堡兴起的原因、要塞作为历史事件的直接发生地，以及堡垒作为著名囚禁场所的历史。

关键词：堡垒、城堡、要塞、要塞、要塞、高超的工程技术、高水平的行政管理、天文计算、水文资源、要塞和城堡的融资、防御、历史庇护所。

This article is dedicated to the study of golonyms – names of fortresses, palaces, and dizh (fortifications) as monuments of high architectural and administrative knowledge of the Middle Ages, based on "Tarikh-i Bayhaqi" of Abulfazl Baihaqi and "Ajoib-ul Mahluqot and Garoib-ul-Mawjudot" of Ahmad Tusi. The research

showed that these written sources, in addition to historical and geographical information, also contain data about objects that serve as toponyms. Golonyms belong to a category of toponymic names of administrative-geographical objects that are studied as historical monuments, through which can also be identified the geographical location of certain objects. The article examines the historical founders of golonyms, the high level of engineering knowledge in the construction of these objects, the use of astronomical calculations in the construction of golonyms, the building of golonyms with access to hydronyms, golonyms as places for rest and treatment, factors that facilitated financing their construction, mythological sources of the origin of golonym, golonyms as defensive objects and shelters for historical figures, reasons for the emergence of fortresses and castles, fortresses as direct sites of historical events, and golonyms as famous places of imprisonment.

Keywords: *golonyms, qasr, qal'a, kushk, dij, hisn, high engineering level, high administrative level, astronomical calculations, access to hydronyms, financing of fortress and castle construction, defense, historical shelters.*

The history of Persian-Tajik civilization has produced numerous historical, geographical, literary, and scholarly written works. In addition to reflecting the socio-economic conditions of various periods, each source provides detailed information about the geographical situation of specific regions. Abu'l-Fazl Bayhaqi's "*Tarikh-i Bayhaqi*" and Ahmad Tusi's "*Aja'ib al-Makhlūqat wa Ghara'ib al-Mawjudat*" are among such historical-geographical written sources that contain valuable information about the administrative and geographical conditions of the 11th -12th centuries. These works are outstanding administrative-geographical sources that, alongside major toponymic names, also record names associated with administrative and geographical objects.

Holonyms – the names of castles and fortresses – constitute one category of names related to administrative and historical sites. Their locations, often on mountaintops, riverbanks, or elevated areas that facilitated surveillance and defense, directly indicate the geographical characteristics of particular regions. During the Middle Ages, the placement of castles was crucial for protecting populations and resources. Furthermore, castles were frequently constructed along borderlines and trade routes, serving the purposes of monitoring and safeguarding important commercial and military routes. Their locations also reveal the presence of favorable natural environments, including water resources (rivers and springs) and rich flora and fauna. Access to castles and fortresses was provided through strategic routes, emphasizing the importance of mountain passes and communication corridors.

Descriptions of castles and fortresses in the 11th-12th centuries, based on the sources examined, demonstrate that their primary significance was connected with important social, political, and cultural functions. These historical and

geographical structures symbolized the power and authority of rulers, served as defensive and protective sites, functioned as centers of local administration, and represented military strength. Fortresses are among the most prominent architectural and historical monuments of the Middle Ages. They performed not only military functions but also important administrative-geographical roles. During periods when centralized states and administrative systems were still developing, fortresses constituted key elements in the control of territory and population. First and foremost, they served as centers of power and governance. In this way, a fortress was not merely a military stronghold but also an administrative center that organized local authority and protected inhabitants from external threats. The strategic geographical placement of fortresses enabled effective monitoring of the movement of people and goods, as well as ensuring security and surveillance.

Fortresses functioned as “bottlenecks” within the administrative-territorial structure, dividing lands into manageable units. Through these fortifications, fragmented territories could be integrated into a unified state. In historical studies, fortresses are often described as “bridges” between the central government and peripheral regions. They also influenced the development of cities and settlements, around which shops, artisan quarters, and rural communities emerged, contributing to economic growth and the stability of administrative structures. Bayhaqi’s *“Tarikh-i Bayhaqi”* contains 37 holonyms, while Ahmad Tusi’s – *“Aja’ib al-Makhluqat wa Ghara’ib al-Mawjudat”* includes 26 holonyms denoting castles and fortresses. In addition to using these names, both authors describe their geographical locations, architectural characteristics, and surrounding environments. Besides representing administrative-geographical objects, these holonyms also demonstrate the high level of architectural knowledge and achievement in the Middle Ages, which is clearly reflected in the works under study.

The study of holonyms—names of castles and fortresses – first requires an examination of the synonymous terms associated with them, which also facilitates the identification of their architectural characteristics. The synonymous series of the word *qasr* (“castle” or “palace”) includes *qal’a*, *hisar*, *dizh*, *kushk*, and *hisn*. Their meanings are as follows: *qal’a* – a high, solid, and strongly fortified structure built for protection against enemies and resistance to attack; a fortress or stronghold; *qasr* – a palace, royal residence, or pavilion; *hisar* – a fortified place, fortress, or the wall surrounding a fortress; *dizh* (*diz*) – a fortress, stronghold, or citadel; *kushk* – a magnificent building outside a city, usually surrounded by gardens; a palace or pavilion; *hisn* – a refuge, fortified place, or fortress.

These terms collectively reflect the diversity of architectural forms and defensive structures characteristic of the medieval Persian-Tajik world. It should be particularly noted that the various synonymous terms used for castles and fortresses in the sources under study differ in their specific semantic and functional

characteristics. From the perspective of the authors of these works, one distinctive feature of the synonym *dizh* (*diz*) in relation to *qal'a* (fortress) may be identified. The term *dizh/diz* was widely used and highly productive in the formation of holonyms, as will be discussed and analyzed separately below.

In “*Tarikh-i Bayhaqi*” the lexical meanings of *dizh/diz* and *qal'a* are explained as follows: “from the Indian word *kut* – fortress; *kutwal* – guardian of a fortress; *dizhban* – keeper of a fortress; *qala'* – the plural of *qal'a*, fortresses; *kuhandiz* – the arabicized form of *kuhandizh*; *kutwal* – fortress keeper, commander of a fortress” (p. 51). In «*Aja'ibnama*», another variant is provided: “*husun* – pavilions, fortresses, castles” (p. 23). In «*Aja'ibnama*», the element *dizh* also functions as a toponym-forming suffix and appears in different categories of geographical names, including hydronyms (*Shabdiz* – the name of a spring), holonyms (*Kuhandizh/Kuhandiz* – the name of a fortress), and settlement names (*Dizh* – the name of a village). Thus, *dizh* serves as a productive component in the formation of various toponyms, including *kuhandizh/kuhandiz*. It should also be emphasized that the characteristics of castles and fortresses in the sources under investigation are generally expressed through noun-adjective constructions (the name of the fortress combined with a descriptive attribute). Through such descriptions, the high level of architectural and administrative culture of the Middle Ages can be identified. Among these indicators, the following is particularly significant:

1. Construction of holonymic objects by historical personalities. In addition to being stone defensive structures, castles and fortresses possess a historical background closely associated with prominent historical figures. These individuals were responsible for the construction, administration, and utilization of such fortifications. During the construction of historical castles, resources and labor were invested not only in the physical structure itself but also in the embodiment of the rulers' views on power, strategy, and symbolism. Many kings and influential leaders of the medieval period understood that a fortress was not merely a military installation but also a powerful symbol of their authority and influence. Historical figures carefully selected the locations for the construction of castles, taking into account the strategic significance of particular regions. This demonstrates their awareness of geopolitical realities and the necessity of controlling important transportation routes and border areas.

Furthermore, castles reflected the personalities of their owners. Some rulers constructed fortifications that were strictly functional and primarily designed for defense, while others built magnificent and aesthetically impressive structures that symbolized prestige and wealth. The construction of castles by historical figures in the Middle Ages was a complex process in which military strategy, political considerations, and personal visions of authority were intertwined. Consequently, historical castles reveal not only the characteristics of their era but

also the personalities and worldviews of those who built and governed them. The above observations are clearly illustrated by the following examples from the sources under study: *Iram qasrest nek. Onro bino kard Shahdod ibni Od. Qolallohu taolo. Va Ofaridgor guft: «Yod kuned Iramro, ki sutunhoi olī dosht va dar bilod misli on nest»* [6, p.15].— It was built by Shahdad, son of Adam. Glory be to God Almighty. And the Creator said: “Remember Iram, which had lofty pillars, and there is nothing like it in the lands.; «*Va qasri Mashid malike kard dar bani Isroil. Vayro vazire bud. Bo chahor hazor mard dar biyobone shud, joye did narm va obe nekū, onro ibodatjoyi xyð kard va ibodat mekard rūzgore daroz. On gah, hisori malikro va qasri malikro barham zad va onro muattalu holī va xarob bigzosht»* [6, p.241].— And the palace of Mashid was built by a king among the Children of Israel. He had a vizier. With four thousand men he went into the desert and found a place with soft ground and pure water; he made it his place of worship and worshipped there for a long time. Then he destroyed the king’s fortress and palace, leaving it desolate, empty, and ruined.”; *Hisni Sufr qal’aest rūyin dar biyoboni Andalus. Onro Zulqarnayn bino kard va kitobho va ganjho dar on nihod va dar vay ba tilism kard. Va kas dar on roh nayoabad. Va andaruni on ba sang bino kard va devori on ba nuhos. Har ki on jo rasad, onro binad, chandon bikhanda, ki bimupað* [6, p.207].— Hisn-i Sufr is an iron fortress in the desert of Andalusia. It was built by Dhu al-Qarnayn, who placed books and treasures inside it and enchanted it with a talisman. No one can find a way into it. Its interior was built of stone, and its walls were made of copper. Whoever reaches it and sees it begins to laugh so much that they die.

2. Evidence of advanced engineering knowledge in the construction of holonymic objects. Medieval castles and fortresses were not merely defensive walls, they were remarkable achievements of engineering and architecture that demonstrated the high level of skill, knowledge, and creativity possessed by medieval builders. The construction of castles during the Middle Ages was a complex process in which military necessity, aesthetic considerations, and technical innovations were closely intertwined. First and foremost, the construction of castles required profound engineering expertise. In building strong walls, towers, and moats, engineers employed the most advanced methods of fortification and defense available at the time. Thick stone walls and narrow defensive openings, for example, provided protection against siege equipment, while sophisticated systems of drawbridges and gates made access difficult for enemies. Engineers carefully calculated the structural stability of fortifications and took into account the characteristics of the terrain and climatic conditions to ensure the durability and longevity of these structures.

The architectural design of castles was equally noteworthy. Every component of a castle served a specific purpose, ranging from reception halls and storage

facilities to residential quarters for its inhabitants. Architects designed spaces that ensured both the comfort of residents and the effectiveness of defensive measures. Furthermore, castles were often adorned with carvings, wall paintings, and symbols of state authority that reflected the social status of their owners and their level of cultural development. The construction of castles also reflected the technological progress of the medieval period. With the introduction of new building materials and tools, builders were able to create increasingly complex and magnificent structures. The use of columns, arches, and carved architectural elements made it possible to construct larger, more durable, and more sophisticated spaces.

Finally, castles functioned as symbols of power and prestige and were therefore designed and constructed with exceptional care and grandeur. Their imposing appearance was intended to inspire fear in enemies and respect among allies. A castle was not merely a defensive structure but also an architectural monument that combined practical functionality with aesthetic excellence.

This high level of architectural and administrative culture embodied in castles and pavilions is clearly illustrated by the following examples: *“Ahrām qasrest olī. Ibnī Ufair g̃yad in qasrro Jubayri Mu ‘tafi kard ba haftod sol, ba haftod hazor mardi banno. Du amudro bikard bar du saratoni r̃ỹyin, onro «musallatayn» g̃ỹyand. Va g̃ỹyand in har du amudro az k̃ỹhi Barqa ovar̃d va ba haftsad sol onro biburidand va bar kor nihodand. Va javone bud nomi vay Katan ibni Havoron, har du amudro bar du gunbad nihod az obgina ba ilme, ki Ofaridgor vayro doda bud va barobari eshon du gov kard az mis”* [6, p.159]. – *Ahrām is a magnificent palace. Ibn Ufair states that this palace was built by Jubayr al-Mu ‘tafi over a period of seventy years with the labor of seventy thousand builders. He erected two columns upon two bronze crabs, which were called the ‘Musallatayn’. It is said that both columns were brought from Mount Barqa and that it took seven hundred years to cut and prepare them before they were put into place. There was also a young man named Qatan ibn Hawaran who, through the knowledge bestowed upon him by the Creator, placed the two columns upon two glass domes and fashioned two copper bulls corresponding to them.*

3. The role of astronomical calculations in the construction of holonymic objects. In addition to their defensive functions, castles were often constructed with consideration of astronomical knowledge, reflecting the profound understanding medieval architects possessed regarding the relationship between celestial phenomena and earthly life. This demonstrates the advanced intellectual and scientific culture of the medieval period. One of the key aspects of the astronomical approach to castle construction was the orientation of structures toward the cardinal directions and significant celestial bodies. Main gates, towers, and principal halls were frequently designed so that their axes aligned with the position of the rising or setting sun during the equinoxes and solstices. Such orientation not

only facilitated the effective use of natural light and heat but also symbolically connected the fortress with the cosmic order, thereby reinforcing the authority and protective power of its rulers. Furthermore, some castles incorporated architectural elements that functioned as astronomical instruments. Windows, openings, and arrow slits were often designed in such a way as to enable the observation of important astronomical events or the monitoring of the positions of stars and planets. Such observations were significant for planning agricultural activities, military operations, and religious ceremonies.

During the Middle Ages, astronomy was closely associated with politics and governance. Rulers frequently consulted astronomers and astrologers when making important decisions concerning the construction and strategic placement of castles. The alignment of a fortress with cosmic cycles was regarded as a guarantee of success, prosperity, and protection from enemies. This phenomenon is also clearly reflected in the sources examined in the present study: "Va g̃yand, ki: «Ba hududi Misr qal'ae ast, onro Haramon g̃yand. Bar dari vay nabishtaand, ki on r̃y, ki in binoro kardand, Nasri Toir va Nasri Voqe'dar burji Saraton budand. Va aknun ba burji Jadī rasidaand. Va har burje se daraja buvad va har darajae ba sad sol bibarad. Tu bibin, ki umri sobita chand boshad!» Az in jins, az a'mori olam va sinni kavokib bozg̃yand.» [6, p.45]. – It is said that within the boundaries of Egypt there is a fortress called Haramon. An inscription on its gate states: 'On the day when this structure was built, the stars Nasr al-Tā'ir (the flying eagle) and Nasr al-Wāqi' (the falling eagle) were in the zodiac sign of Cancer. Now they have reached the sign of Capricorn. Each zodiac sign comprises thirty degrees, and each degree corresponds to one hundred years. Consider, therefore, how great its age must be!' Through such accounts, they describe the age of the world and the antiquity of the stars".

4. Construction of holonymic objects in relation to hydronymic sources.

Medieval castles were often deliberately constructed with careful attention to their location near hydronymic features, including rivers, lakes, canals, and other water sources. Such placement played a crucial role not only in the defensive and economic functions of the fortress but also in ensuring the livelihood of its inhabitants and maintaining strategic control over surrounding territories. The presence of water near a castle was of vital importance. Water served not only for drinking purposes but also as an essential resource for agriculture, irrigation, and livestock. A castle located near a river or lake also enjoyed a significant advantage during sieges, as access to water was a decisive factor for survival. Water bodies were also used as natural defensive barriers. Rivers or lakes surrounding a fortress made access more difficult for enemies and restricted possible routes of attack. Water-filled moats represented a classical element of military architecture, significantly enhancing the defensive capabilities of castles.

Proximity to waterways also enabled strategic control over trade and transport routes. Castles located near rivers or ports were able to monitor the movement of goods and people, thereby strengthening their economic and administrative influence. Hydrological features also influenced architectural and engineering decisions in castle construction. Engineers took into account water levels, flood risks, and terrain characteristics when designing fortifications, drainage systems, and water supply mechanisms. Castles were built in accordance with natural environmental conditions, ensuring their long-term functionality and structural stability. Access to hydronymic resources was therefore one of the key factors in selecting locations for castle construction. Water provided essential resources, natural defense, and opportunities for economic and strategic control. Understanding this complex relationship helps to better appreciate the historical significance and engineering expertise embodied in medieval castles, as is clearly reflected in the sources under study: “*Sadir qasrest mashhur, miyoni nahr-i Hira to Najaf va Kaskar. Va chashmahost: Ayn-ut-Taf va Saydo va Kutkutona. Sadirro bino kard Bahromi Chubin ibni Yazdigird ibni Shapur. Va sabab on bud, ki Yazdigirdro hech pizar name mond va Bahromro istisqo rasid, az atibbo pursidand, ki: «Joyi neku va havoi khush kujjoast?» Guftand: «Ba Sadir»*” [6, p.345]. – *Sadir is a well-known fortress located between the Hira River, Najaf, and Kaskar. Nearby are several springs: Ayn al-Taff, saydo, and Kutkutona. Sadir was built by Bahram Chobin, son of Yazdegerd, son of Shapur. The reason for its construction was that Yazdegerd had no surviving sons, and Bahram suffered from a severe illness. When he asked the physicians, ‘Where is a good place with a pleasant climate?’ they replied: ‘In Sadir.*

5. Construction of holonymic objects for recreation and medical purposes. Medieval castles were not solely designed for military purposes; many of them were built as places of recreation and seclusion for the nobility, where comfort, aesthetic beauty, and social status were simultaneously emphasized. These castles were often located in picturesque environments—on hills overlooking valleys, or near rivers and lakes—allowing their owners to temporarily distance themselves from the demands of military and political affairs and to enjoy nature and tranquility. Such environments contributed to the improvement of health, facilitated family life, and enabled the holding of social gatherings. From an architectural perspective, recreational castles differed from purely defensive fortifications. In their construction, greater attention was paid to aesthetics and comfort. They typically included spacious rooms, halls with large windows, gardens, and surrounding promenades. Many such castles also contained bath complexes, hunting lodges, and summer reception halls, effectively transforming them into palaces of leisure and relaxation. These structures often became centers of cultural life within their regions. Recreational castles also served strategic purposes. They reinforced the presence of the nobility in specific regions and facilitated the administration

and control of land, though in a softer and more comfortable manner compared to military fortresses. A description of such a castle is presented in the sources under study as follows: «*Бифармуд то касри Садир бино карданд ва ўро он ӯ оварданд. Ва вай аз ин иллат шифо ёфт. Ва шиғифт ӯйеест*» [6, с.172]. – He ordered the construction of the Sadir palace and had him brought there. There he was cured of his illness. It is a wondrous place.

6. High financial expenditure in the construction of holonymic objects. The construction of medieval castles and fortresses involved large-scale architectural and engineering projects that required substantial financial resources, materials, and labor. Castle building in the Middle Ages was a complex and costly process that could last for decades and demand continuous investment. The cost of construction materials—stone, wood, metal, and tools was extremely high, as these constituted the essential components of any fortress. Another significant factor was human labor. The construction of a castle required a wide range of specialists, including stonemasons, carpenters, diggers, weapons craftsmen, and other artisans, as well as a large number of general laborers and servants. Organizing and coordinating this workforce, as well as providing food, shelter, and protection, placed a considerable financial burden on the patrons of construction.

Investment in castles also had political and social implications. A magnificent fortress symbolized status and authority, reinforcing the power and independence of its owner. This often led to competition among the nobility, resulting in even greater investment in defense and architecture. In some cases, castles took decades to complete, requiring continuous funding, maintenance of construction sites, and adaptation of designs in accordance with new technologies and architectural trends, further increasing costs and complexity.

Financing of castle construction was typically carried out through taxation, collection of revenues from the population, income from property and trade, and in some cases through alliances, political centers, or even loans. Despite all efforts, castle construction remained a privilege of the wealthy and powerful, as clearly indicated in the sources under study through references to the phrase “great expenditure of silver and gold»: Matn ba lotinī “*Shirmoh qasrest on jo, ki dehi Abuayub ba Kuhiston. Va dakkai azim va obe ravon. Gʻyand zane meraft, tife dar kanor dosht, lashkari Nuʻmon ibni Munzir dar ob rond, zan joma bardosht, bitarsid va biaftod va tiftl gʻarq shud. Nuʻmon diltang shud va nazr kard, ki on jo pule sozad. Az Kisro dasture khost. Manʻ kard. To vayro asare naboshad dar in diyor*” [6, p.205]. – *Shirmoh is a fortress located in the place where the village of Abu Ayyub lies in the mountainous region. It has a great ravine and flowing water. It is said that a woman was passing by carrying a child in her arms when the army of Nuʻman ibn Mundhir passed through the water. The woman lifted her garment, became frightened, fell, and the child drowned. Nuʻman became saddened and vowed to build*

a bridge there. He asked permission from Khosrow, but it was refused so that no trace of him would remain in that land.

7. Mythological sources of the origin of holonymic objects. Medieval castles have always stimulated human imagination and thought, and were often remembered as objects associated with numerous myths, legends, and epic narratives. They were perceived as large and imposing structures, frequently situated on hilltops or deep within forests, and were regarded as symbols of mystery and the supernatural. Mythological castles in the Middle Ages were often associated with forces and beings beyond the natural world. It was believed that spirits, ghosts, sorcerers, or even dragons inhabited their walls. A castle could be seen as both a place of great power and protection, as well as a site of curse or evil enchantment. Such legends endowed castles with a mystical status and sometimes served as warnings to those who dared to approach them. Although historical evidence regarding the existence of such castles is often debated, they are understood as symbols of absolute sovereignty and as expressions of the dreams, ideals, and fears of medieval society. Mythological castles were frequently linked to the concept of sacred space, as if they had been constructed in places endowed with special power—near springs, on sacred hills, or on ancient cult sites. These locations were considered “bridges” between the human world and the divine or spiritual realm.

Castle legends also reflected the social and political realities of their time. Stories of dragons, sorcerers, and displaced princes often symbolized struggles for power, loyalty, and betrayal. A clear example illustrating the nature of mythological castles is the following passage: “*Va qal'ai Qatron madinaest azim dar Maghrib. Sulaymon alayhi-s-salom az bod pursid az aja'ibi dunyo. Vayro khabar kard az qal'ai Qatron, ki onro bino kard Shis ibni Odam alayhi-s-salom ba sanghoi azim va qatron ba joyi gil. Va dar on jo sanameast az zabarjad. Sulaymon (a) devro khond, nomi vay Faqtas, bifarmud, ki on qal'aro barkanad va biovarad. Dev onro biovard, bar dush girifta va pesh-i Sulaymon (a) biniod...*” [6, p.220]. – *And the Fortress of Qatrān is a great city in the Maghreb. Prophet Solomon (peace be upon him) asked the wind about the wonders of the world. The wind informed him about the Fortress of Qatrān, which was built by Seth, the son of Adam (peace be upon him), using enormous stones and pitch instead of clay. Inside it there was an idol made of beryl. Solomon (peace be upon him) summoned a demon named Faqtas and ordered him to dismantle that fortress and bring it to him. The demon brought it, carrying it on his shoulders, and placed it before Solomon.*

Конец формы

8. Holonymic objects as defensive structures and refuge for historical figures. It is well established that the primary function of medieval castles was protection and defense, as they served as reliable shelters for nobility and the general population against enemies and invaders. These large-scale constructions were

designed in accordance with the military technologies of their time and reflect a deep understanding of the art of warfare and defense. Castles were typically built in strategic locations, including hilltops, riverbanks, trade crossroads, and border zones. Such placement ensured effective territorial control and made it difficult for enemies to approach. High walls, strong towers, and deep moats formed significant obstacles for attacking armies.

The architecture and layout of castles were primarily focused on defense. Thick stone walls were capable of withstanding siege attacks, while narrow arrow slits allowed archers to shoot without exposing themselves. Drawbridges and large fortified gates provided additional layers of security. Inside the castles, provisions were made to withstand prolonged sieges, including residential quarters, military barracks, food storage facilities, and armories. Thus, castles functioned not only as physical shelters but also as symbols of political authority and power. For the surrounding population, the castle represented a place of safety and refuge, to which they could turn in the event of an attack: *“Va bidon, ki dar Yaman az jum-lai qal’aho qal’ayi Masone’ ast, joye mani’. Va hargiz bar on zafar nayofstand az balandie, ki hast. To ruzgori Kisro Aparvez”* [6, p.242]. – *And know that in Yemen, among the fortresses, there is the fortress of Masone’, a strongly fortified and inaccessible place. No one was ever able to conquer it because of its great height, until the time of Khosrow Aparvez.*

9. Causes of the emergence of holonymic objects. Medieval castles. In addition to serving as military structures, administrative centers, and symbols of social status and power, also had an economic dimension, which is reflected in their frequent construction near important trade routes, rivers, or resource-rich areas. The construction of castles could also be associated with religious and spiritual motives. Some castles were built near sacred places and combined defensive functions with the support of religious life. In addition, smaller castles could be constructed by wealthy individuals as commemorative structures dedicated to deceased relatives, loved ones, or ancestors: *“To ba hadde, ki kalimahoi hikmat bar dari qal’aho nabishtand va bar sahroho, chunon ki ba darvozai Kuyravan va bar qal’ayi Haramon va bar suri Samarqand va bar safhi Arvand va maqsudashon on bud, ki to nomashon mukhallad buvad”* [6, p.25]. – *To such an extent that words of wisdom were inscribed on the gates of fortresses and on open plains, such as at the gate of Kuyravan, the fortress of Haramon, the wall of Samarkand, and the plain of Arvand. Their purpose was that their names might remain eternal.*

10. Holonymic objects as direct sites of historical events. Castles are living witnesses to numerous historical events that have shaped the course of history. These large structures served as centers of political power, venues for important political meetings, battles, and diplomatic negotiations, preserving within their walls the memory of successive centuries. Holonyms played a

key role in medieval military conflicts. Castles functioned as centers of political and social life, where the fate of states was often decided, and important agreements and alliances were concluded in their halls. They frequently hosted coronations, royal weddings, and other significant ceremonies that influenced the further development of regions and peoples. Through the history of castle inhabitants, it is possible to trace changes in political and cultural traditions, as well as the development of arts and crafts. These medieval administrative and geographical structures, in addition to symbolizing power and authority, also preserve the historical memory of former states and systems of governance, as they reflect military heroism, political decisions, and cultural transformations. The historical significance of castles and fortresses in the sources under study is described as follows: "*Va rūzi seyum hojib bar nishastu nazduku qal'a raft va pil bo madh on jo burdandu payghom dod, ki farmon chunon ast, ki «amirro ba qal'ayi Mandesh burda oyad, to on jo neku doshtatar boshad va hojib biyoyad bo lashkare, ki dar payi qal'a muqim ast, ki hojibro bo on mardum, ki bo vay ast, bo muhimme boyad raft»*" [16, p.93]. – *On the third day, the chamberlain (hajib) mounted and went near the fortress, and they brought the elephant there with praise. A message was delivered that the order was as follows: "The emir should be taken to the fortress of Mandesh, so that he may be kept there in better conditions, and the chamberlain should come with the army stationed at the base of the fortress, for it is necessary to proceed on an important mission with those people who are with him"*.

11. Holonyms as historically significant sites designated for imprisonmen.

Despite functioning as residences of rulers, medieval castles often also served as prisons and detention facilities. Although castles are commonly associated with prestige and protection, historically many of them were used as places for the confinement of enemies, criminals, and political prisoners. First of all, castles were constructed with a strong emphasis on security not only from external threats but also from internal escape attempts. Thick walls, dark and narrow underground chambers, and windowless rooms made such structures particularly suitable for the detention of captives. Imprisonment within castles represented one of the most effective forms of punishment, as escape from such heavily fortified structures was virtually impossible. Castles were frequently used to isolate important political prisoners. Detainees were held in separate towers or underground cells, where their ability to resist or communicate was significantly limited. Conditions in castle prisons are well documented in the memoirs and accounts of political prisoners.

It should also be noted that prison castles were not used solely for punitive purposes; they also served as venues for negotiations and prisoner exchanges. Medieval castles thus reflected the severity of political power, struggles for control, and the fate of individuals confined behind their fortified walls.

The perception of castles as both symbols of strength and protection and as places of suffering and confinement is also clearly reflected in the sources under study: “*Va Khojaro chandon khidmat karda bud dar roh, ki az hadd bigzaum va az vay muhtashamtar dar on ruzgar az ahli qalam kas nabud va Khoja Abdurrazzoqro, pisari Khojai Buzurg Ahmad-i Hasan, ki ba qal’ati Nannahana mavquf bud. Qal’ayi Nandana dar Panjob voqe’ bud*” [16, p.158]. – *And he had served the vizier so much on the journey that it went beyond measure, and in that time there was no one more distinguished among the people of the pen than him. He also (mentions) Khwaja Abdurrazzaq, the son of the great Khwaja Ahmad Hasan, who was held in the fortress of Nannahana. The fortress of Nandana was located in Punjab.*

From the analysis of the aforementioned historical objects, it becomes evident that castles were not merely military constructions, but also important administrative and geographical centers that ensured territorial control, supported political authority, and contributed to the formation of early state structures. Their historical role extends beyond defense and reflects a complex interaction of political, geographical, and social relations. At the same time, medieval castles represent outstanding works of engineering and architecture that demonstrate a high level of technical knowledge, creative approaches, and strategic thinking. They remain significant monuments of history and art. It has been established that in the Middle Ages, castle construction also incorporated astronomical relations, reflecting the integration of science, art, and the belief systems of contemporary society. These fortifications were not only military structures but also symbols of cosmic order, harmony, and authority, designed in accordance with natural and celestial principles. In addition, a special category of architectural structures was developed for recreational purposes, combining the functions of a residence, palace, and fortified headquarters. The process of castle construction in the medieval period reflects a combination of financial resources, political will, and contemporary technical knowledge. The use of mythological castles in the Middle Ages, in addition to their architectural significance, represents a synthesis of cultural symbols, history, imagination, and popular beliefs. Through these structures, it becomes possible to better understand the spiritual worldview and intellectual thought of people of that era. Overall, terms such as *qasr*, *qal’a*, *hisor*, *hisn*, and *dizh* denoted regional defensive centers that played a key role in territorial protection and governance.

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科尔涅·丘科夫斯基作品的塔吉克语译本中的双关语和词语创造
**PUNS AND WORD CREATION IN TRANSLATIONS OF KORNEY
CHUKOVSKY'S WORKS INTO TAJIK**

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摘要：本文探讨了科尔涅·丘科夫斯基作品塔吉克语译本中双关语和作者新造词的翻译特点。本研究的意义在于，当代翻译研究日益关注语言游戏翻译的挑战，以及儿童文学领域俄塔翻译实践研究的不足。本文重点分析了丘科夫斯基作品中营造喜剧效果的语言手法，以及译者在塔吉克语译本中呈现这些手法的策略。研究揭示了主要的语言游戏类型，包括双关语、偶喻、拟声词和不寻常的构词法。研究发现，译者运用了多种改编、补偿、替换和中和策略来保留原文的艺术表现力。研究结论表明，在翻译丘科夫斯基的儿童诗歌和童话时，实现功能对等往往比逐字逐句地还原原文语言形式更为重要。该研究成果可应用于文学翻译、比较文学研究和跨文化交际理论等领域。

关键词：儿童文学，翻译研究，语言游戏，双关语，构词法，科尔涅·丘科夫斯基，塔吉克语，文学翻译，儿童诗歌，跨文化交际。

Abstract. *This article examines the features of translating puns and authorial neologisms in the translations of Korney Chukovsky's works into the Tajik language. The relevance of this study stems from the growing interest of contemporary translation studies in the challenges of translating linguistic play, as well as the insufficiently explored Russian-Tajik translation practices in the domain of children's literature. Special attention is given to the analysis of linguistic devices that create the comic effect in Chukovsky's works, as well as to the strategies for their rendering in the Tajik translation. The study revealed the main types of linguistic play, including puns, occasionalisms, onomatopoeia, and unusual word-formation constructions. The research found that translators employ various strategies of adaptation, compensation, substitution, and neutralization to preserve the artistic expressiveness of the original. It is concluded that achieving functional equivalence in the translation of Chukovsky's children's poetry and fairy tales is often*

deemed more important than the literal reproduction of the original linguistic form. The research findings can be applied in the areas of literary translation, comparative literature studies, and intercultural communication theory.

Keywords: *children's literature, translation studies, language play, pun, word formation, Korney Chukovsky, Tajik language, literary translation, children's poetry, intercultural communication.*

Children's literature occupies a special place in the system of literary translation, as it is oriented not only toward transmitting information but also toward forming the child's linguistic, aesthetic, and cultural competence. One of the most challenging objects of translation is works based on wordplay, humor, and word formation. In this regard, the works of Korney Chukovsky hold significant scholarly interest.

Korney Ivanovich Chukovsky (1882–1969) was a writer, translator, and literary critic. Through self-education, he independently learned English and French using self-study guides and books and translated foreign literary works. Thanks to Korney Ivanovich, readers became familiar with the works of Rudyard Kipling, Mark Twain, Oscar Wilde, and English folk songs.

Chukovsky's poetic tales and poems are characterized by a high degree of linguistic expressivity. The author actively employs occasional word formations, onomatopoeia, rhymed playful constructs, and elements of verbal absurdism. These features specifically account for the difficulties in translating the author's works into other languages.

Despite numerous studies dedicated to Chukovsky's oeuvre and issues in children's literature translation, the problem of rendering linguistic play in Tajik translations remains insufficiently researched. This underlines the relevance of the present study.

The aim of the article is to identify the features of transmitting puns and authorial word formation in Tajik translations of Korney Chukovsky's works and to determine the most common translation strategies.

In modern linguistics, language play is understood as the deliberate use of linguistic resources to create an unusual artistic or comic effect. Puns based on lexical ambiguity, phonetic similarity, or the unexpected juxtaposition of different meanings hold a particular significance.

According to Dirk Delabastita, translating wordplay is one of the most complex challenges in literary translation, as it requires preserving both the form and function of the text simultaneously.

From Eugene Nida's perspective, the translator's main objective is to achieve dynamic equivalence—that is, to produce in the translation's reader an effect comparable to that experienced by the original audience.

This principle gains particular importance in children's literature, since a child perceives the text primarily through emotion and imagery.

In Chukovsky's works, language play is one of the key elements of the author's artistic system.

In the fairy tale 'The Mix-Up', the comic effect is created by disrupting the usual associations between objects and actions:

The piglets meowed:

Meow, meow!

The humorous effect arises from the mismatch between the image of the animal and the sound it produces.

When translating such fragments into the Tajik language, the primary task is to preserve the absurdity of the situation. In most cases, translators employ functional replacement, conveying not the literal form of the utterance but its comic effect.

Thus, the translation is aimed at the child reader's perception and at preserving the playful nature of the text.

A distinctive feature of Chukovsky's works is the active use of authorial neologisms.

The most well-known example is the title of the fairy tale 'Moydodyr.' This word constitutes a complex neologistic formation that combines the meaning of an action with a characterization of the character.

The translator faces the simultaneous necessity to solve several tasks:

- preserve the uniqueness of the name;
- convey its semantics;
- ensure comprehensibility for a child audience;
- maintain the comic effect.

In such cases, various strategies may be employed:

1. transliteration;
2. calquing;
3. creation of a new occasional word formation using the means of the Tajik language;
4. semantic adaptation.

Practice shows that literal reproduction of the author's neologisms does not always guarantee preservation of the artistic effect.

Onomatopoeic constructions are extensively represented in Chukovsky's children's poetry:

Quack-quack-quack!

Oink-oink-oink!

Phonetic play serves not only an artistic but also a cognitive function, facilitating the development of a child's speech perception.

When translating into Tajik, difficulties arise due to differences in national traditions for conveying words and objects unfamiliar to the Tajik reader; thus,

translators must introduce a national color familiar within the Tajik linguistic worldview. This strategy allows preserving the communicative orientation of the text and its playful function.

As an example, one can cite the translation of a passage from the well-known work by K. Chukovsky's «Doctor Aybolit», which attracted considerable interest from translators Nariman Bakozoda in 1984 and Ato Mirhodzha in 2023.

Korney Chukovsky:

*И прибежала зайчиха
И закричала: «Ай, ай!
Мой зайчик попал под трамвай!
Мой зайчик, мой мальчик
Попал под трамвай!
Он бежал по дорожке,
И ему перерезало ножки,
И теперь он больной и хромым,
Маленький зайчика мой!»*

Translation by Nariman Bakizoda:

*Гириста Заргӯш омад:
«Э, вай-вой! Э, вай-вой!
Писарчаи моро зад
Тирамвой! Тирамвой!
Пешо-пеши тирамвой
Давид он балоча!
Чудо бишуд дар он ӯой
Балочаам аз поча!»*

В слезах прибежала Зайчиха: «Ой, ой, ой! Нашего мальчика сбил трамвай! Трамвай! Наш егоза перебежал дорогу трамваю, и на месте наш егоза лишился ноги!» (our translation)

Ato Mirhodzha narrates this incident in a more tragic manner:

*Ин дам Харгӯшақбону
Зад назди духтур зону,
Афгонкунон гуфто вай:
«Бачаамро зад трамвай!
Бачам аз раҳ мегузашт,
Омад трамвай ба шаст,
Пояки ўро бурид...»*

“В это время пришла Госпожа Зайчиха, бросилась на колени перед доктором, громко плача, сказала: «Моего мальчика сбил трамвай!. Мой мальчик переходил дорогу, и трамвай на высокой скорости переехал через его ножку...» (our translation)

Each translator rendered this ‘transport incident,’ i.e., the ‘accident,’ according to their own interpretation. In Nariman Bakozoda’s translation, we understand that the culprit is the little hare – a mischievous character who likely crossed the road at an unauthorized place. However, in A. Mirhodzha’s translation, it is apparent that the culprit of this accident is the tram driver; the tram was moving at high speed (бо шаст омад) and ran over the little hare, thereby depriving it of its leg. In the original, the text simply relates the incident in which the little hare was injured.

N. Bakozoda and A. Mirhodzha attempted to convey this incident to children with a cautionary message, so that the child would understand that crossing in front of a vehicle is dangerous and can cause injury or even result in the loss of a leg.

The translation of the word tram proved to be particularly interesting. Indeed, translating terms such as bus, trolleybus, tram, and tractor into Tajik poses certain difficulties, since the names of such modes of transport are not directly translatable into the Tajik language. However, it is noteworthy that Nariman Bakozoda rendered the word «трамвай» as «тирамвой». It appears that the translator did this intentionally to rhyme with the interjections «Э, вай-вой!».

Regarding the word doctor, the translators use the term «духтур», although the Tajik language has the word «табиб». Additionally, the translators did not translate the word «whale», even though in Tajik the whale is translated as наҳанг. Translations of these words can be found in the translation texts.

Shark Karakula K. Chukovsky has become a major figure among translators. A. Mirhodzha calls it Қароқул- наҳанги хап, i.e., the silent whale Karakul, whereas Nariman Bakozoda refers to it as «наҳанги аррадандон» – a toothed whale (a whale with saw-like teeth).

It should be noted that A. Mirhodzha preserved all the place names where Doctor Aybolit rushed to save the animals: Zanzibar, Calahor, Sahara, Mount Fernando-Po, Limpopo, Africa, Kilimanjaro.

Also A. Mirhodzha used the word ‘арғушт’: ‘Аз шодӣ рафтанд арғушт’ – From joy, they started dancing (our translation). ‘Арғушт’ is a word from a local dialect, more commonly used in Uzbek; it is of Turkic origin. In Tajik, the word ‘рақс’ is used. Here, it is also evident that the translator attempted to use this word to rhyme with ‘Шугурчаҳои қачпушт’ (Hunchbacked camel calves).

Nariman Bakozoda, in his work, shortened Doctor Aybolit’s route, listing only: Africa, the Kalahari, Mount Fernando-po, Limpopo.

Doctor Aybolit received his little patients sitting under a tree; in A. Mirhodzha’s version, Doctor Aybolit was situated «зери дарахти чормағз» (under a walnut tree), while in Nariman Bakozoda’s version he was «...зери бед» (under a willow...).

Doctor Aybolit was awaited in Limpopo by Hippo-po, sitting under a palm tree. Mirhodzha also designated the waiting place as « дар зери наҳли хурмо»

(under the date palm). At Nariman Bakozoda's, Aybolit's arrival was awaited by the seaside.

Korney Chukovsky also includes a tree such as the oak:

А малютки бегемотики

Ухватились за животики

И смеются, заливаются —

Так что дубы сотрясаются.

If we are precise about this word, it is known that oaks grow in the northern part of Africa: in Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, and Libya. K. Chukovsky transferred this type of tree to the hot part of Africa, to the fairy-tale Limpopo.

And of course, the most important question is what Doctor Aybolit used to treat the animals.

K. Chukovsky's Aybolit gives the little animals:

И всем по порядку

Даёт шоколадку,

И каждого гоголем,

Каждого моголем...

Гоголем-моголем потчует.

Nariman Bakizoda's Aybolit:

Дод ба баҳмут

Чаккаву қурут.

Бар наҳангакон

Чақ-чақи хандон

Баҳри калламӯш-

Резини калӯш...

Бар ҳама бидод

Ҳалво, ҳандалак,

Аз қафои он

себу сумалак.

“He gave the hippopotamus kefir and kurut (salted balls made from hardened kefir), gave the shark chak-chak (fried dough sticks coated in honey); For the rat, he brought rubber galoshes...; Gave everyone halva, handalak (small melons) and after them apples and sumalak (a traditional spring dish made from sprouted wheat). (our translation)

Aybolit A. Mirhodzha gave the animals medicine for treatment:

...ба ҳар як бачча

Дода ӯ қанду кулча

Чун дид табашон баланд

Доруяшон дод якчанд....

Дору ниҳоду марҳам...

Каждому малышу

Дал он сахар и пряник

Как увидел, что температура высока

Дал несколько лекарств...

Смазал лекарствами и мазью... (our translation)

As we see, A. Mirhodzha approached the treatment of the animals more realistically; his Aybolit primarily gave them medicines, treating them not only with sweets but also with medicines and ointments.

Nariman Bakozoda enumerated the most delicious national sweets and fruits as medicines. These ‘medicines’ symbolically represent spring in folk understanding; they are sweet and flavorful.

The analysis of Tajik translations of Chukovsky’s works allows for the identification of several principal strategies:

- complete preservation – applied in cases where language play can be reproduced by means of the Tajik language without substantial loss;

- substitution – the Russian language play is replaced by a comparable Tajik construction that elicits a similar emotional response;

- compensation - an artistic effect lost in one place is compensated for in another part of the text;

- adaptation - a playful element is transformed taking into account the cultural and linguistic characteristics of the Tajik reader;

- neutralization - applied in cases where preserving the wordplay proves impossible.

The most productive strategies in children’s translation are adaptation and compensation, as they ensure the preservation of the communicative effect of the original text.

The study showed that pun and authorial word formation are essential elements of Korney Chukovsky’s artistic system. Their translation into the Tajik language involves a number of difficulties arising from differences between linguistic systems and national-cultural traditions.

The most common methods of transferring language play are adaptation, substitution, and compensation. In most cases, translators aim to preserve not the formal structure of the original, but its functional effect on the children’s audience.

The results obtained confirm that in the translation of Chukovsky’s works, achieving an equivalent artistic and emotional effect is more important than the literal transmission of the linguistic form of the text. Further research may focus on studying other aspects of the translation of Russian children’s literature into Tajik and on developing a more detailed typology of translation solutions.

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科学和人文认知术语改进和细化的基本原则
**BASIC PRINCIPLES FOR THE IMPROVEMENT AND
REFINEMENT OF THE TERMINOLOGY IN SCIENTIFIC AND
HUMANITARIAN COGNITION**

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摘要：本文探讨了如何克服因“双重”使用（即科学术语和日常用语的双重使用）而导致的不准确性问题。这种不准确性阻碍了对研究对象的深入理解和对其本质的揭示。文章讨论了五个分析理论原则，这些原则为在科学和人文理论研究中运用现有术语和概念体系以及开发新的术语和概念体系提供了方法论基础。

关键词：科学和人文认知，自然语言和理论语言，术语和词汇，术语学，术语分析的理论原则

Abstract. *The article considers the problem of overcoming those inaccuracies that are associated with the “double” – scientific and casual – use of both special terms and natural language words and that creates the obstacles for deeper insight into the studied object and the disclosure of its essence. Five theoretical principles of analysis are discussed in the article which serve as a methodological basis for the use of existing and the development of new terminological and conceptual apparatus used in the process of carrying out scientific and humanitarian theoretical research.*

Keywords: *scientific and humanitarian cognition, natural and theoretical languages, terms and words, terminology, theoretical principles of terminology's analysis*

The creation, improvement and refinement of the terminological and conceptual apparatus for describing the studied object is one of the main tasks of theoretical cognition.

Overcoming those inaccuracies that are associated with the “double” – scientific and everyday – use of both special terms and natural language words creates the conditions for deeper insight into the studied object and the disclosure of its essence.

Cognition in natural sciences strive for the maximum possible use of special terminology, mathematics and artificial languages to describe the objects under study

and express the knowledge gained in order to eliminate ambiguity and everyday meanings of natural language words. However, as scientific knowledge develops, internal scientific disagreements may arise about the meanings of various terms and the content of the concepts denoted by these terms. The improvement of the terminological and conceptual apparatus of scientific research involves the elimination of such differences to ensure the unity of scientific language and the accuracy of perception of scientific information by all members of the scientific community.

Unlike the mathematized and formalized fields of natural science knowledge, humanitarian knowledge develops on the basis of natural languages, which inevitably leads to the identification of special (terminological) and everyday meanings of the words used. This happens because the existence of society and man as a subject of culture is reflected in the everyday consciousness of people, regardless of the development of specialized branches of humanitarian knowledge. And natural language captures precisely those meanings of words that arise in everyday life and communication.

Specialized humanitarian knowledge cannot neglect the everyday meanings of those words that are used in theoretical research, since these meanings reflect the real characteristics of socio-cultural existence. However, the inevitability of the identification of natural and theoretical languages leads to the fact that the analysis of the content of terms and concepts of humanitarian knowledge must be carried out constantly and never loses its relevance.

In order for the analysis of terms and concepts to meet the requirements of theoretical research, it is necessary to understand and formulate the principles that will underlie this analysis. The principles of theoretical research determine the analysis of specific terms and concepts, since they contain knowledge about the features of the studied object and the methods of its research, which is obtained as a result of the previous development of cognition. The content of the principles is not universal, but is derived from those specific historical structures (worldviews, research paradigms, fundamental theoretical models, etc.) that determine the theoretical activity of the subject of cognition. Whatever the content of the principles, it is not deducible within the framework of a given study. On the contrary, logical rules require the derivation of all other statements of a given theoretical study from the principles that underlie it.

Thus, principles are the foundations on which theoretical reasoning is based.

The question of which principles should be used as the basis for the study of terms and concepts of humanitarian knowledge can be considered not only the most important, but also the most difficult. On the one hand, any researcher is free to choose the principles of his analysis. On the other hand, the choice of principles that do not correspond to the already known features of cognition or violate the laws of logic makes it impossible to clarify terminology and analyze the content of concepts.

This article discusses five principles of theoretical analysis of scientific and humanitarian terminology.

The first principle. *Ideal images (thoughts, ideas) and material (linguistic) forms of their expression belong to different spheres of reality.*

According to the first principle, thought as an ideal product of thinking belongs to subjective reality, i.e. to the consciousness of the cognizing subject, and language as a system of material signs (oral, written, gestural, pictorial, etc.) belongs to objective reality, which is outside the consciousness of the cognizing subject.

Linguistics and semiotics are engaged in the study of linguistic – material – forms of expression of thought; the study of the form and content of thought itself is a matter of logic, epistemology and methodological sections of certain branches of natural science, social and humanitarian knowledge.

The second principle. *It is necessary to distinguish in the meanings of natural and theoretical language words two aspects: referential and semantic.*

According to the second principle, the meaning of a word (sign, term) has two aspects: referential and semantic. The referential aspect of the meaning of a word (term) reveals the relationship between the word (term) and the object that is designated by the given word (term) and which is called the denotata, or referent, of the given word (term). The semantic aspect of the meaning of a word (term) is related to the understanding of the designated object itself (denotata/referent).

The connection between language and thinking is such that a word, say, “atom” or “wave”, can have the same denotata/referent, but different meanings, i.e. denote different ideas about an object. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the difference between the processes of studying the objects of reality themselves (natural or socio-cultural) and the study of the lexical meanings of words in everyday language. Thus, as a result of the discovery of new facts about the nature of waves, there has been a change not in the lexical meaning of the noun “wave” (“a moving bulge or shaft on the surface of a liquid”), but in scientific knowledge about the nature of this phenomenon [4].

It follows that, knowing the lexical (linguistic) meanings of words, we cannot answer the question: what is the essence of the object (phenomenon, process, etc.) of reality that this word denotes? But even in the case when we do not identify the lexical meanings of the word with ideas about the structure of the denotata/referent of this word, it must be borne in mind that the lexical meanings of natural language words change if these words are used as terms of theoretical languages.

The third principle. *The meanings of the same words in natural and theoretical languages are not identical to each other.*

According to the third principle, the meanings of words as elements of a natural language are not identical to the meanings of the same words as terms of a

theoretical language. In order to obtain the status of terms, natural language words must be unambiguously interpreted within the framework of a particular concept [2].

If we turn to humanitarian knowledge, we will find that the enumeration of the various meanings of natural language words used in research has become an integral part of all humanitarian disciplines and is considered by humanities scholars themselves as an expression of the specifics of humanitarian research. Meanwhile, the ambiguity of the terms does not allow us to differentiate the contexts of their use into those in which different objects of reality are discussed, and those in which different models (concepts) of the same object are discussed. The lack of such differentiation, characteristic of many humanitarian studies, leads to the incommensurability of arguments relating to different objects of reality, but referred to by the same term [1]. To avoid such incommensurability, the fourth principle is introduced.

The fourth principle. *The meaning of a theoretical language term is determined by the definition of this term, which introduces both the referent/denotata of the term (theoretical object) and its conceptual meaning.*

According to the fourth principle, the transformation of a natural language word into a scientific term requires its definition, which introduces both the referent/denotata of the term (theoretical object) and its conceptual meaning. In other words, any term of theoretical knowledge means that and only that, which is referred to in the definition of this term.

Each definition has its own referent/denotata, i.e. the object of reality that is designated by this term. The introduction of the same term by at least two different definitions requires either proof of the identity of the definitions, or recognition of the non-identity of the referent/denotata (object), since different definitions cannot have the same referent.

The application of the fourth principle is of particular importance in humanitarian knowledge [5].

It is a mistake to believe that by using the same term, but defining it in many different ways, we thereby highlight only certain aspects of studying the same referent (object). Those who define values as “any phenomena significant to a person” and those who define values as “the ultimate goals and meanings of human life” study different objects that act as referents of the same term “values”. And the differences in definitions cannot be presented as conceptual, because the introduction of a theoretical object through different definitions requires justification that we are talking about the same referent (object).

The use of the same term does not mean, by itself, the identity of the reference, i.e. the identity of the object under study. In order to establish the identity of the referent (object), it is necessary to prove the identity of the definitions. However, neither empirically, nor logically, nor semantically is the term defined as “any

phenomena significant to a person” identical to the term defined as “the ultimate goals and meanings of human life”.

When it comes to natural language words, we can rely on practical human interaction with the material objects of the natural world. It is the practical interaction with the world that clearly indicates different objects of reality, designated by the same word. In case of difficulties in understanding or translating into another language, in order to clarify the lexical meaning of a word, a person can always switch to “pointing by a finger” or to an image of the object that the word means.

The definition of referents of humanitarian cognition terms is a process that is fundamentally different from the definitions of referents of natural science terms. The terms of humanitarian cognition denote not sensually perceived, but abstract objects, the specificity of which lies in the fact that they cannot receive an empirical interpretation in the process of scientific experimental or communicative practice. The humanities scholar does not rely on every day or scientific experimental practice and cannot point to or depict the object under study. The field of meaning of humanitarian terms is determined solely by the definition by which the term is introduced into the study.

Why is it that when humanitarians define the same term in different ways, they are sure that they are talking about the same object?

The basis of this erroneous opinion is the identification of linguistic and cognitive aspects of the thinking process. Since the content of most concepts of humanitarian knowledge is expressed in natural languages, the enumeration of the meanings of the corresponding words in a particular natural language and the practice of everyday communication expresses the desire of humanitarians to create by linguistic means a “general universe of reasoning” for all researchers containing a common reference to the objects they study.

The illusion of intuitive clarity of the referencing of terms of humanitarian cognition arises because human existence itself, of which language is an integral element, is perceived as a common referent of all terms used in the process of cognition of any aspects of this existence. Humanitarians do not take into account that the context of being, common to all subjects of cognition, ensures the invariance of the meaning of only universal categories of thinking, but not the terms of natural science or humanitarian research.

The invariance of lexical meanings of natural language words does not lead to the invariance of referential meanings of theoretical terms. This happens because, unlike the terms of natural science theories and like the terms of mathematical theories, the terms of humanitarian cognition do not describe the object under study, but define it. This means that by defining a particular term of humanitarian knowledge, we not only define the scope of its object (referential) meaning, but also define the essence (content, structure) of the object under study.

The fifth principle. *The semantic aspect of the meaning of the theoretical term is the concept of the studied object of reality, expressed in the definition.*

According to the fifth principle, the semantic aspect of the meaning of a theoretical term is the concept of the studied object of reality, expressed in the definition. In other words, each definition of a theoretical term in humanitarian knowledge is a “collapsed concept” of the referent (object), which makes it impossible to distinguish between the reference and the meaning of the term.

Any object has only one essence, which can be reflected in only one concept, although this concept itself is the result of a long development of cognition [3]. In the process of this development various, sometimes opposite, approaches to understanding the essence of the studied object are carried out, various hypotheses about its essential features are put forward. But this does not mean that there can be several concepts of the same object. On the contrary, the presence of many approaches and hypotheses indicates that the concept has not yet been formed, that the essence of the object has not yet been recognized. But in any case, the linguistic form of expression of the concept in the definition is not identical to the content of the concept itself.

Thus, the principles of the analysis of terms and concepts of theoretical knowledge formulated by us serve as a methodological basis for the use of existing and the development of new terminological and conceptual apparatus used in the process of carrying out theoretical, especially – humanitarian, research.

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当代塔吉克哲学家论伊本·西那哲学遗产的作用和重要性
**CONTEMPORARY TAJIK PHILOSOPHERS ON THE ROLE AND
IMPORTANCE OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL LEGACY OF IBN SINA**

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摘要：本文分析了当代塔吉克哲学家研究阿布·阿里·伊本·西那（阿维森纳）哲学遗产的方法。文章考察了塔吉克学术界对阿维森纳研究的主要方向，涵盖形而上学、逻辑学、人类学、伦理学、科学哲学以及这位伟大思想家的医学遗产等领域。文章重点关注了M. Dinorshoeva、K. Olimova、M. Rakhimova和Yu. Nuralieva等学者的著作，他们为在当代塔吉克人文学科框架下诠释伊本·西那的哲学思想做出了重要贡献。研究表明，阿维森纳的哲学遗产不仅被视为全球知识文化的重要组成部分，而且也是民族哲学意识、文化认同和科学世界观形成的基础要素。结论认为，伊本·西那的思想对于当代社会的哲学、科学、教育和精神文化的发展仍然具有重要意义。

关键词：伊本·西那（阿维森纳），塔吉克哲学，阿维森纳学，哲学遗产，穆索·迪诺尔肖耶夫，哲学人类学，形而上学，理性主义，科学方法论，民族认同。

Abstract. *This article analyzes the approaches of contemporary Tajik philosophers to the study of the philosophical heritage of Abu Ali Ibn Sino (Avicenna). It examines the primary directions of Tajik scholarship on Avicenna, encompassing investigations into metaphysics, logic, anthropology, ethics, the philosophy of science, and the medical legacy of the great thinker. Particular emphasis is placed on the works of M. Dinorshoeva, K. Olimova, M. Rakhimova, and Yu. Nuralieva and other scholars who have made significant contributions to the interpretation of the philosophical ideas of Ibn Sino within the framework of contemporary Tajik humanities. The study demonstrates that the philosophical heritage of Avicenna is considered not only a paramount component of global intellectual culture but also a foundational element in the formation of national philosophical consciousness, cultural identity, and scientific worldview. It is concluded that the ideas of Ibn Sino*

remain relevant for the advancement of philosophy, science, education, and the spiritual culture of contemporary society.

Keywords: *Ibn Sino (Avicenna), Tajik philosophy, Avicennology, philosophical heritage, Muso Dinorshoev, philosophical anthropology, metaphysics, rationalism, scientific methodology, national identity.*

In the 21st century, humanity confronts profound worldview challenges connected to a crisis of spiritual values, cultural fragmentation, and the proliferation of utilitarian thinking. Under these circumstances, the importance of recourse to the classical philosophical heritage, capable of providing orientations for the understanding of contemporary processes, increases.

One of the paramount achievements of global intellectual culture is the Tajik-Persian philosophical tradition, which developed at the confluence of Islamic, ancient Greek, Indian, and ancient Iranian thought. A distinguished position within this tradition is held by Abu Ali Ibn Sino (980–1037), known in the European tradition as Avicenna. His philosophical, medical, and natural-scientific treatises have had a profound impact on the development of science and philosophy both in the East and in the West. Ibn Sino represents one of the highest achievements of classical Muslim, Tajik-Persian philosophy and science. In the history of global thought, he occupies a unique position as a philosopher, physician, logician, poet, and natural philosopher. His works, covering numerous disciplines, stand as a compelling testimony to the intellectual flourishing of the Samanid East. Contemporary Tajik scholarship increasingly regards Ibn Sina not only as a historical figure but as an integral part of the national intellectual canon. This is evidenced by the work on the multivolume edition «Abu Ali Ibn Sina (Avicenna) Writings», where the preface highlights the role of his philosophy as the foundation for moral-humanistic and rational thought: «Centuries will pass, hundreds of generations of people will succeed each other on Earth, and humanity will enter a completely new socio-economic, scientific-technological, and cultural-civilizational era.» However, the greatness and glory of Ibn Sina, who kindled the light of reason in the 10th century and sowed the seeds of knowledge on our planet, shall never fade.»[6, 154].

Of particular interest is the evaluation of Ibn Sina's personality in authoritative scientific and encyclopedic references. In the Great Soviet Encyclopedia, he is characterized as an outstanding Tajik philosopher, scholar, and thinker of universal significance. The encyclopedic entry highlights that Ibn Sina's father, Abdullah, was a Tajik from Balkh, while his mother, Sitorabon, originated from the Tajik village of Afshana. These data indicate that in Soviet-period academic literature, Ibn Sina was regarded not only as a prominent representative of medieval science but also as an outstanding figure within the Tajik cultural-philosophical tradition.

The philosophy of Ibn Sina constitutes a comprehensive system of thought founded upon the principles of rational cognition, logical argumentation, and the pursuit of understanding the essence of being. His works on metaphysics, logic, epistemology, and ethics marked a significant phase in the development of medieval philosophy. Particular significance is attributed to the doctrine he developed concerning necessary and possible being, which exerted influence on the subsequent development of both the Islamic and European philosophical traditions.

Contemporary Tajik history regards Ibn Sino as a symbol of the nation's intellectual unity. His name has become a symbol of cultural continuity; it is therefore not accidental that the leading universities and scientific institutions of the country bear his name. Nuriddin Said writes: "Ibn Sino is not only a part of the history of the Tajik people; he is its living foundation." [10, 154]

In the introductory part of the first volume of Abū 'Alī ibn Sīnā (Avicenna) 'Writings' [1], emphasizes that the philosophy of Ibn Sina is a worldview system in which intellect, morality, and empirical practice are harmoniously integrated. 'One of the brilliant thinkers who accumulated in his works the entire wealth of preceding human knowledge and developed all branches of science of his era – logic, philosophy, theology, natural science, mathematics, and medicine – is Abū 'Alī ibn Sīnā.' [6, 7]

Contemporary Tajik researchers regard the heritage of Ibn Sino not only as an object of historical-philosophical analysis but also as a vital component of the national cultural and intellectual legacy. An essential contribution to the study of his philosophical views has been made by M.S. Asimov, A.M. Bogoutdinov, M.D. Dinorshoev, K.O. Olimov, M.H. Rakhimov, N. Saidov, F. Sirodzov, N. Rakhmatulloev, and other scholars. Rakhmatulloev and other researchers

Academician Muso Dinorshoev occupies a prominent position among contemporary Avicennologists, having been one of the first in Tajikistan to undertake a systematic study of the philosophy of Ibn Sino. In his works, he devoted particular attention to the doctrine of essence and existence, issues of metaphysics and cognition, as well as the role of Ibn Sino in the development of Eastern Peripatetic philosophy. According to this scholar, Ibn Sino's philosophy constitutes a dynamic philosophical worldview that maintains its relevance in contemporary contexts.

In his works, Academician Muso Dinorshoev demonstrates that Ibn Sina is a philosopher-encyclopedist of global significance who established a philosophical system encompassing all branches of knowledge of his time, including logic, theoretical philosophy, practical philosophy, mathematics, and metaphysics. In the first chapter, on the basis of indisputable evidence, Dinorshoev successfully argues that Ibn Sina is a genuine son of the Tajik people. In recognition of his contributions to the study and promotion of Ibn Sina's heritage, Academician Muso Dinorshoev was awarded the Abu Ali Ibn Sina Prize in 2013.

Muso Dinorshoev, a pioneer of Tajik philosophical hermeneutics of Ibn Sina, situates him within the context of the Eastern anti-idealist tradition. He underscores the category central to Ibn Sina—the distinction between *мавҷуд* (*wujūd*, existence) and *маъқул* (*ma'qūl*, essence)—which enabled Eastern metaphysics to transcend orthodox religious paradigms. Muso Dinorshoev is a figure of exceptional significance within the Tajik intellectual tradition. His profound analysis of the philosophy of Ibn Sino, along with the integration of Eastern philosophical thought into contemporary scientific discourse, has laid the groundwork for the formation of a national philosophical identity. He not only rediscovered Ibn Sino for Tajikistan but also rendered his ideas pertinent to the 21st century.

M.Kh. Rakhimov made a significant contribution to the study of Ibn Sino's philosophical anthropology. In his works, he treats the human being as the central element of Avicenna's philosophical system, providing an analysis of the doctrines of the soul, intellect, and the moral perfection of the individual. The study indicates that in the philosophy of Ibn Sino, man serves as the connecting link between the material and spiritual worlds, and the path to perfection lies through knowledge, reason, and moral self-improvement.

Ibn Sino occupies a distinguished position in the history of Tajik and global thought. His ideas continue to hold significance for contemporary philosophical and scientific research. Due to the efforts of Tajik scholars including Osimi M.S., Bolttaev M., Bogoutdinov A., Dinorshoev M., Olimov K., Nuraliyev Yu., Rakhimov M., Sirodjev F., Rakhmatulloev N., Mardonov T., Said N., Khudoiddodov F., and Sultanov S. Among others, an original interpretation of Ibn Sino's heritage is being formed in Tajikistan, integrating philosophy, science, culture, and ethics. This renders Ibn Sino not only a legacy of the past but also an inspiring source for the future.

An equally significant area of contemporary Avicennology is the study of the thinker's medical heritage. Yu. Nuraliev regards the medical system of Ibn Sino as a holistic doctrine encompassing medicine, ethics, psychology, and natural philosophy. According to the researcher, many of Avicenna's ideas continue to hold significance even within the framework of contemporary medical practice.

Thus, Avicenna's works become not only objects of scholarly examination but also a living source for the reform of medicine. Modern physicians, when confronted with difficult cases, turn to the Canon—this majestic treasury of wisdom—and primarily, with great hope, appeal to its creator, the eternally living Great Avicenna.[11, 55]

Today, numerous scholars among medical practitioners, including Mansurov Kh.Kh., Mirodzhev G.K., Sharofova M.U., Soatov I.S., Isomiddinov A.I., Babaev A.B., Odinaeva L.E., Gulzoda M., and Kurbanov U., have continued and still continue to engage in research on the medical writings of Avicenna. Regarding the medicine of Ibn Sino, a comprehensive doctoral dissertation could be dedicated to the analysis

of the medical system developed by Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Regrettably, the present article cannot provide an extensive analysis of this issue. Nonetheless, it is undeniable that today the medical heritage of Ibn Sino is extensively studied by Tajik scholars.

Contemporary Tajik philosophers also underscore the importance of Ibn Sino as one of the founders of the rational scientific method. His writings pay significant attention to observation, analysis, and the empirical study of nature. Scholars observe that many of Ibn Sino's ideas anticipated principles of scientific reasoning that were further developed during the Renaissance and the Early Modern period.

The figure of Ibn Sino in the contemporary Tajik philosophical and scientific arena is not a relic of the past, but an active archetype of the scholar-humanist. Contemporary Tajik researchers not only continue interpreting his works but also establish methodological foundations for the application of his ideas in education, science, and moral and intellectual formation. Engagement with the works of Ibn Sino constitutes a path toward the internal revival of Tajik philosophy as an integral part of global intellectual culture.

Ibn Sino is not only a philosopher of the past but also a cultural code of the present era. His interpretation within Tajik humanitarian scholarship functions as a bridge between classical rationalism and contemporary humanistic challenges. His name symbolizes the connecting link among reason, faith, and empirical knowledge. The aspiration of contemporary Tajik thinkers to integrate his ideas into educational, medical, and philosophical practice attests to the enduring vitality of his heritage in the twenty-first century.

Thus, in contemporary Tajik philosophical scholarship, Ibn Sino is regarded not only as an outstanding thinker of the past but also as a crucial source of intellectual and cultural development. His philosophical and scientific heritage remains the subject of active research, fostering the development of national consciousness and reinforcing the connection between classical and contemporary philosophical traditions.

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从跨文化方法论的角度探讨伊本·西那哲学观点的某些方面
**ON SOME ASPECTS OF IBN SINA'S PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS
IN THE LIGHT OF INTERCULTURAL METHODOLOGY**

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摘要。后现代主义关于万物相对性和不存在单一真理的原则已在哲学领域得到巩固，由此催生了多元对话哲学和跨文化方法论，使得对特定思想家的文本和哲学观点进行多元解读成为可能。从这个角度来看，这种假设有助于拓展研究者的能力，使其超越单纯的评注者角色，并促进一种创造性的研究方法，从而能够对前人的哲学思想进行新的理解。这不仅解释了学者们，特别是那些研究伊本·西那著作的学者们，对其哲学观点持有不同立场的原因。然而，作者认为，在科学研究中必须避免走极端：对哲学著作（文本）采取作者式的、创造性的研究方法无疑有助于其焕发活力，带来新的解读，并在新的历史语境中得以体现。然而，对被考察思想家的哲学思想进行过度“革新”或“现代化”的尝试，可能会导致其自身原初思想的消亡。

关键词：哲学，历史哲学研究，分析方法，后现代主义，比较哲学，多元对话哲学，跨文化方法论，诠释学，文本，苏菲主义，理性主义，相对主义，真理，方法论。

Abstract. *Postmodernist principles concerning the relativity of all things and the absence of a single truth have been consolidated within philosophy, resulting in the emergence of the philosophy of polylogue and intercultural methodology, which permit diverse interpretations of the texts and philosophical views of a given thinker. Such an assumption, from this perspective, facilitates the expansion of the researcher's capabilities, surpassing the role of a mere commentator and fostering a creative approach that enables a renewed understanding of the philosophical ideas of preceding thinkers. This, and not only this, explains the diversity of positions held by scholars, particularly those examining the works of Ibn Sina, regarding his philosophical views. However, the author expresses the view that it is necessary to avoid extremes in scientific research: an authorial and creative approach to a philosophical work (text) undoubtedly contributes to its revitalization,*

a new reading, and its actualization in new historical circumstances. However, attempts at excessive “renewal” or “modernization” of the philosophical ideas of the examined thinker may lead to the destruction of his own original ideas.

Keywords: *philosophy, historical-philosophical research, analytical approach, postmodernism, comparative philosophy, philosophy of polylogue, intercultural methodology, hermeneutics, text, Sufism, rationalism, relativism, truth, methodology.*

Abu Ali Ibn Sina is undoubtedly a foremost figure in the global history of philosophy and science, and this fact does not give rise to doubts among the objectively minded scientific-philosophical community. European, Soviet, Iranian, and Arab scholars, particularly in the twentieth century, exhibited significant interest in the oeuvre of this eminent medieval thinker. Consequently, his works were translated into various languages, his philosophical system examined and analyzed, and a substantial number of monographs and articles were published, with numerous dissertations defended. Each of these academic investigations elucidated different facets of Ibn Sina's philosophy, and as is often the case in scholarship, researchers frequently arrived at diverse and sometimes divergent conclusions regarding Ibn Sina's stance on various issues. One of the principal reasons for the divergence of opinions and conclusions among researchers investigating the same issue concerning the philosophical views of Ibn Sina (including his ontological, epistemological, theological, ethical, and other perspectives) lies, in our view, in a subjective factor—specifically, the researcher's own worldview stance, as well as the ideological frameworks established within the respective society. A review of all those who studied Ibn Sina's philosophy in the twentieth century reveals that one of the points on which scholars diverge is the question of the nature of Ibn Sina's 'Eastern philosophy' and the relationship between the mystical-Sufi and rationalist perspectives within his philosophy. Thus, European scholars Louis Gardet and A. M. Schimmel (1) held that it is precisely Ibn Sina's mystico-Sufi views that exhibit originality, as opposed to his rationalistic arguments. By contrast, Soviet researchers—V. V. Sokolov, S. B. Serebryakov, M. T. Stepanyants, and others regarded the philosopher's Sufi views as a 'facade' for his materialistic reasoning (2). The Lebanese scholar Majid Fahri also maintained that by the end of his life Ibn Sina adopted Sufi positions (3), whereas Said Hasan Buroni argued that Ibn Sina's entire philosophical system serves as a justification of his religious views (4). Tajik Soviet researchers of the thinker's legacy – A. Bakhovaddinov, M. Boltaev, and M. Dinorshoev – regarded Ibn Sina as a consistent rationalist (5). Regarding scholarly discourse on Ibn Sina's Sufi perspectives, these were based on analyses of his late works – 'Instructions and Admonitions,' 'On the Soul,' 'On Love,' 'On Prayer,' 'Birds,' 'On Hayy son of Yaqzan,' and 'Eastern Philosophy.' In this article, we do not seek to demonstrate the conflicting viewpoints of

all scholars studying Ibn Sina's philosophy; rather, we only wish to emphasize that such plurality is a natural process in science and, from the standpoint of comparative philosophy, hermeneutics, and intercultural methodology, this diversity of opinions is indeed encouraged.

It should be noted that in Soviet historical-philosophical scholarship, the study of a philosopher's work employed an analytical method extensively described by S.I. Bazhov in his article 'Problems of Methodology in Historical-Philosophical Research.' In this work, he raises issues for historians of philosophy whose resolution is necessary alongside a set of methodological and substantive disciplinary challenges. Bazhov clearly defines the overarching purpose of historical-philosophical research as the empirical and analytical reconstruction of ideological-philosophical phenomena. Concerning the methods of analytical reconstruction of historico-philosophical phenomena, they represent a comprehensive analytical description of the historico-philosophical phenomenon, commencing after the completion of empirical research, and encompassing the study of historico-philosophical literature pertinent to the subject; the historiographical and source-critical dimensions of the investigation are examined. Upon the completion of this stage, the analytical examination of the empirical material begins. S.I. Bazhov outlined the stages of analytical reconstruction of the historico-philosophical system once the necessary empirical data have been gathered: the consideration of sociocultural, axiological, and ideological-theoretical premises of the philosophical doctrine and the questions concerning its genesis; consideration of the premises of the doctrine, that is, the actual study of the totality of the substantive propositions of the doctrine; comparison of the particular philosophical doctrine with related, comparable doctrines in order to formulate new species-specific characteristics of the doctrine, reveal its original aspects, and refine its substantive structure; consideration of the evolution of the doctrine, if such an evolution occurred; determination of the influence of the particular doctrine on other ideological formations; theoretical evaluation of the doctrine, taking into account both its historical and contemporary significance (6;8). According to S.I. Bazhov, 'well-reasoned answers to all the above questions will constitute a comprehensive analytical reconstruction of the historical-philosophical phenomenon' (6;9).

A significant aspect in the process of analytical research is the comparative analysis with previously conducted studies concerning the doctrine of the same thinker. This creates a space for polemics and exchange of views, wherein the philosophical and worldview positions of the studied philosopher are interpreted divergently by scholars. This phenomenon is especially evident under the influence of ideological commitments, as acknowledged by S.I. Bazhov, who argues that ideology and ideological positions impede the researcher from performing an objective and analytical historical-philosophical analysis, citing the dominant

influence of communist ideology that necessitates viewing all socio-humanitarian issues through the lens of Marxist philosophy and the dialectical-materialist method. Tajik historians of philosophy of the Soviet era are well acquainted with the phenomenon whereby materialistic, dialectical, and anti-religious ideas were sought within the views of medieval Muslim philosophers, either out of necessity or inclination. However, to be fair, it should be acknowledged that such perspectives did indeed appear in their teachings, indicating the breadth of their thought even within the strict confines of the prevailing religious worldview. Thus, it is confirmed that even a study of the ideas of the same thinker, conducted within a unified framework of requirements, criteria, and structure, can lead authors to different conclusions, due not only to their subjective features of the cognitive process but also to ideological reasons.

In our view, an example of analytical research on Ibn Sina's philosophy is the work of the well-known Tajik Avicenna scholar M. Dinorshoev, who, rigorously adhering to the aforementioned stages of analytical inquiry, conducting comparative analyses with previously completed studies, and, most importantly, meticulously examining the texts of the thinker's original works, advanced arguments in support of his conclusions precisely on the basis of Ibn Sina's own texts. Thus, rejecting the viewpoints of several scholars regarding Ibn Sina's 'Eastern philosophy' (Guashon, Guter, Garde, Corbin, Ihsan Yarshatir, Qasim Ghani, S. Nasr, et al.), M. Dinorshoev states: "The question of the essence of Ibn Sina's 'Eastern philosophy' ought not to be addressed solely on the basis of assumptions but through a comprehensive study of his works, such as 'Eastern Philosophy' and 'Some Provisions of Eastern Philosophy.'" Only a thorough study of these works, alongside a comparative analysis with Suhrawardi's **Philosophy of Illumination** and Fakhr al-Din al-Razi's **Al-Mabahis al-Mashriqiya**, can illuminate the longstanding debates concerning the nature of Ibn Sina's Eastern philosophy that have persisted for nearly a thousand years (since Suhrawardi—recognized as the founder of the Philosophy of Illumination). M. Dinorshoev, upon examining the issue through primary sources, concludes that "... Ibn Sina's "Eastern philosophy" is neither the Philosophy of Illumination nor Eastern mysticism, but rather constitutes the same Eastern Peripateticism articulated in his works **The Cure**, **The Salvation**, and **Daneshnameh**." Furthermore, M. Dinorshoev advances a series of his own arguments in defense of his position, referring to the works of Ibn Sina, Suhrawardi, Fakhr al-Din al-Razi, and Ghazali (7:52–56).

With regard to European scholars, they likewise conducted their research within the established ideological, scientific, philosophical, and worldview paradigms prevalent in Europe — including philosophical idealism and irrationalism, Eurocentrism in philosophy and science, as well as the developed postmodernism characterized by the credo 'everything is relative and there is no absolute truth.' These

postmodern principles and ideals—whose foundation lies in ontological pluralism and epistemological relativism—have emerged from such European philosophical movements as existentialism, personalism, structuralism, hermeneutics, and others, thereby conditioning a new understanding of the history of philosophy and fostering the development of novel research methodologies.

Consequently, the majority of European scholars studying Ibn Sina's oeuvre have perceived him as a philosopher—an irrationalist—while considering his works of 'Sufi content' to be more original than other writings. Soviet scholars, similarly influenced by ideology, attempted to portray Ibn Sina as an absolute rationalist, while the Sufi motifs in his works were interpreted, as previously noted, as a 'mask' or 'research interest.'

The Russian philosopher A. A. Krotov, in his article 'The Methodology of Contemporary Historical-Philosophical Research in France,' examines the methodologies of historical-philosophical inquiry proposed by French philosophers (incidentally, postmodernism is believed to have originated in France) and emphasizes that for them—specifically Obencka, Vieillard-Baron, and Worms—the central issue in historical-philosophical research is the problem of context. They oppose reductionism and, in interpreting philosophical texts, deliberately maintain a critical distance from various versions of the history of philosophy. A.A. Krotov observes that, according to P. Obenku, research in the field of the history of philosophy during the past 40 years has been conducted within the framework of two methodological principles: 1. the analytical (Anglophone historians of philosophy) and 2. the hermeneutic (European and Latin American historians of philosophy). At the same time, Obenku regrets that there is no connection between these two schools. According to him, the analytical approach, aspiring to scientific objectivity, seeks to minimize the role of the researcher. Regarding the hermeneutic approach, it is the interpreter's duty to capture possible meanings, many of which—being present in the text seemingly independent of the author's intentions—are even more significant than those clearly acknowledged by the author. The rupture between the intended and actual speech enables the interpreter to understand the author better than the author understands themselves" (8;4).

Thus, it follows that the analytical approach in historical-philosophical research aims to reproduce the author's thinking (his philosophical views) as accurately and adequately as possible based on the analysis of his ideas, resulting in the researcher's role being limited solely to reproducing, commenting on, and evaluating the author's thought. Regarding the hermeneutic approach, which also entails a methodological stance toward the interpretation and understanding of the text, as noted by Obenku, it affords the researcher greater opportunities than merely serving as a reproducer and commentator of ideas. In Obenka's understanding, the hermeneutical approach permits the researcher a liberal interpretation of the

text in the service of realizing one's own conceptual flight. That is, the text, in this case philosophical, can act as a 'trigger' for the researcher, generating within him certain 'new' ideas, shaping his own perspective on the problem, and eliciting from his subconscious specific thoughts, feelings, and emotions, thereby stimulating a renewed comprehension of the text and the issue under consideration.

Speaking of the shortcomings of the analytical approach, Obenk asserts: 'The genuine criteria for the comparative evaluation of systems must be different: above all, productivity and effectiveness, the capacity to expand the boundaries of thought, and to create the most effective models.' The value of a philosophical system increases in proportion to the extent of possibilities it opens for thought» (8;6). Consequently, the diversity of opinions concerning the philosophical views of Ibn Sina, as well as those of other philosophers, becomes comprehensible.

In his article 'On the "New" Methods of Studying the History of Russian Philosophy,' the Russian scholar A.V. Malinov also discusses methods such as the method of historico-philosophical reconstruction; the method of reactualization/marginalization of philosophical content; intercultural methodology (philosophy of polylogue). In principle, these methods are not new in themselves, yet their reevaluation is necessary. Thus, the author states that 'historico-philosophical reconstruction is a creative endeavor; it not only introduces new texts into the scholarly discourse but, in essence, creates them.' Intercultural methodology (polylogue) is founded on the principle of equality and complementarity among various philosophical traditions and schools; recognizes the diversity of approaches to attaining truth; presupposes a close interrelation of philosophical thought with the specific culture, society, and worldview that engender it and in which it finds its meaningful actualization (9;6). Furthermore, philosophical polylogue seeks not primarily to reinterpret anew, thereby reactualizing or reviving, but—if necessary—to supplement and elaborate the philosophical ideas and concepts of the past (9;8). Thus, the history of philosophy transcends itself and becomes philosophy in its proper sense. There is no doubt that the recreation, elucidation, commentary, and interpretation of philosophical texts and works represent a creative process. The subject of inquiry unquestionably performs the aforementioned process within the framework of the Self, even when striving for objectivity. A creative approach to research genuinely enables the disclosure of previously unnoticed aspects of the philosophical doctrine of a given thinker, directing the researcher towards the formulation and resolution of new problems grounded in the contemporary context and emerging paradigm.

From our perspective, all the aforementioned approaches and methods of historical-philosophical research are outcomes of postmodern stances, particularly epistemological relativism, which absolutizes the relativity of truth and the conventionality of cognitive content. This implies that each researcher is entitled to

discern varying meanings within the oeuvre of a given thinker, thereby uncovering their own truth. Accordingly, pluralism of opinions concerning the same text or work of a philosopher (in this case, Ibn Sina) is justified and even preferable to the presence of a singular viewpoint that deprives researchers of further reflection, investigation, and the creative liberty of thought. However, we consider it appropriate here to recall the notion of “measure,” the violation of which inevitably leads to extremes. Specifically: restricting the role of the researcher solely within the confines of the text, minimizing their creative engagement, and absolutizing a singular perspective can result in the stagnation of philosophical doctrine, thereby depriving it of relevance in subsequent eras. Conversely, an excessive preoccupation with imposing subjective sensations and thoughts—not a renewed reading but a ‘reworking’ of the text (the philosopher’s doctrine as a whole)—can so distort the original exposition of the author/philosopher as to lead to the ‘death’ of their own doctrine and standpoint.

In conclusion, it should be noted that for a more adequate understanding and interpretation of the ideas of thinkers, including Ibn Sina, it is necessary to thoroughly examine the categorical apparatus they employ—that is, to engage deeply with the content of the concepts they use to articulate their thoughts. Furthermore, the permissible plurality of interpretations in the polemics concerning thinkers’ views must undoubtedly be justified and proven, rather than relying solely on opinion. Existing methods and approaches in historical-philosophical research will be constructive and productive only if they complement, rather than exclude, one another. Accordingly, researchers must move beyond their comfort zones; that is, they should not confine themselves to conventional research methods but apply, ideally modernize, and develop new methods that will advance historical-philosophical studies to a new level and facilitate a «new reading» of philosophical works from various epochs without compromising their original authenticity.

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教育是文化和意义的对话

EDUCATION AS A DIALOGUE OF CULTURES AND MEANINGS

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摘要：本文以文化对话为视角分析语言教育问题。作者认为，语言作为一种图像系统，反映了使用者对周围现实的感知和理解的特征，揭示了特定文化群体成员思维的核心特征。

关键词：对话，语言，知识，文化对话，经验，意义，图像，信息空间，文化群体。

Abstract. *In this article, the issue of language education is analyzed through the lens of cultural dialogue. The authors contend that language, as a system of images, reflects the characteristic features of perception and understanding of the surrounding reality by its speakers, revealing the core traits of the mentality of members of a given cultural group.*

Keywords: *dialogue, language, knowledge, cultural dialogue, experience, meaning, image, information space, cultural groups.*

The issue of education and educational technologies has always been and will remain pressing, since humanity inevitably faces the question of how to convey the experience accumulated by the current generation, how to reconcile it with the experience inherited from previous generations, and how the existing experience will be enriched and developed by future generations. Two globally interconnected questions thus arise: how to evaluate the accumulated experience and by what means to transmit it to subsequent generations. A maximally effective evaluation of the conveyed experience will help determine both the content of the educational material (defining what is conveyed, prioritizing the information transmitted, identifying the unit of transmitted material, etc.) and the methods (technologies) of information delivery within the educational material.

Over many years, human beings have accumulated experience and skills, and have developed methods for transmitting it to subsequent generations. At present, modern science offers a wide range of methods for transmitting accumulated experience within educational material from one generation to another [4, p. 73].

It is impossible to assert that one method, one methodology, of delivering educational content is superior to another method or methodology. To make such an assertion would be a grave error, as it would result in elevating a single method (one methodology) of transmitting information to the level of an absolute, thereby marginalizing other methods of delivering educational material and, consequently, eliminating choice within the realm of methods (methodologies) for conveying existing experience as such. The diversity of methods (methodologies) for transmitting existing experience (knowledge) is determined by numerous factors (temporal, social, rational, psychological, linguistic, hermeneutic, physiological, etc.), but primarily by the inherent diversity of the experience (knowledge) itself—its multi-level structure, multidimensionality, volume, and so forth.

We know that in the surrounding world, the essence of phenomena and processes generally possesses a multi-layered nature; everything depends on the informational segment from which it is viewed. In other words, at each level of material presentation, a 'new' essence of the existing knowledge is revealed. Thus, within the educational process, students uncover a 'new meaning' in the knowledge already familiar to them, thereby perceiving this experience (knowledge) at a higher level. The search for new meaning (essence) in already known experience indicates that pedagogical problems have risen to a philosophical level, which can and should thereafter be examined in close connection with this sphere of human activity. Therefore, we will not separately address the issue of searching for new meaning or attributing new meaning to existing knowledge, but will demonstrate how the choice of mode of knowledge transmission conditions the motivation to seek meaning and facilitates its discovery at a given level, reflecting the amount of meaning inherent in knowledge at the corresponding level[5, p. 82].

The transmission of knowledge (experience) within the framework of learning material is systematic. Firstly, each method (methodology) comprises its own 'key steps' (algorithm) that eliminate randomness while allowing for improvisation in the transmission of experience (knowledge). Secondly, the informational units of the transmitted experience (knowledge) must be selected deliberately rather than spontaneously, in order to reveal significant interconnections among them. This is crucial because, in our view, the ultimate goal of the educational process is to cultivate in the learner informational representations of various processes and phenomena of the surrounding reality, in relation to which the learning material is conveyed. This is one of the key aspects of the educational process, as an important feature of human thinking is the ability to think in images. This was discussed by Aristotle,

Plato, F. Bacon, and other philosophers. A person thinks not in terms of objects or their individual qualities, but in the images of objects. This suggests that the properties of an object are considered in relation to each other; some properties appear directly, while others are expressed indirectly, through connections with other objects.

In historical terms, a vivid example of the figurativeness of human thought is language. Language is not merely a system of signs; it is primarily a system of images through which accumulated experience is encoded and recognized. Moreover, language, as a system of images, reflects the distinctive features of perception and understanding of the surrounding reality by its speakers, demonstrating the defining features of the mentality of representatives of a particular cultural group. Language itself, as an open living system, can reveal much about the cultural evolution of its speakers, the societal processes underway, the cultural aspirations of language bearers, and the influence of other ethno-linguistic groups on its development.

In contemporary post-industrial society, the informational space is highly condensed, and the interaction among various cultures is very intensive. This suggests that representatives of different cultures are continuously engaged in dialogue at appropriate levels, aiming to enrich and complement each other. For dialogue to be successful, it is necessary to possess a specific toolkit, a crucial element of which is language, or more precisely, knowledge of another culture's language. Throughout the historical development of humanity, there has always existed a language through which representatives of various cultures communicated. At different historical periods, ancient Aramaic, Greek, Latin, French, and others have functioned as international languages. At present, English occupies this role.

Thus, in order to successfully master a foreign language, it is necessary not only to study its grammar and expand one's vocabulary, but also to develop an understanding of the culture of the people who are its native speakers. The achievement of this goal is facilitated by the establishment of a dialogue of cultures. The school of cultural dialogue, as a methodology for delivering educational material alternative to the traditional approach, was founded by V.S. Bibler (1918–2000), an outstanding Russian philosopher, cultural historian, and culturologist. The cultural dialogue school program was founded by its creator V.S. Bibler on the ideas of M. Bakhtin's concept of 'dialogue as the essence of consciousness, thought, and the activity of the 20th-century human' [1, p. 217], V.S. Bibler's ideas on the dialogue of logics as a form of modern theorizing, and L.'s concept Vygotsky's inner speech as a unit of individual thought, the practice of 'teacher-dialogists' [3, p. 135]. As fundamental propositions of the Cultural Dialogue Theory (ШДК), V.S. Bibler identified:

- dialogue and dialogicity as an integral component of personality;
- the existence of the world's polyphony within individual consciousness as a form of internal dialogue;

- the infinite development of new meanings of each phenomenon entering into dialogue as the principal event of the dialogue;
- dialogue is understood as the interaction of diverse consciousnesses irreducible to a single whole, as the communication of different forms of understanding;
- Modern thinking is constructed on the models and schemes of different cultures, implying dialogic communication between the experience accumulated at the contemporary stage and the experience of previous eras [2, p. 37].

Thus, one of the distinctive features of the cultural dialogue school methodology is that dialogue serves as both the unit and the form of learning. Moreover, dialogue can take place simultaneously on several levels: teacher – student, student – cultural era, student – student, and internal dialogue. The most important aspect is that the student is able to articulate their own point of view, that is, to externalize their internal dialogue (speech), while the teacher is able to observe, understand, and support the student's standpoint (idea). Dialogue, as a unit of learning, presupposes the 'discovery' of new knowledge by the student within the context of a dialogue focused on a specific problem. Dialogue, as a form of learning, entails initiating the dialogue situation, that is, creating the conditions and prerequisites for its occurrence.

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意义翻译的现象学

THE PHENOMENOLOGY OF THE TRANSLATION OF MEANINGS

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摘要：本文运用现象学方法，探讨了社会共同体构建的问题。作者认为，文化不仅是促进区域和族群融合的工具，也是构建民族认同的神圣空间。文章考察了人们从被动接受文化传统到积极参与文化共创的转变，并分析了数字化和价值挑战对传统经验传承方式的影响。文章特别关注互动和游戏实践，将其解读为内化神圣意义和伦理规范的现代机制。作者论证了共创和教育指导在保护文化资本和增强社会凝聚力方面的重要性。文化统一被阐释为传统伦理与相关社会实践持续互动的结果。

关键词：文化统一，民族认同，神圣意义，文化诠释学，互动实践，文化资本，社会文化融合。

Annotation. *The paper examines the problems of forming a community of society through the prism of a phenomenological approach. The author considers culture not only as a tool for the integration of regions and ethnic groups, but also as a sacred space for the formation of national identity. The transition from passive perception of cultural traditions to active co-creation is investigated. The transformation of traditional forms of experience transmission under the influence of digitalization and value challenges is analyzed. Special attention is paid to interactive and gaming practices, which are interpreted as modern mechanisms for the interiorization of sacred meanings and ethical norms. The author substantiates the importance of co-creation and pedagogical mentoring in preserving cultural capital and strengthening social cohesion of society. Cultural unity is interpreted as the result of the continuous interaction of traditional ethics and relevant social practices.*

Key words: *cultural unity, national identity, sacred meanings, cultural hermeneutics, interactive practices, cultural capital, socio-cultural integration.*

The current stage of societal development is characterized by a search for stable value orientations capable of ensuring the consolidation of nations and ethnic groups within a unified state. The concept of the unity of peoples becomes not merely an event or a set of formalized activities but a profound existential challenge that demands reflection on what it means for each citizen to share in the common fate of the country. In this context, culture emerges as a fundamental and the most powerful instrument of integration, representing a universal language through which society engages in dialogue not only verbally but also through a diversity of artistic forms: music, dance, theatrical imagery, literature, and architecture. Considering culture as a dynamic system, it is important to highlight its immense multidimensionality, evidenced by the existence of hundreds of definitions of this term in scholarly literature, which underscores the complexity and vast scope of the object under investigation. Cultural capital in contemporary conditions serves as an integral characteristic that defines the extent of a society's vital forces and the human spirit's capacity for self-development and creative reflection.

The process of national unity formation is inextricably connected with the actualization of cultural heritage, where each element functions as a repository of meanings that can be activated depending on the epoch's demands. It is precisely through culture that the individual apprehends themselves in the perception of the other, assessing historical experience and co-creating a common future. Transcending the boundaries of everyday life reveals an elevated bridge that links regions and ethnic groups. An exceptional role in this process is occupied by theatrical art, which throughout different historical periods has addressed the most complex challenges – ranging from educational and formative to socio-communicative functions. Theatrical art possesses a unique capacity to expand the boundaries of empathy, enabling individuals to perceive a fragment of their own experience within the creativity of others.

However, in the context of global digitalization and value relativism, traditional forms of transmitting experience undergo substantial transformation, necessitating a shift from the static perception of values to their active engagement through practice. Contemporary culture aims to involve the subject in the process of constructing a semantic field, which manifests through play practices acting as a mechanism for entering the space of otherness, where familiar social roles are suspended. The sacred character of the game, rooted in ancient rituals, today emulates interactive formats, among which the Quest occupies a significant place as a specific sociocultural phenomenon. The Quest becomes a metaphor for the human journey through the labyrinths of post-industrial society, reestablishing the hierarchy of the world and the significance of each step toward truth.

The concept of the unity of peoples is based on the recognition that each distinct region contributes its unique contribution to the national cultural map. Regional

festivals, creative competitions, and local initiatives constitute not merely a series of events but a living network that demonstrates the interaction of diverse forms of expression, which complement and enrich each other. Within this system, it is crucial to uphold respect for local traditions and histories, since it is precisely at the intersection of different experiences that authentic dialogue and mutual understanding emerge. The integration of innovative interactive game formats into the culture-forming environment enables the actualization of latent layers of historical memory, rendering them accessible to the sensory perception of a broad audience. The hermeneutics of culture regards the participant in such practices as an interpreter who, in the course of resolving tasks, interiorizes values by translating external information into personal experience.

The key to stable social unity lies in cultivating a sense of responsibility for the cultural space of one's region and country as a whole. Mentorship and generational continuity acquire particular importance here, as fundamental meanings are passed on to the younger generation in a language accessible to them. The use of Quests designed for family participation or a child audience establishes the foundation for transmitting fundamental ethical norms through game engagement and the shared overcoming of challenges. This makes it possible to transcend the rigidity of traditional educational institutions, transforming the process of cognition into an adventure and restoring to the individual the right to personal discovery and wonder. Engagement with young authors, the development of pedagogical mastery, and the support of talents cultivate new generations of creators whose energy, combined with the experience of mentors, reinforces the state's cultural system.

Cultural practices, in a broad sense, teach to see the value of another person, overcome stereotypes, and find a humanistic foundation for interaction. This is particularly important under conditions of global challenges, when society requires a culture of solidarity, attentiveness, and responsible behavior. Philosophical analysis of contemporary leisure forms demonstrates that they can ensure an increase in the creative potential of the population and the strengthening of social cohesion. The inclusion of action elements, immersive performance, and theatricalization in public projects transforms them into a full-fledged anthropological experiment, where not only erudition is tested but also the readiness for empathy, teamwork, and acceptance of responsibility for the collective outcome. The sacred in this context is understood as the transcendence of spirit over circumstances and the capacity to perceive the eternal in the transient.

Thus, the concept of unity among peoples should be supported by projects aimed at creating accessible cultural platforms where people of different ages and nationalities learn to listen to each other. Cultural capital can be substantially enhanced through the development of creative industries that address the higher cognitive and aesthetic needs of the individual. Unity is not a static

condition, but a continuous process of renewal manifested through acts of individual and collective creativity. It demands courage in the preservation of the country's wealth and fidelity to the sacred origins of human existence, ensuring the harmonization of the psycho-physical state of the individual and the maintenance of the nation's cultural well-being.

The integration of regional traditions and innovative play models forms a specific cultural competence – the capacity not merely to consume benefits but actively to produce new meanings within a given context of unity. The design of such interactive formats represents a promising challenge for cultural specialists and educators aiming to preserve the cultural code in an era of transformation. Ultimately, through engagement with art and participation in dynamic cultural practices, the contemporary individual acquires a path to self-understanding and awareness of their connection to the great heritage of peoples, transforming the country's diversity into its primary unifying force. Culture as a system of meanings provides an individual with a reliable set of tools for navigating the world, while collective creativity and the collaborative pursuit of truth become the foundation of the sustainable development of civic consciousness and the prosperity of society as a whole.

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数字文化语境下女性权力原型的转变：一个哲学维度
**TRANSFORMATION OF THE ARCHETYPE OF WOMAN
IN POWER IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL CULTURE:
A PHILOSOPHICAL DIMENSION**

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摘要：本文从哲学角度探讨了数字文化中女性权力原型的转变。文章借鉴荣格分析心理学、海德格爾的技术本体论、鲍德里亚的拟像理论以及福柯的话语分析，探究了在算法环境和网络认同实践的影响下，集体无意识矩阵如何重构。文章提出，数字文化将女性权力原型从本体论上稳定的结构转变为流动的拟像建构。

关键词：原型，数字文化，女性权力，拟像，技术本体论，权力话语，集体无意识，表演性，格斯特尔，媒体形象。

Abstract. *The article offers a philosophical examination of the transformation of the archetype of woman in power within digital culture. Drawing on Jungian analytical psychology, M. Heidegger's ontology of technology, J. Baudrillard's theory of simulacra, and M. Foucault's discourse analysis, the mechanisms by which collective-unconscious matrices are restructured under the influence of algorithmic environments and network identification practices are explored. The thesis is advanced that digital culture transforms the archetype from an ontologically stable structure into a fluid simulacral construct.*

Keywords: *archetype, digital culture, woman in power, simulacrum, ontology of technology, discourse of power, collective unconscious, performativity, Gestell, media image.*

Between the Archetype and the Algorithm

The image of the woman in power is among the most stable yet simultaneously the most contentious symbolic configurations within Western culture. From the standpoint of C.-G. Jung's analytical psychology, archetypal images constitute primary forms of psychic organization, rooted in the collective unconscious and expressed through cultural symbols, myths, and imagery [1]. The archetype of the

woman in power—whether the Great Mother, the Anima, or the 'dark mistress'—has for millennia provided a stable matrix for the collective perception of real women aspiring to public authority. The question of what happens to this matrix within the conditions of digital culture constitutes not only a psychological but also a deeply philosophical problem.

Digital culture — a concept denoting a qualitative shift in the modes of production, transmission, and consumption of symbolic forms — calls into question the very ontological stability of archetypal structures [2]. If in the pre-digital era the archetype functioned as a relatively stable matrix of the collective imaginary, transmitted through slowly evolving cultural channels — mythology, religion, literature — then algorithmic media generate a fundamentally different situation: images are reproduced, fragmented, and remixed at such a rate that the archetype loses its traditional function as a stable cultural orienting point and turns into a fluid, constantly redefined construct.

This problem requires a comprehensive philosophical toolkit that transcends both classical Jungian psychology and media sociology. The present article offers an interpretation at the intersection of several theoretical horizons: Martin Heidegger's ontology of technology, Jean Baudrillard's theory of simulacra, Michel Foucault's discourse analysis, and post-Jungian feminist philosophy.

Ontological dimension: the archetype as a structure of being and its digital destruction

The central ontological question arising in the analysis of the archetype in the digital age can be formulated as follows: is the archetype a transcendental structure, independent of the modes of its cultural representation, or is it constituted by the very practices of symbolic production? Jung favored the first position, postulating the archetype as an 'empty form' [1], which acquires specific content depending on the cultural context, while maintaining an immutable structural core. Digital culture undermines this position by advancing a radically constructivist challenge: if the archetypal image can be reproduced in thousands of mutually exclusive versions simultaneously, does the «structural core» indicated by Jung exist at all?

The philosophical framework for answering this question is provided by M. Heidegger's ontology of technology [6]. According to Heidegger, modern technology is a particular mode of revealing being — «Gestell» (Gestell), in which all entities appear exclusively as «standing-reserve», that is, as resources made available for use. Applied to digital media, this idea acquires acute concreteness: algorithmic platforms 'unveil' the image of the woman-leader not as a multifaceted subjecthood or archetypal depth, but primarily as a resource for generating engagement (engagement) and advertising revenue. The post transforms the archetype into the 'deliverable': it exists only insofar as it functions as affectively

charged content. In this sense, digital culture performs a genuinely ontological transformation of the archetype, altering the very mode of its being in culture.

Epistemological shift: from representation to simulacrum

If Heidegger describes the ontological aspect of the problem, then J. Baudrillard proposes its epistemological dimension. In the concept of simulacra [3], Baudrillard outlines a process whereby signs progressively lose their connection to reality: from a faithful reflection of profound reality, they proceed to its masking, then to the concealment of the absence of any reality, and finally to a pure simulacrum—a sign that refers to nothing except itself. This trajectory is fully reproduced in the destiny of the image of the woman in power within the digital environment.

At the level of traditional media, the image of a particular female politician still retained at least the claim to represent a real individual. Within the realm of social networks and algorithmic platforms, this image undergoes a simulacral shift: it becomes a self-referential sign circulating according to the logic of virality and affective resonance, rather than the logic of reflecting the real qualities of the subject. A meme depicting a politician that has amassed millions of views constitutes the reality of this politician for a significant part of the audience more effectively than any real actions or decisions. The archetype does not disappear but is simulated: instead of Jung's 'empty vessel' filled with collective unconscious content, a simulacrum of the archetype emerges — an image merely imitating archetypal depth.

Power, discourse, and subject production: the Foucauldian dimension

Analysis by M. Foucault allows shifting the emphasis from the question of the nature of the image to the question of the mechanisms of power that produce this image [4]. From the Foucauldian perspective, discourse is not merely a set of statements about a subject, but a practice that constitutes the very objects it addresses. The discourse on the woman in power circulating within the digital environment does not describe a pre-existing archetypal image but actively produces it, establishing parameters of the permissible and impermissible, the normal and pathological.

Digital platforms create mechanisms of discursive production of the subject unprecedented in scope. Algorithms that select and promote content function as a panoptic [4] structure: they record every user interaction with the image of the woman leader and use this data for increasingly precise targeting. As a result, a specific digital panopticon is formed, in which the woman leader is simultaneously under constant surveillance (each of her public actions is immediately archived and analyzed) and obliged to perform self-surveillance, internalizing the platform's normative requirements. The double standard to which women in politics are subjected in the digital space — the necessity to simultaneously display 'masculine' decisiveness and 'feminine' empathy — is nothing other than the effect of discursive normalization in the Foucauldian sense.

It is significant that the digital environment not only reproduces traditional mechanisms of disciplinary power but also creates new ones — horizontal and decentralized. If in the classical disciplinary model power originates from an identifiable center (the state, a media conglomerate), then in the network environment the production of normative images is carried out by the users themselves through likes, reposts, and comments. This creates the illusion of horizontality and democratization, whereas in reality, archetypal norms are reproduced with even greater intensity—precisely because of their apparent “spontaneity” and “popular character.”

Performativity and Feminist Deconstruction of the Archetype

Feminist philosophy introduces a critical dimension into this analysis by questioning the very status of the archetype as a neutral psychological category. From the perspective of J.'s performative theory Butler [5] argues that gender images do not reflect any inherent nature but are constituted through ritualized repetitive practices. From this perspective, the archetype of the woman in power appears not as a transhistorical structure of the collective unconscious but as a historically conditioned residue of normative gender performances, entrenched in cultural tradition and masquerading as 'natural.'

Digital culture creates a paradoxical situation for feminist deconstruction: on one hand, it opens new possibilities for the performative re-signification of the archetype. User content, ironically reinterpreting images of women in power, feminist memes, and 'empowerment' narratives undermine established archetypal clichés. On the other hand, algorithms oriented towards affective engagement systematically prioritize precisely those images that resonate with the most archaic and emotionally charged archetypal matrices. Deconstruction and archetypal reproduction coexist in the digital environment not as successive historical stages, but as simultaneous processes competing for symbolic space.

Archetype in the Conditions of Simulative Ontology: Towards a Synthesis

The integration of the examined theoretical perspectives allows for the proposition of the following synthetic thesis: digital culture effects the transition of the archetype of the woman in power from an ontological to a simulative mode of existence. Within the traditional cultural space, the archetype functioned as a stable structure with relatively stable symbolic content, providing collective identification and value orientation. In the digital environment, it transforms into what can be termed an 'archetype-simulacrum': an image reproducing the formal characteristics of archetypal depth (stability, emotional saturation, collective resonance), yet devoid of ontological rootedness and continuously redefined by the logic of the platform economy.

This transition carries significant implications for the philosophy of culture and social philosophy. If the archetype ceases to function as a stable symbolic orientation, this indicates a profound crisis of collective identity — in this instance, the identity associated with the perception of female leadership as a culturally significant

phenomenon. Society finds itself in a situation where normative images structuring the perception of power lose their stability and become the subject of an unceasing struggle for symbolic domination—a struggle waged not only by political actors but also by algorithms, advertisers, and anonymous network communities.

Philosophy of education and the transformation of concepts of female leadership:

The issue of the transformation of the archetype of the woman in power holds particular interest within the context of the philosophy and sociology of education. The educational environment is precisely one of the key spaces where normative conceptions of power, leadership, and gender identity are formed. Within the environment of digital culture, the process of socialization is increasingly conducted not only through traditional educational institutions. An algorithmically organized information-communicative environment begins to compete with schools and universities in the production of values and behavioral models.

The contemporary learner is immersed in a continuous stream of digital representations. These representations shape conceptions of permissible forms of publicity, authority, and leadership. The image of the woman in power becomes part of a latent educational mechanism operating through media consumption, social networks, and algorithmic platforms. Consequently, the educational space ceases to be solely an institutional system for knowledge transmission. It transforms into a distributed digital environment of symbolic identity construction.

From a philosophical perspective, this signifies a radical transformation in the very nature of educational impact. The classical model of education presupposed a relatively stable system of cultural reference points and value patterns. The digital era creates a situation characterized by fragmentation and simulacra of normative models. The archetype of the woman in power existing in the media environment is no longer internalized by students as an integral cultural image. It is perceived as a set of rapidly changing visual and discursive patterns. This creates a contradiction between the aims of humanistic education and the logic inherent in algorithmic culture, which is primarily oriented towards emotional engagement and content consumption.

In this context, the philosophy of education faces the necessity of developing new critical approaches to the analysis of digital socialization. The development of media literacy, critical thinking, and the capacity for philosophical reflection on the mechanisms of the digital construction of power and gender becomes especially relevant.

The comprehension of the transformation of the archetype of the woman in power emerges not only as an issue within social philosophy and cultural studies but also as a significant educational challenge. It is connected with the development among youth of the ability to distinguish authentic subjectivity from simulacral forms of

media representation. The younger generation must learn to critically reflect on the images of power and leadership that the digital environment offers.

Conclusion

The analysis conducted allows for the formulation of a number of fundamental conclusions. Firstly, the transformation of the archetype of the woman in power in conditions of digital culture represents not merely a change in media presentation, but a genuinely ontological shift: the algorithmic ‘supply’ restructures the very mode of being of archetypal structures in culture. Secondly, at the epistemological level, this shift is described as a transition from representation to simulation: the image of the woman leader in the digital environment functions according to the logic of the simulacrum, losing its referential link to real subjectivity. Thirdly, the discursive mechanisms of digital platforms reproduce and reinforce normative requirements for the gendered presentation of women in power, creating new forms of disciplinary control conceptualized within the framework of Foucauldian biopolitics.

At the same time, digital culture opens new possibilities for the performative re-signification of outdated archetypal matrices. The philosophical task is to develop critical tools that enable the distinction between authentic deconstruction of normative images and their simulacral reproduction under the guise of liberation. This requires an interdisciplinary dialogue between analytical psychology, philosophy of technology, post-structuralist theory, and feminist philosophy—a dialogue whose urgency in the era of algorithmic culture is difficult to overestimate.

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俄罗斯足球场建筑

ARCHITECTURE OF FOOTBALL STADIUMS IN RUSSIA

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The problem of maintaining mine workings amid the deepening of mining operations and their spatial development remains relevant when substantiating options for the opening and preparation of reserves. Although in recent years the specific volumes of development workings in the Karaganda basin have significantly decreased (from 8.4 m/1000 t of production in 1990 to 4.3 m/1000 t in 2003), the specific volume of supported workings has not only failed to decrease but on average increased by 15%. This trend is determined by several factors:

- the majority of operating mines in the Karaganda basin, after their merger with adjacent mines, do not achieve production corresponding to their combined design capacity;
- despite the reduction in production volumes, the length of the opening workings required to support the production processes in the mines has not undergone significant changes;
- the increasing complexity of mining conditions, primarily due to deepening, has necessitated the use of ventilation and degassing technological schemes to mitigate the adverse effects of mining and geological factors.

Technological schemes have been implemented in the mines of the Karaganda basin, which allow for a significant reduction in both the extent of driving and the maintenance of preparatory and cutting workings, for example, by using the transport roadway of an adjacent extraction panel as ventilation for the subsequent panel. In the development of seams with high gas content, technological schemes for maintaining the workings of the adjacent extraction panel are employed to ensure the required volume of air supply. In some mines of the basin, drainage drifts are excavated for preliminary degassing of the seam using boreholes. The wide range of seam occurrence conditions necessitates the development of a techno-economic model of the mine subsystem ‘maintenance and repair of mine workings’ to select technological schemes for seam preparation and extraction.

The methodological approach to model development is based on building operational models of labor intensity and volumes of work for reinforcing (sealing)

mine workings. The initial data for the research were timing observations of teams repairing mine workings at the mines of the Karaganda basin. Based on the conducted research, relationships for labor intensity by operations have been established. The total labor intensity for the subsystem is considered as

$$\overline{T_p^{kp}} = \sum_{l=1}^L (T'p_l + T''p_l), \text{ man-sm./year}, \quad (1)$$

$\overline{T'p_l}$ where – labor intensity of reinforcement work for the l -th mine working ($l=1, 2, \dots, L$), let us represent it as a sum of the labor intensities of individual operations

$$\overline{T'p_l} = LB_l k \kappa p_l (\overline{T_p1_l} + T_p2_l + T_pA_l), \text{ man-sm. per year}, \quad (2)$$

$\overline{T_p1_l}$ – labor intensity of work for extracting support and cleaning the released rock mass, man-s·m/m,

– metallic arched, reinforced concrete bolts

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = (0,012S_{np_l} + 0,168) \times np_l, \quad (3)$$

– metallic arched, metallic mesh

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = (0,0112S_{np_l} + 0,226) \times np_l, \quad (4)$$

– metallic trapezoidal, reinforced concrete bolts

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = \frac{0,9 \times S_{np_l} np_l}{18,271 + 3,487 \times S_{np_l}}, \quad (5)$$

– metallic trapezoidal, metallic mesh

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = (0,0123 \times S_{np_l} + 0,249) \times np_l, \quad (6)$$

– reinforced concrete arched, reinforced concrete bolts

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = \frac{1,1 \times S_{np_l} np_l}{16,61 + 3,17 \times S_{np_l}}, \quad (7)$$

– reinforced concrete arched, metallic mesh

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = \frac{0,791 \times S_{np_l} np_l}{16,61 + 3,17 \times S_{np_l}}, \quad (8)$$

– reinforced concrete trapezoidal, reinforced concrete bolts

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = \frac{S_{np_l} np_l}{16,61 + 3,17 \times S_{np_l}}, \quad (9)$$

– reinforced concrete trapezoidal, metal mesh

$$\overline{T_p1_l} = \frac{0,719 \times S_{np_l} np_l}{16,61 + 3,17 \times S_{np_l}}, \quad (10)$$

– anchor with roof bolting using metal mesh

$$\overline{T_{p1}} = \overline{0,619 \times np_l (21,975 - 1,935 \times \text{нак}_l)^{-1}}, \quad (11)$$

– column-free support

$$\overline{T_{p1}} = \overline{S_{np_l} np_l (35,28 - 14,39 \times S_{np_l})^{-1}}, \quad (12)$$

$\overline{T_{p2}}$ – labor effort for support installation work, man-cm/m by support types:
– metal arched

$$\overline{T_{p2}} = \overline{k_{ma} (0,437 + 0,423 np) \times \left(\frac{1,217 - 0,085 f_{cp}}{4,3 - 0,294 f_{cp}} \right) (0,002 S_{np}^2 - -0,043 S_{np} + 1,226)}, \quad (13)$$

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.155$ with working reinforcement by reinforced concrete bolts,

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 0.857$ – metal mesh;
– metal trapezoidal,

$$\overline{T_{p2}} = \overline{k_{ma} \times (0,437 + 0,423 np) \times \left(\frac{0,936 + 0,047 f_{cp}}{4,3 - 0,294 f_{cp}} \right) (0,33 + 0,075 S_{np})}, \quad (14)$$

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.176$ – working reinforcement by reinforced concrete bolts,

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 0.873$ – support with metal mesh;
– reinforced concrete arched

$$\overline{T_{p2}} = \overline{k_{ma} \times (1,252 - 0,189 np) \times \left(\frac{0,936 + 0,05 f_{cp}}{4,3 - 0,294 f_{cp}} \right) (0,338 + 0,074 S_{np})}, \quad (15)$$

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.423$ – support of the working by reinforced concrete supports,

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.056$ – support with metal mesh;
– reinforced concrete trapezoidal

$$\overline{T_{p2}} = \overline{k_{ma} \times (0,437 + 0,423 np) \times \left(\frac{0,944 + 0,05 f_{cp}}{4,3 - 0,294 f_{cp}} \right) (0,337 + 0,074 S_{np})}, \quad (16)$$

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.851$ – support of the working by reinforced concrete supports,

$\overline{k_{ma}} = 1.373$ – support with metal mesh;
– anchored with roof support by metal mesh

$$\overline{T_{p2}} = \overline{(21,975 - 1,935 \times \text{нак})^{-1} \times np}, \quad (17)$$

\overline{nak} – number of anchors per set, pcs.;
– frameless support

$$\overline{Trp2_l} = 0,049 \times np \times S_{np}^{0,329} \times (0,682 + 0,227f_{cp}) \quad (18)$$

$\overline{TrpD_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of support elements, man-cm/m,

$$\overline{TrpD_l} = \overline{Trmet_l} + \overline{Trp3_l} + \overline{Trpl_l} + \overline{Tсет_l} + \overline{Tанк_l} \quad (19)$$

$\overline{Trmet_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of metal support elements, from the shaft, man-cm/m,

$$\overline{Trmet_l} = \left(\frac{L_{Dl}}{41,696L_{Dl}+1995} \right) \left(\frac{SCB_l}{1,045SCB_l-0,0064} \right) \times np_l \quad (20)$$

$\overline{LD_l}$ – delivery distance, m;

$\overline{Trp3_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of reinforced concrete sets, man-cm/m,

$$\overline{Trp3_l} \text{ – labor intensity of delivery of reinforced concrete sets, man-cm/m,} \\ \overline{Trp3_l} = \frac{L_{Dl}V_3}{7,903L_{Dl}+232} \quad (21)$$

$\overline{Trpl_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of timber materials, man-cm/m³

$$\overline{Trpl_l} = \left(\frac{L_{Dl}}{12,624L_{Dl}+2301} \right) \left(\frac{S_{np_l}}{0,638S_{np_l}+0,053} \right) V_{pl_l} \quad (22)$$

$\overline{Tсет_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of mesh, man-cm/m,

$$\overline{Tсет_l} = \frac{L_{Dl}V_{сет}}{10,645L_{Dl}+312,5} \quad (23)$$

$\overline{Tанк_l}$ – labor intensity of delivery of anchors, man-cm/m,

$$\overline{Tанк_l} = \overline{nak_l np_l 10^{-3} (1,6 + 0,067 \times L_{Dl})} \quad (24)$$

$V_{z,,}$, V_{net} – volumes of drifts and entries by support types (Table 1);

$\overline{kкр_l}$ – coefficient accounting for the number of repairs per 1 m of mine working

per year

$$\overline{k\kappa p_l} = k y_l \times k m_l \times k o_l, \tag{25}$$

$\overline{k y_l}$ – coefficient characterizing the influence of the stability of roof and side-walls of the mine working (Table 2);

Table 2. Coefficient of stability of enclosing rocks – $k y$

Type of mine working	Rock stability class		
	Stable	Moderately stable	Unstable
Workings advanced:			
- by coal	0.276	1.0	2.320
- by rock	0.41	1.0	2.5
- in seam split	0.468	1.0	1.594

$\overline{k m_l}$ – coefficient characterizing the influence of the i-th seam thickness working (Table 3) [3];

Table 3. Coefficient accounting for seam thickness – $\overline{k m}$

Type of support	Coefficient $\overline{k m}$
1. Workings driven in close proximity	
- metallic, concrete, reinforced concrete	
arched	$\overline{0,401 + 0,385m - 0.0475m^2}$
trapezoidal	$\overline{0,488 + 0,25m}$
- other types of support	$\overline{1,0}$
2. Field workings and workings driven along coal	$\overline{1,0}$

$\overline{k o_l}$ – coefficient accounting for the method of working support (Table 4) [3];

$\overline{T'' p_l}$ – labor intensity of working closure, man-shift·cm/m, – arched support

$$\overline{T'' p_l} = n p_l (0,036 + 0,014 \times S_{CB_l}); \tag{26}$$

– trapezoidal support

$$T''p_l = 0,021 \times np_l ScB_l^{0,663} \quad (27)$$

Table 4. Coefficient accounting for the method of working support – \overline{ko}

Method of working support		Coefficient \overline{ko}
on one hand	on the other hand	
Coal massif	Coal massif	0.5
Coal massif	Coal pillar	1.2
Coal pillar	Mined-out space	1.25
Coal pillar	Coal pillar	1.00
Mined-out space	Mined-out space	1.45
Coal massif	Mined-out space	0.7
Coal pillar	Gob-side entry	1.35
In the zone of influence of longwall mining operations		3.5

The labor input required for supporting workings secured by anchor and timberless supports is determined according to (11) and (12).

The volume of supported workings is determined in accordance with the technological system for reserve preparation. The intensity of conducting longwall mining operations influences the total extent of working support, which can be expressed as the product of the length of supported workings and the duration of support (months).

Volume of maintained workings at time t

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПОД}t}} = \sum_{l \in t} LB_{tl} \quad (28)$$

Volumes of maintained workings per single longwall face (months) according to the preparation technological scheme:

a) horizontal along long pillars in the rise (dip) direction:

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПОД}sj}} = \overline{Q_{\text{ПП}1sj} + Q_{\text{ПП}2sj} + Q_{\text{ППЛ}1sj} + Q_{\text{ППЛ}2sj}} \quad (29)$$

where j – index of the extraction pillar in the s -th extraction panel;

$\overline{Q_{\text{ПП}1sj}}$ – volume of maintained main field drifts in the s -th panel, ($s=1, 2, \dots, S$)

m;

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПП}1sj}} = \frac{Q_{\text{ПП}1s}^{\text{II}}}{M_{03s}} \times (t_{\text{ПОДГ}j} + \sum_{j=1}^{M_{03s}} T_{\text{ЭК}j}) \quad (30)$$

$\overline{t_{\text{ПОДГ}}}_j$ – duration of longwall face preparation for extraction, including work on driving workings, degassing of the pillar, and equipment installation. duration of longwall operation, months;

$\overline{T_{\text{ЭКС}}}_j$ – duration of operation of the j -th extraction panel, including its processing and dismantling of longwall equipment, months;

$\overline{M_{03}}_s$ – total number of production faces in the s -th extraction field;

$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР1}}}_{\text{IS}}^{\text{II}}$ – volume of maintained main field drifts:

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР1}}}_{\text{IS}}^{\text{II}} = L_{\text{П}} \left(\frac{H_s}{\bar{L}_{\text{Л}}_s} + 1 \right), \text{ m}, \quad (31)$$

$\overline{L_{\text{П}}}_s$ – dimensions of the extraction panel along strike, m;

\overline{H}_s – dimensions of the extraction panel along dip, m;

$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР2}}}_{\text{Sj}}$ – the same for field crosscuts,

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР2}}}_{\text{Sj}} = \frac{Q_{\text{ПР2}}^{\text{II}}}{M_{03_s}} \times (t_{\text{ПОДГ}}_j + \sum_{j=1}^{M_{03_s}} T_{\text{ЭКС}}_j), \text{ m}, \quad (32)$$

$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР2}}}_{\text{IS}}^{\text{II}}$ – volume of maintained fault-related (breakdown) furnaces,

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПР2}}}_{\text{IS}}^{\text{II}} = \bar{L} \bar{c} \bar{b}_s \left(\frac{H_s}{\bar{L}_{\text{Л}}_s} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{L_{\text{П}}}{\bar{L}_{\text{Л}}_s} + 1 \right), \text{ m}, \quad (33)$$

$\overline{L \bar{c} \bar{b}}_s$ – average length of the gob fire gate in the s -th extraction panel, m;

$\overline{Q_{\text{ПРЛ1}}}_{\text{Sj}}$ – the same for breaklines,

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПРЛ1}}}_{\text{Sj}} = 1,5 \times \bar{L}_{\text{Л}} \times (t_{\text{ПОДГ}}_j + T_{\text{ЭКС}}_j), \text{ m}, \quad (34)$$

$\overline{L}_{\text{Л}}_s$ – average longwall face length in the s -th extraction panel, m;

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПРЛ2}}}_{\text{Sj}} = \frac{Q_{\text{ПРЛ2}}^{\text{II}}}{M_{03_s}} \times (0,5 \times t_{\text{ПОДГ}}_j + T_{\text{ЭКС}}_j), \text{ m}, \quad (35)$$

b) panel type, with long pillars along the strike:

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПОД}}}_{sj} = Q_{\text{ПП}}_{sj} + Q_{\text{ППЛ1}}_{sj} + Q_{\text{ППЛ2}}_{sj}, \quad (36)$$

where – volume of maintained field workings: $\overline{Q_{\text{ПП}}}_{sj}$

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ПП}}}_{sj} = \frac{Q_{\text{ПР}}_{sj}}{M'_{\text{ОЗ}_s}} \times (T_{\text{ПР}}_j + \sum_{j=1}^{M_{\text{ОЗ}_s}} T_{\text{ЭК}}_j : m_{\text{РОЗ}}_{ts}) \quad (37)$$

$\overline{m_{\text{РОЗ}}}_{s}$ - number of simultaneously operating faces in the extraction field;

if =1, then always =1, otherwise >1, $\overline{n_{\text{КР}}}_s m_{\text{РОЗ}}_s m_{\text{РОЗ}}_s$

$\overline{n_{\text{КР}}}_s$ - number of wings in the panel of the extraction field;

$\overline{T_{\text{ПР}}}_j$ - duration of development works for the preparation of the j -th extraction pillar;

$\overline{Q_{\text{ППЛ1}}}_{sj}, \overline{Q_{\text{ППЛ2}}}_{sj}$ – volume of maintained seam workings,

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ППЛ1}}}_{sj} = \frac{\left(\frac{H_s}{L_s} + 1\right) \times (L_{\text{П}}_s + 100)}{M_{\text{ОЗ}_s}} \times (T_{\text{ПР}}_j + T_{\text{ЭК}}_j), \text{ m}; \quad (38)$$

$$\overline{Q_{\text{ППЛ2}}}_{sj} = \frac{(4H_s + 100)}{M_{\text{ОЗ}_s}} \times (T_{\text{ПР}}_j + \sum_{j=1}^{M_{\text{ОЗ}_s}} T_{\text{ЭК}}_j : m_{\text{РОЗ}}_{ts}), \text{ m}. \quad (39)$$

Thus, in modeling the parameters of the subsystem, the control parameters are those of the cleaning and preparatory works subsystems.

The economic evaluation of the accepted mining development options at the mine based on the factor ‘maintenance of mine workings’ is performed on the basis of calculating operational maintenance costs.

Operational costs of maintaining workings ($C_{\text{ext}\{maintenance\}}$)

$$\overline{C_{\text{ПОД}}} = \sum_{l1=1}^{L1} L_{B1l1} C_{\text{ПОД}l1} + \sum_{l2=1}^{L2} L_{B2l2} C_{\text{ПОД}l2}, \quad (40)$$

where (L_{p}), (L_{a}) are the lengths of the maintained and abandoned

workings, respectively, $\overline{L_{B1l} L_{B2l}}$ workings, m;

$\overline{C_{\text{ПОД}l}}$ – costs of maintaining workings, tg/m per year;

$$\overline{C_{\text{ПОД}l}} = k_{\text{КР}} \times (C_{Ml} + C_{ЗП_l}) \quad \overline{C_{\text{ПОД}l}} = k_{\text{КР}} \times (C_{Ml} + C_{ЗП_l}), \text{ t/m per year.} \quad (41)$$

$\overline{C_{Ml}}$ – material costs per 1 m, KZT/m per year

$$\overline{C_{Ml}} = k_{\text{пн}l}(V_{\text{мет}l}\text{Ц}_{\text{мет}} + V_{\text{сет}l}\text{Ц}_{\text{сет}} + V_{\text{з}l}\text{Ц}_{\text{з}}) + V_{\text{л}l}\text{Ц}_{\text{л}} + V_{\text{анк}l}\text{Ц}_{\text{анк}} \quad (42)$$

$\overline{k_{\text{пн}l}}$ – coefficient accounting for reuse of the support, is given in Table 5;

$\overline{V_{\text{анк}l}}$ – anchor consumption per 1 m of the working,

$$\overline{V_{\text{анк}l}} = n_{\text{ак}l}n_{\text{р}l} \text{ pcs/m};$$

$\text{Ц}_{\text{мет}}$, $\text{Ц}_{\text{з}}$, $\text{Ц}_{\text{л}}$, $\text{Ц}_{\text{сет}}$, $\text{Ц}_{\text{анк}}$ – the price of 1 t of metal, 1 m³ of rock supports, 1 m³ of lumber, 1 set of anchor support, respectively, KZT;

$\overline{C_{\text{зп}l}}$ – labor costs are determined for the following operations: removal of support with clearing of the released rock mass (C_{1l}), replacement (C_{2l}), and delivery of support elements to the working from the main transport roadway (C_{3l})

$$\overline{C_{\text{зп}l}} = [(C_{1l} \times k'_{\text{ткр}l} + C_{2l} \times k''_{\text{ткр}l}) \times T_{\text{ст}4} + C_{3l} \times k'''_{\text{ткр}l} \times T_{\text{ст}3}] \times k_{\text{д}}, \text{ t/m}, \quad (43)$$

where – coefficients taking into account the type of support, respectively, during

extraction, installation, and transportation, $\overline{k'_{\text{ткр}l}, k''_{\text{ткр}l}, k'''_{\text{ткр}l}}$

– if the support is trapezoidal with a flat covering, then

$$\overline{k'_{\text{ткр}l}} = 0,887 \quad \overline{k''_{\text{ткр}l}} = 0,887, \quad (44)$$

$$\overline{k''_{\text{ткр}l}} = 0,884 \quad \overline{k'''_{\text{ткр}l}} = 0,0007 \times L_{\text{д}l} + 0,597$$

– for other types of support

$$\overline{k'_{\text{ткр}l}} = \overline{k''_{\text{ткр}l}} = \overline{k'''_{\text{ткр}l}} = 1;$$

$$\overline{C_{1l}} = T_{\text{р}1}k_{\alpha 1l}, \text{ tg/m} \quad (45)$$

Table 5. Formulas for calculating the coefficient accounting for the repeated

use of support – $\overline{k_{\text{пн}}}$

Type of support	Coefficient $\overline{k_{\text{пн}}}$
1. KVV2, KVV4, KMP-TO, KMP-A3	$\overline{0,82}$
2. Arched reinforced concrete, concrete with an arch	$\overline{0,82 \left(0,805 + \frac{1,768}{S_{\text{СВ}}} \right)}$

3. Concrete with flat covering	$\overline{0,66 \left(0,803 + \frac{1,625}{SCB} \right)}$
4. Other types of support	$\overline{1,0}$
5. New support	1.0

$\overline{k\alpha 1_l}$ – coefficient accounting for the change in labor intensity due to the inclination angle of the working,

$$\overline{k\alpha 1_l} = (0,991 - 0,0546\alpha)^{-1}, \quad (46)$$

$\overline{k_d}$ – surcharge coefficient to the tariff rate,

$$\overline{C2_l} = \overline{Tp2_l k\alpha 2_l k p_l}, \text{ tg/m}, \quad (47)$$

$\overline{k\alpha 2_l}$ – coefficient accounting for the change in labor intensity due to the inclination angle of the working face,

$$\overline{k\alpha 2_l} = 0,009\alpha + 0,892, \quad (48)$$

$\overline{k p_l}$ – coefficient accounting for the density of support installation

$$\overline{k p_l} = 0,328 + \frac{0,674}{n p_l}, \text{ if the support is framed}, \quad (49)$$

$\overline{k p_l} = 1$, if the support is concrete or tubing

$$\overline{C3_l} = \overline{T p_{мет_l} + T p_{з_l} + T p_{л_l} + T_{анк_l} + T_{сет_l}} \quad (50)$$

$\overline{T_{ст3}}$ – wage rates of workers of grades 3 and 4, respectively, $\overline{T_{ст4}}$ tg/person-shift;

$\overline{C_{пог_{l2}}}$ – costs for mine workings sealing, tg/m,

$$\overline{C_{пог_{l2}}} = \overline{T_{ст4} T'' p_{l2} + C3_l \times T_{ст3}}. \quad (51)$$

The proposed model enabled the selection of parameters for technological schemes of preparation and extraction of mining panels at the Karaganda basin mines according to the criterion of minimizing costs for maintaining the workings. In developing measures to intensify coal mining at the mines, the main directions for applying the research results were:

– Justification of the technical and technological potential of mines under the current conditions of mining development, aimed at formulating long-term development programs for the coal mining enterprise;

– Justification of directions for implementing investment projects.

The analysis of the state of mine subsystems and the technical and technological decisions made during the preparation of their development programs allowed concluding that the availability of industrial reserves at the mines, including exposed ones, together with the use of high-performance machinery in the main production processes, enables consideration of several promising options for the development of coal mining.

The proposed methodological approach to modeling and joint optimization of parameters of technological processes and parameters of the mine subsystems makes it possible to establish the boundaries of their variation. The choice of the optimal variant for mine development is based on substantiated proposals using the developed techno-economic model and systematized evaluation characteristics, which allow defining the main parameters of coal mining development. In this case, it can be represented by a dynamic series of techno-economic indicators reflecting changes in the variant parameters. The essence of optimization is to select, given the chosen variant of longwall placement and sequence of face development, the most advantageous production dynamics for the coal mining enterprise at the specific mine. When the load on the faces decreases with an unchanged structure of the GPR and ventilation system, their temporal dynamics change, and the quantitative parameters of technological processes are established based on optimization results within the scope of the study. Thus, the optimal rate of roadway advancement is achieved at the minimum cost per 1 m (1 m³). At the same time, its duration will be optimal, and the parameter ‘number of simultaneously active driving faces’ is determined based on the required volume of drivage that ensures timely preparation of the extraction pillars. The completion of preparation works for an extraction pillar is defined as the scheduled moment of finishing the previous one, while the start of these works corresponds to the parameters of each GPR object. The formation of the parameters of the RGV subsystem directly depends, on one hand, on the duration of pillar and extraction field development as a whole, and on the other hand, on the schedule for optimal GPR organization. As an option for the minimum annual coal production at the mine, the planned indicators proposed by the mine for 2005–2010 are taken into account.

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莫斯科地下体育设施通风参数的合理性
**JUSTIFICATION OF VENTILATION PARAMETERS
OF UNDERGROUND SPORTS FACILITIES IN MOSCOW**

Kosirnikov Victor Sergeevich

研究结果已阐明，这些结果能够确定通风井通风系统参数与新井层开挖和施工工艺方案之间的相互关系。

文中还展示了通风井设计井和工作井开挖和施工工艺方案参数的技术评估示例。

There have been stated the results of the research which enable to determine the interconnection of ventilation systems parameters of air-shafts and technological schemes of opening and preparing new levels of shafts.

There have been presented a sample of technical evaluation of technological schemes parameters of opening and preparing both design and working shafts with regard to ventilation.

Ventilation schemes, parameters of the technological scheme, ventilation parameters, ventilation system, joint optimization

The subsystem ‘shaft ventilation’ is designed to ensure the accident-free and safe operation of other subsystems. The calculation of the parameters of the technological process of the ‘ventilation’ subsystem, which include the volume of air supplied to the shaft, is based on the instructions and safety regulations for coal mining enterprises [74, 80, 83, 84, 100, 105, 106], while the number of workers involved in the process is determined in accordance with workplace assignments based on standards applied in the coal industry. The task of studying the process consists in analyzing its development in connection with other processes and subsystems of the mine. In this regard, there is a need to study the state of mine air supply and its distribution across ventilation facilities.

The current condition of the ventilation system of the Karaganda basin mines is associated with different stages of development of the mine infrastructure and the specific mining-geological conditions of the coal-bearing regions. The consolidation

of several mines into a single ventilation system and the construction of additional ventilation shafts have significantly complicated the ventilation system topology and caused challenges in ventilation management. The shafts of the Saransk section, built after the shafts of the Industrial section, have shafts and winzes located at the seam outcrops. As mining operations deepened, the air supply routes to them lengthened; therefore, when opening deeper horizons, it was necessary to construct new air supply and ventilation shafts closer to the mine workings.

Subsequently, as a result of shaft reconstruction, the problems associated with the complexity of ventilation were resolved. A distinctive feature of the shafts in the Churubay-Nurinsky and Tenteksky districts is the significant extent of the shaft fields along the strike and the large number of ventilation shafts. On average, approximately 7100 m³ of air per ton of extraction is supplied daily to the basin. Analysis showed that only about 54% of this volume of air is used for ventilating mining faces and preparatory headings. About 35% is used for ventilating supported workings, which is explained by their considerable extent, complex network topology, and irrational air distribution within the shaft.

Table 1 presents the main technical characteristics of the operational ventilation shafts of the Karaganda basin mines. From the table, it is evident that all basin mines are supplied with air in excess of the design quantity, i.e., they have reserves for increasing production capacity.

A different situation is observed regarding the use of air-supplying shafts: more than half of them operate at only 50...60% of their throughput capacity. This difference in the utilization of air-supplying and ventilation shafts is explained by the fact that, as a rule, at all mines, when new horizons were opened, new air-supplying shafts were driven, designed in most cases to provide air supply for the long-term operation of the mine. With the increase in mining depth, this reserve will constantly decrease.

Table 1. Main technical characteristics of ventilation shafts of the operating mines of the Karaganda Basin

Name of mines	Number of shafts		Maximum throughput Shaft capacity, m/s ³	
	Air-supplying	Ventilation	Air-delivering	Ventilation
1. n. a. Kostenko	4	5	1004	1207
2. n. a. Kuzembaev	1	3	454	573
3. Saranskaya	2	3	673	794
4. Abayskaya	2	3	534	793
5. Kazakhstanskaya	3	5	795	916
6. n. a. Lenin	6	7	930	1024

Name of mines	Number of shafts		Maximum throughput Shaft capacity, m/s ³	
	Air-supplying	Ventilation	Air-delivering	Ventilation
7. Shakhtinskaya	2	3	531	534
8. Tentekskaya	3	4	806	608
9. n.a. Gorbachev	3	4	773	1172
10. Kirovskaya	4	6	604	646
11. named after Baizhanov	2	3	422	496

Before the restructuring of the mine stock in the Karaganda basin, there were 180 vertical and 25 inclined shafts (an average of 7 shafts per mine). In addition, another 40 shafts were planned for development. However, according to the analysis of the results of depression surveys, the utilization of the shafts' maximum throughput capacity relative to the actual volume of supplied air ranged between 50% and 80%. Furthermore, the concentration of methane gas in the total outgoing airflows has been and remains significantly below the maximum allowable norms, fluctuating within the range of 0.25...0.40% (0.75% is permitted according to PB). However, this does not imply that the shafts possess significant air supply reserves, which is due to the rather complex ventilation scheme. Analysis of air distribution in the shafts showed that, on average, about 54% of the total airflow is consumed for ventilating the working faces, while the amount used for ventilating the preparatory faces is nearly twice as low. However, in some shafts with high gas content, the airflow rate supplied to the preparatory faces exceeds that required for ventilation of extraction operations.

Changes in the mechanization equipment of mining operations, characterized primarily by their productivity, necessitate revising the methods for determining the parameters of the shaft's technological scheme (TS) and its individual subsystems.

Under current conditions of mining development, both when justifying rational schemes for opening, preparation, and mining of seams, and when studying underground mining processes, a systematic approach is applied as an objective necessity in selecting project and technological solutions. The shaft is regarded as a complex system composed of subsystems interconnected across space and time. These subsystems are defined according to the purpose, objectives, and subject of the research. In order to substantiate the parameters of technological schemes when designing shafts of a new technical level, the shaft is presented as a complex system formed through the synthesis of rational technological schemes of subsystems and their parameters. To date, such substantiation has been carried out using mid-basin or mid-industry standards, resulting in the creation of static (i.e., incapable of evolving across space and time) models that address a limited range

of tasks. Such mathematical models constrained the justification process itself, leading to the necessity of developing an optimization mechanism tailored to the specific research task.

The use of high-performance equipment in the excavation of mine workings and coal extraction has necessitated the integrated consideration of TS parameters for opening, preparation, and development systems, alongside the parameters of technological processes within the mine. To this end, a new approach is proposed for developing a model to substantiate the rational parameters of the TS, created through the establishment of an integrated dynamic system for opening, preparation, and extraction of reserves. During its development, the fundamental conditions for subsystem allocation were established as follows:

- their functional and technological homogeneity;
- a clearly defined hierarchy of internal structure;
- internal logical interconnection and multivariate development potential.

In accordance with this, the first-order mine subsystems were delineated as:

I – the «Reserves» subsystem, consisting of elements such as exposed, prepared, and ready-for-extraction reserves;

II – the subsystem of technological schemes for shaft exposure, preparation, and deposit extraction systems;

III – technological process schemes that realize these technological schemes over time and space, considered in turn as complex second-order systems.

The technological scheme ‘shaft ventilation’ is regarded as a complex system, whose parameters depend on numerous factors, including the opening and preparation schemes, systems for developing the number of simultaneously active extraction and preparatory faces, as well as the length of supported mine workings. They are largely determined by the volumes and efficiency of degassing activities during the preparation period of reserves for extraction. That is, the parameters of the ventilation TS are formed under the influence of both qualitative and quantitative parameters of other subsystems within the mine’s technological scheme.

The objects of the study are TS for opening (X_1), preparation (X_2), and mining systems (X_3) of the mine (extraction) field, as well as technological equipment for mine ventilation. The subject of the study is the parameters of the objects and their interrelationship. The purpose of the study is to establish the regularities governing the formation of the parameters of the technological process of mine ventilation as a whole under the influence of the parameters of the TS and technological equipment.

The set of design-solution calculation variants () is a combination of the number of variants representing possible compatible combinations of TS X_1 , X_2 , X_3 which form the parameters of the second-order subsystem, that is,

$$\tilde{N}_{\text{PB}} = \{X_1, X_2, X_3\},$$

then the parameters of the ventilation network can be determined as

$$Q_B = \{X_1, X_2, X_3, X_c\}, \text{ m}^3/\text{min.},$$

$$X_c = \{T_{c_1}, T_{c_2}, T_{c_3}, T_{c_4}\}$$

where $T_{c_1}, T_{c_2}, T_{c_3}, T_{c_4}$ is the set of parameters of the processes of, respectively, stoping and development operations, maintenance of mine workings, and mine ventilation.

The parameters of mine ventilation networks are determined on the basis of the distribution of air quantity among the ventilation objects of stoping and development faces, as well as the system of mine workings. The initial information for calculating the parameters of the mine ventilation TS consists of the parameters of technological processes of its other subsystems, the mining and geological conditions of seam occurrence, and the mining-engineering characteristics of the elements of mine ventilation networks.

The studies conducted, based on an analysis of a large number of observations of air distribution in mines according to ventilation log data, made it possible to obtain relationships for the demand for air supplied for mine ventilation:

– in stoping operations (m^3/min):

$$Q_B^{oc} = k_n^{oc} \times 2000(0,443m_{oc} - 0,185) \times (0,846q^{0,79} - 1,014), \quad (1)$$

– in development operations (m^3/min):

$$Q_B^{np} = 1200 \times k_n^{np} \times [0,05 \times \exp(0,15m_{np}) + 0,81] \times (0,971 + 0,286 \times Ly_d) \times (0,869q^{0,617} - 3,119), \quad (2)$$

– in maintaining workings (m^3/min):

$$Q_B^{nb} = k_n^{nb} \times 1200(0,964 + 0,00001L_{под}) \times 0,24 \times q^{0,023}, \quad (3)$$

where Ly_d – specific volume of mine working excavation, $\text{m}^3/1000 \text{ t}$ of production;

$L_{под}$ – length of maintained workings in the mine, m ;

m_{oc} and m_{nb} – the number of stoping and development faces, respectively, operating simultaneously in the mine;

q – absolute methane emission rate of the mine, m^3/min .

k_n^{oc} , k_n^{np} , k_n^{nb} – air loss coefficient in stoping, in the workings being driven and maintained.

Graphs of the obtained relationships are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Graphs of the dependence of the quantity of air supplied for ventilation of maintained workings and simultaneously operating production and development faces

Q_b – quantity of air; $L_{под}$ – length of the maintained workings; $m_{оз}$, $m_{пз}$ – number of production and development faces

Analysis of the distribution of the air supplied to the mine among the ventilation objects makes it possible to represent its total volume as

$$Q_b = 1,10 \times 1,05 \times 1440(Q_b^{оч} + Q_b^{np} + Q_b^{пв}), \text{ m}^3/\text{day}, \quad (4)$$

where 1.10 is the coefficient of non-uniform air distribution in the mine;

1.05, the coefficient accounting for air consumption for the ventilation of other facilities.

The quantity of air supplied to the mine at time t (Q_{θ}) must ensure the safe operation of all mine subsystems. During the construction of new mines, the substantiation of ventilation network parameters is based on ensuring the maximum load on the mine. This determines the selection of opening schemes, the optimal location of shafts, their diameter, and their depth. The basis for establishing the ventilation network in this case is the load on the production face that is feasible given the mining and geological conditions of occurrence and the technical characteristics of the extraction equipment, as well as the number of production faces operating simultaneously. The sequence for establishing the parameters in this case may be as follows: marketable coal production taking into account market demand, methane emission rate of the mine, daily load on the production face, number of production faces, preparation scheme and mining system, length of horizontal and inclined workings, opening scheme, required air quantity for normal ventilation, mine ventilation scheme, and ventilation system parameters. The

construction of new horizons in an operating mine necessitates the coordination of the parameters of technological schemes for opening and preparation with the parameters of the existing ventilation system and its technical capabilities. This is due to the fact that the shafts involved in the mine ventilation system cannot be reconstructed to increase the volume of supplied air. Consequently, when substantiating the parameters of technological schemes (TS) for opening and preparing new horizons, they must be coordinated with the parameters of the mine ventilation system. The substantiation of the mine TS parameters must be based, in addition to verification against other criteria, on verification according to the criterion of supplying all subsystems of underground coal mining with the required quantity of air. The substantiation of the TS parameters and the evaluation of the efficiency of the ventilation system operation can be performed using the model

$$Q_{\theta_i} - \sum_g^G Q_{\theta_{ig}} \geq 0,$$

$$\sum_u^U Q_{\text{вент}_{iu}} - Q_{\theta_i} \geq 0,$$

provided that

$$\frac{\alpha_{\text{аэ}} \times P_{\text{сгб}} \times H_{\text{сгб}} \times \sum_i^n Q_{\theta_{ti}}}{S_{\text{сгб}}^3} \leq h_{\text{ош}}^{\text{max}}$$

where i is the index of the ventilation network, $i=1,2,\dots,n$;

u is the fan index, $u=1,2,\dots,U$;

$Q_{\text{в}_{ti}}$ – the quantity of air for ventilating the i -th network at time t , $\text{m}^3/\text{min.}$,

$$Q_{\theta_{ig}} = \sum_g^G Q_{\theta_{ig}}$$

$Q_{\text{в}_{tig}}$ – quantity of air for ventilating the g -th facility at time t , $\text{m}^3/\text{min.}$;

$h_{\text{ош}}^{\text{max}}$ – maximum permissible value of total mine depression, mm water column;

$\alpha_{\text{аэ}}$ – coefficient of aerodynamic resistance, $\text{kgf} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{m}^4$;

$P_{\text{сгб}}, H_{\text{сгб}}$ – the shaft perimeter and its depth, respectively, m;

$Q_{\text{вент}_{iu}}$ – capacity of the u -th ventilation installation, $\text{m}^3/\text{min.}$

Analysis of the ratio of the calculated quantity of air required for supply to the mine to the maximum possible throughput capacity of the air-supplying shafts, given the current state of development of mining operations, shows that the air provision of mines is 110...160%; that is, stoping and development operations are supplied with air at 100%, although significant air losses occur. The presented

data on the throughput capacity of the shafts of operating mines in the Karaganda Basin confirm the availability of reserves in the mines' air supply capacity.

The substantiation of mine ventilation parameters is performed using the developed model for the formation of direct costs

The dependencies of the amount of air supplied for ventilation on the influencing factors (1), (2), (3), as well as the total volume of air supplied to the mine (4), form the basis for modeling the costs associated with the process.

Modeling of mine ventilation costs (rubles/day) is carried out by cost items: materials (C_{vm}), depreciation (C_{va}), electricity (C_{ve}), wages (C_{vzp}). Ventilation costs per 1 t of output for the mine as a whole at time t will amount to:

$$C_{\sigma_t} = \frac{C_{\sigma M_t} + C_{\sigma a_t} + C_{\sigma \varepsilon_t} + C_{\sigma \varepsilon n_t}}{\sum_{j \in t}^{m(t)} D_{cym_{tj}} + \sum_{l \in t}^{L(t)} D_{cym_{tl}}}, \text{ monetary units/t,}$$

Electricity costs:

$$C_{B\varepsilon} = W_B \times C_{\varepsilon l} \times k_{\max} N, \text{ monetary units/day,}$$

where W_B is the total electricity consumption by all fans, kWh/day;

$$W_B = \sum_{k=1}^K W_{\text{вент}_k},$$

k – fan index, $k=1, 2, \dots, K$;

$W_{\text{вент}_k}$ – electricity consumption by the k -th fan, kWh/day,

for the k -th fan [122]

$$W_{\text{вент}} = \frac{9,81 \times 24 \times Q_B \times h}{102 \times \eta_B \times \eta_{\text{дв}}}, \text{ кВт} \cdot \text{ч/сут.},$$

η_B – fan efficiency;

$\eta_{\text{дв}}$ – fan motor efficiency;

h – total mine depression;

Q_B – fan capacity, m^3/s .

Depreciation costs

$$C_{\sigma a} = kn_B \times \sum_{b=1}^B C_{\text{воб}_b} \times H_{\sigma a_b}, \text{ monetary units/day,}$$

where kn_B – coefficient accounting for the cost of auxiliary equipment; for aggregated calculations, $kn_B = 1.25$;

$H_{\sigma a}$ – daily depreciation rate of ventilation equipment, $H_{\sigma a} = 0.0085$;

$C_{\text{воб}}$ – book value of ventilation equipment at the mine, monetary units;

Material costs:

$$C_{em} = \frac{k_{n\theta} \times k_{34\theta}}{T_2} \times \sum_{b=1}^B U_{\theta\theta b}, \text{ monetary units/day,}$$

where $k_{34\theta}$ – coefficient accounting for expenditures on materials and spare parts; for aggregated calculations, $k_{34\theta}=0.06$.

Labor costs:

$$C_{B3\Pi} = k_{ДВ} \times N_{CM} \times \sum_{b=1}^B H_{обс_b} T_4, \text{ monetary units/day,}$$

where $k_{ДВ}$ is the coefficient of supplementary payments to workers relative to tariff rates, $k_{ДВ}=1.74$;

– service standard for the b -th fan, persons/shift.

Mine costs per 1 m³ of air supplied to the mine:

$$\bar{C}_\theta = \frac{C_{em} + C_{ea} + C_{e\theta} + C_{e3n}}{Q_\theta}, \text{ monetary units/m}^3.$$

When developing a model for the joint optimization of the parameters of technological processes and technological schemes of mine subsystems, constraints are introduced on the throughput capacity of air-supply and ventilation shafts, as well as a check of whether the technical characteristics of fan installations correspond to the overall mine pressure drop, with linkage to the application software package used at mines for ventilation calculations.

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